

Pensacola Theological Seminary

**Characteristics Identified That Contributed to the Survival and Revitalization
of Two Independent Baptist Churches—A Multiple Case Study**

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By

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Preface

The project director for this research has pastored three churches, each needing revitalization. His pastoral efforts began in 2000 when he began a church in his home. He then moved his effort into a church building whose last remaining membership was about to leave. The ministry at this church lasted for six years. The author's next church was a one-year effort. Although the experience at the next church was problematic on many levels, the author reflects on it as a learning experience and as a bridge to the future. The author has been at his current church for nine years, and it has also been a significant challenge. This church was founded in 1979 and eventually, because of sin and severe dysfunction, completely shut down and eventually replanted in 2010. Based on the author's personal experience with struggling churches and the lack of research material specific to the revitalization of Independent Baptist churches, he desired to design a research project that specifically sought to understand the revitalization process of Independent Baptist churches. The following pages describe this research.

Abstract

Although many denominations of American Christianity have placed an emphasis on church revitalization, no significant emphasis (academic or popular) on church revitalization has been witnessed among Independent Baptist churches. This paper reports the author's first approach to revitalization research among Independent Baptist churches. This research focuses on two churches that have been successfully revitalized. Personal interviews were conducted with the lead pastors of these two churches. Also, six individuals (two lead pastors and four other church ministers) were given a 176-point questionnaire, which all participants filled out twice: once as they recalled what the church had been like when they first arrived and once to describe what the church is like currently.

These questionnaires and interviews were combined in a mixed-methods research software called Dedoose; and valuable information, including revitalization themes (for current application and future research), was gained through the resulting analysis. The top five characteristics of revitalization associated with the survival and recovery of the two studied churches were leadership, community engagement, discipleship, evangelism, and programmatic emphasis. Because those in leadership consistently pursued and applied these revitalization factors, each church overcame problems and has continued to advance to the present day.

Introduction

Much research has been done on church revitalization among various denominations. Unfortunately, based on the researcher's investigation, little research has been done on the revitalization efforts of Independent Baptist churches. This research project aims to ignite a new era of such research. Church revitalization plays a crucial role in addressing the challenges faced by declining churches, aiming to renew their purpose, relevance, and influence.

The following information helps the reader gauge the state of American Christianity, and it lays the foundation for the present discussion. Despite some discrepancy in the statistics, current research shows that on any given Sunday, about eighteen percent of the American population attends a church of any kind.¹ Eighteen percent of America is about fifty-two million people. An often-repeated statistic reveals that approximately eighty percent of all churches in North America have reached a plateau or are declining.² More recent figures by Thom Rainer show that as of 2016, sixty-five percent of churches have plateaued or declined (nine percent and fifty-six percent, respectively), and thirty-five percent of churches are growing.³ The question of how churches are growing is also addressed by Alan Hirsch, who states that the majority of current church growth comes from “switchers”—people who move from one church to another. Hirsch indicates that there is little conversion growth in churches.⁴ In a revealing research study,

¹ Kelly Shattuck, “7 Startling Facts: An Up Close Look at Church Attendance in America,” *Church Leaders*, accessed November 7, 2016, <http://www.churchleaders.com/pastors/pastor-articles/139575-7-startling-facts-an-up-close-look-at-church-attendance-in-america.html>.

² Daniel R. Sanchez, *Church Planting Movements in North America* (Fort Worth, TX: Church Starting Network, 2007), 18.

³ Thom Rainer, “Dispelling the 80% Myth,” *Growing Healthy Churches Together* (blog), accessed June 28, 2017, <https://thomrainer.com/2017/06/dispelling-80-percent-myth-declining-churches/>.

⁴ Alan Hirsch, *Slow Church: Cultivating Community in the Patient Way of Jesus* (Downers Grove, IL: Inter Varsity Press, 2014), 50.

Earley noted that during an average year, half of all churches studied did not add one new member through conversion growth.⁵ A recent survey by Lifeway also expresses this scarcity of conversions.

Fifty-four percent of pastors say fewer than 10 people indicated a new commitment to Jesus Christ as Savior in 2018, including 8 percent who had none. In some ways, however, those numbers mask deeper evangelistic issues. When evaluating churches based on the number of conversions per 100 attendees, 67 percent had fewer than 10 per 100 people attending their church. Around a third (35 percent) had fewer than five new commitments for every 100 people attending their worship services.⁶

In 2021, Gallup researchers published new data on church membership, and the results are not encouraging. For the first time in eighty years of observation, membership in houses of worship in America dropped below fifty percent. Only forty-seven percent of the population now claims affiliation with a “house of worship.”⁷

The statistical decline in church attendance is also disturbing. In 1990, 20.4 percent of Americans attended church on a given weekend. In 2000, that number declined to 18.7 percent. By 2005, 17.5 percent of Americans went to church. Only 16.2 percent were going to church in 2010. It is estimated that only 10.7 percent of the population will be considered church attendees by 2050.⁸ Declining church attendance is highlighted in multiple statistical analyses, one of which is found in Pew’s research in Figure 1.

⁵ David B. Earley, “The Desperate Need for New Churches,” *LBTS Faculty Publications and Presentations*, Liberty Baptist Theological Seminary and Graduate School, accessed November 13, 2016, https://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1142&context=lbs_fac_pubs.

⁶ Aaron Earls, “Small, Struggling Congregations Fill U.S. Church Landscape” Lifeway Research, accessed March 6, 2019, <https://lifewayresearch.com/2019/03/06/small-struggling-congregations-fill-u-s-church-landscape/>.

⁷ Jeffery Jones, “U.S. Church Membership Falls Below Majority for First Time,” Gallup, accessed March 29, 2021, <https://news.gallup.com/poll/341963/church-membership-falls-below-majority-first-time.aspx>.

⁸ “Church Behavior Statistics,” Simple Church: A New Testament House Church Network, accessed November 12, 2016, <https://www.simplechurchathome.com/sobering-statistics/#.WCJorneZPeQ>.

In U.S., church attendance is declining

% of U.S. adults who say they attend religious services ...

Source: Pew Research Center Religious Landscape Studies (2007 and 2014). Aggregated Pew Research Center political surveys conducted 2009-July 2019 on the telephone.

"In U.S., Decline of Christianity Continues at Rapid Pace"

PEW RESEARCH CENTER

Figure 1. Church Attendance in the United States. Data from the Pew Research Center, "In U.S., Decline of Christianity Continues at Rapid Pace," published October 17, 2019, <https://www.pewforum.org/2019/10/17/in-u-s-decline-of-christianity-continues-at-rapid-pace/>.

Approximately 195 million adults in the United States are unchurched (meaning not belonging to or connected to a church).⁹ Churches lose an estimated 2,765,000 people each year to nominalism and secularism.¹⁰ Sixty percent of all children in America under the age of thirteen

⁹ Earley, "The Desperate Need for New Churches."

¹⁰ Jim Grassi, *The Spiritual Mentor*, (Harper Collins, 2013), 7, accessed November 15, 2016, <https://books.google.com/books>.

have never been to Sunday school.¹¹ Seventy percent of all teenagers in America do not attend any church.¹²

These statistics lead to certain conclusions. First, America is now recognized as the fourth largest unchurched country in the world, behind China, India, and Indonesia.¹³ Second, the decline in church attendance is unquestionable. Not only do these statistics represent a depressed Christian condition, but these statistics have also caused some concern among certain denominations, sometimes leading to unscriptural innovations (e.g., contemporary and emergent church philosophies) to try to stem the tide of decline.

The research reveals a significant problem, a great need, and a profound opportunity in the church for revitalization. Revitalization is the process of recovering a church from a struggling and ineffective ministry that has plateaued or is declining and restoring it to a vibrant gospel ministry that influences its community and world for the glory of God. A comprehensive review of the various understandings of revitalization can be found in Hudson's work.¹⁴

Revitalizing a declining church is generally a long and arduous process with many challenges. For example, in his research, Hardaway estimates that the recovery process can take anywhere from six to ten years to establish change and gain momentum.¹⁵ Suppose someone has

¹¹ "USA," BIMi Website, accessed November 18, 2016, <http://www.bimi.org/content/fiUsa.php>.

¹² J. Warner Wallace, "Are Young People Really Leaving Christianity," September 30, 2016, Updated November 24, 2016, Cold Case Christianity, accessed November 25, 2016, <http://coldcasechristianity.com/2016/are-young-people-really-leaving-christianity/>.

¹³ Bob Larson, "Reseeding America" (Lecture, New Friendship Baptist Church, Ringgold Georgia, October 5, 2014).

¹⁴ Joseph Stephen Hudson, "A Competency Model for Church Revitalization in Southern Baptist Convention Churches: A Mixed Methods Study" (Doctoral Thesis, The Southern Baptist Theological Seminary, 2017), 24.

¹⁵ Donald Lynn Hardaway, "An Evaluation of the Growing Healthy Churches Program as a Method for Producing Healthy, Growing, and Reproducing Southern Baptist Congregations" (Doctoral Thesis, Liberty Baptist Theological Seminary, 2012), 81.

never personally engaged with a revitalization ministry, especially long term. In that case, it may be difficult for them to fully grasp this type of work's value, fundamental nature, and requirements. With such a large percentage of churches in a plateaued or declining state, the need for a revitalization emphasis and revitalization ministries will continue to be necessary.

The author of this research study has pastored three churches since 2000. All three were in desperate need of revitalization. As the author sought answers, he observed that much of the literature did not approach the topic of revitalization from an Independent Baptist perspective. After an extensive literature review, the author noted that Protestant denominational schools and Southern Baptist schools dominate the revitalization landscape. Also, personal correspondence with some of the leading Independent Baptist training centers in America revealed that no single revitalization training program can be found. Because academic and popular literature emphasizing Independent Baptist church revitalization is lacking, finding targeted information to assist pastors in their desire and efforts to revitalize their churches is difficult. Some of the information available concerning revitalization is not aligned with a biblical perspective (e.g., matters of church polity, worship styles, and translation preferences), and—at best—extrapolation of existing data is piecemeal and must be adapted. Many of the revitalization techniques suggested in the literature, such as changing worship style from traditional to contemporary, potentially limit and inhibit biblical growth, renewal, and revitalization efforts in fundamental and Bible-centered Independent Baptist churches.

Chapter 1

The Research Problem

A great need exists in Independent Baptist churches for targeted and research-based information about church replanting and revitalization. Although church revitalization efforts are growing in academic and practical terms, specific contextual resources for Independent Baptists are woefully limited. Many denominational academic programs attempt to retool a pastor's mindset and skillset, thus equipping them to effectively engage the current ecclesiastical, cultural, and spiritual climate. Unfortunately, a specific academic training program for Independent Baptist church revitalization has yet to be made available to theological or educational institutions. Although researchers have studied church revitalization from various denominational perspectives, the author could locate only one study that approached the topic from an Independent Baptist perspective.¹⁶ This study will be summarized later, along with other research. This paper is offered in response to this lack of targeted research on revitalizing Independent Baptist churches.

Research Goals and Objectives

This research aimed to examine two Independent Baptist churches that experienced revitalization and identify core characteristics that other Independent Baptist churches can model. This evaluation achieved a clearer understanding of Independent Baptist church renewal and revitalization.

¹⁶ Richard T. Carns, "A Rationale for an Independent Baptist Church to Clarify Its Mission, Analyze Its Program, Prioritize Its Objectives and Revitalize Its Ministry" (Doctoral Thesis, Liberty Baptist Theological Seminary, 1993)

The process of achieving this specific research goal involved two efforts. First, an effort was made to better understand church revitalization by examining popular and academic literature concerning the topic. After the literature review, the second effort began, involving the research study of two recovered churches. This research study aimed at providing a framework to help other Independent Baptist ministers to understand the revitalization process better.

As a result of this study, the researcher gained a better understanding of (1) the research-based lifecycle (and lifespan) of the average church, (2) the key elements that can lead to ecclesiastic decline, (3) the key factors that can lead to church revitalization, (4) the various methods of assessing a local church to identify its level of health, and (5) actions necessary to initiate and maintain the revitalization effort of the local church.

Theoretical Framework

Two areas of study compose the theoretical framework for revitalizing Independent Baptist churches. The first area is the biblical theology of revitalization. God has placed in His Word a developing and unfolding expression of truth for revitalizing biblical ministries. Jeremiah's ministry, the Apostle Paul's epistles, and the Apostle John's letters to the churches of Revelation are excellent demonstrative resources for understanding a revitalization framework for ministry. The second area of study that composes the theoretical framework for revitalizing Independent Baptist churches is research literature. An extensive review of revitalization literature (both academic research and popular literature) was conducted to identify essential concepts related to revitalization.

Research Question and Methodology

Research Question

An Independent Baptist church in the Midwest faced daunting challenges threatening its existence. Instead of demise, it experienced a resurgence and renewal. Another church located in the South experienced a similar renewal. This paper has sought to answer the question, “What characteristics of these churches led to their successful revitalization?”

Research Methodology

To attain the answers to the research question, the retrospective cohort case study method was chosen. This study method is well suited to analyzing a group's experience over time. Using this method, researchers have the value of hindsight. In a retrospective cohort case study, the researcher historically analyzes one or more organizations, churches, leaders, or other ministry situations to draw conclusions about similar ministry situations. The researcher then uses the analysis to suggest ways to improve or guide a problem in ministry. According to Vhymeister, a case study has four principal parts when developed into a dissertation. The four parts are as follows:

1. Presentation: A description of what is to be studied, the case, is offered.
2. Analysis: The researcher uses various conceptual frameworks to understand the dynamics involved in the case
3. Interpretation: An attempt is made to contextualize the various aspects of the case
4. Action: A synthesis and summary of the analysis and interpretation are offered, and then an appropriate response is suggested based on all the data¹⁷

¹⁷ Nancy Jean Vyhmeister, *Your Guide to Writing Quality Research Papers for Students of Religion and Theology* (Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 2014), 61.

To identify the critical factors affecting a church's vibrancy, the author utilized a questionnaire discovered during his literature review. This questionnaire by Thom Rainer quantifies church health based on six primary categories: fellowship, evangelism, discipleship, prayer, ministry, and worship. An added category that is not used in assessing church health is doctrine. With Rainer's permission, his Church Health Report (see Appendix A) was slightly adapted to include questions assessing several issues that might influence an Independent Baptist church's revitalization potential. Kenneth Quick's Church Scan Inventory (see Appendix B) was also utilized, but only as a supplemental analysis for comparative purposes and as a description of the overall health of the studied churches. The results of the Church Scan Inventories for both churches can be found in Appendix C.

To initiate the research process for this study, the pastor of a recovered midwestern Independent Baptist church (designated as LP1) filled out the Adapted Church Health Report and the Church Scan Inventory questionnaires twice. During his first assessment, the pastor responded to the questions while remembering the church's characteristics when he first arrived as pastor. During the second assessment, the pastor answered the questions in light of the church's current characteristics. By filling out the questionnaire twice, in the manner prescribed, the church's historical trend and the influence of revitalization factors were discovered. Two other church members (FSM1 and FSM2), with adequate knowledge of the church's revitalization process, also completed these questionnaires twice according to the previous criteria. Through this method of questioning, revitalization characteristics were further clarified and confirmed within the church.

A second church, located in the South, was also analyzed for comparative and contrastive purposes. The pastor of this church was assigned LP2. As before, two other church members

(RSM1 and RSM2) were asked to complete the questionnaires. By labeling the participants in the above way, their identities were safeguarded. All data from this research study was held in strict confidence: directly identified data was not shared with anyone outside of the research effort.

In addition to the questionnaires, personal interviews with lead pastors were conducted. These interviews specifically focused on the revitalization of the individual churches and were recorded or transcribed. Afterward, the author analyzed the content to potentially identify new, enhanced, or even avoided activities that assisted in revitalizing the studied church. As this review process continued with each questionnaire and interview, common themes of revitalization were identified, as were new characteristics not covered in the questionnaires. These characteristics will be shown and discussed later.

The content gleaned from the questionnaires and two interviews was then organized using DeDoose software. This software is used to manage and analyze complex data from qualitative and mixed-methods research. After completing this investigation, the author compared the results to his current church to identify areas of congruence or divergence and areas of current and future need.

Limitations and Delimitations

Limitations

Research limitations are influences that a researcher cannot control and that restrict his methodology and conclusions. Several limitations that influenced the results of this study are identified as follows:

1. This project focused primarily on two churches. This restricted evaluation limits the extrapolation of data, thus limiting the reliability and transferability of results.
2. The setting varied between the two churches. The primary church is in the Midwest, just outside a central metropolitan area. This setting is far different from the author's church setting, a rural city located in a farming community. Could the results of this study be equally valid for churches with other geographical locations and cultures? This geographic factor is offset by the inclusion of the second church, which was located in the rural South. Although unique cultural differences existed between the Midwestern church and the Southern church, there were also what is believed to be universal revitalization characteristics uniting the two. At some point in the future, additional churches in different geographical regions could be surveyed to confirm or deny the reliability and transferability of these characteristics.
3. Religious demographics varied between the two churches. These demographic differences can lead to differences in the type or sort of ministry. As an example of these differences, the following charts identify six key groupings of people (the religious makeup of the three communities under observation) by the number of adherents. The religious demographics begin with the author's community.

Table 1.1. Chattooga County Religious Traditions, 2010

Source: Data from 2010 U.S. Religion Census: Religious Congregations and Membership Study. Collected by the Association of Statisticians of American Religious Bodies (ASARB) and distributed by the Association of Religion Data Archives (www.theARDA.com).

Table 1.2. Chattooga County Religious Traditions, 2020

Source: Data from 2020 U.S. Religion Census: Religious Congregations and Membership Study. Collected by the Association of Statisticians of American Religious Bodies (ASARB) and distributed by the Association of Religion Data Archives (www.theARDA.com).

Tables 1.1 and 1.2 reveal that opportunity exists. The unchurched population of Chattooga County stood at 52 percent (based on the population for 2010). The new statistics for 2020 reveal that the Unchurched percentage stood at 45 percent. Most of the religious landscape in Chattooga County is dominated by the Southern Baptists

and Church of Christ denominations (with a significant upsurge of Roman Catholicism). This fact alone produces a particular environment that makes revitalization efforts in Independent Baptist churches difficult, but it also makes Independent Baptists a distinctive alternative to the others.

For comparative purposes and to reveal the religious demographics of the two studied churches, the following tables are offered, showing the years 2010 and 2020.

Table 1.3. Midwestern County Religious Traditions, 2010

Source: Data from 2010 U.S. Religion Census: Religious Congregations and Membership Study. Collected by the Association of Statisticians of American Religious Bodies (ASARB) and distributed by the Association of Religion Data Archives (www.theARDA.com).

Table 1.4. Midwestern County Religious Traditions, 2020

Source: Data from 2020 U.S. Religion Census: Religious Congregations and Membership Study. Collected by the Association of Statisticians of American Religious Bodies (ASARB) and distributed by the Association of Religion Data Archives (www.theARDA.com).

The unchurched population of Hendricks County stood at fifty-nine percent (based on the total population for 2010) and sixty-one percent (based on the total population for 2020).

Also included is Table 1.5, showing the religious makeup of the area in which the southern church is located.

Table 1.5. Southern County Religious Traditions, 2010

Source: Data from 2010 U.S. Religion Census: Religious Congregations and Membership Study. Collected by the Association of Statisticians of American Religious Bodies (ASARB) and distributed by the Association of Religion Data Archives (www.theARDA.com).

Table 1.6. Southern County Religious Traditions, 2020

Source: Data from 2010 U.S. Religion Census: Religious Congregations and Membership Study. Collected by the Association of Statisticians of American Religious Bodies (ASARB) and distributed by the Association of Religion Data Archives (www.theARDA.com).

4. A fourth limitation is the social variation between church communities.

Table 1.7. Social Variations Comparison Between Studied Churches, 2021–2022

Data USA 2021/2022

	Midwestern City	Southern City	Author's City
Population	20,848 (15.5% 1 year growth)	1747 (6.85% 1 year growth)	24,898 (.29% 1 year growth)
Poverty Rate	5.31%	20%	21.5%
Median Age	36.9	42.6	45.6
Median property value	\$239,500	\$139,900	\$73,300
Median Household Income	\$92,684 (0.716% 1 year decline)	\$35,000 (0.867% 1 year decline)	\$37,946 (1.59% 1 year growth)
Number of Employees	12,000	735	9300

Source: Data from DATA USA, "Comparison - Midwestern City to a Southern City, to the Author's City," accessed April 19, 2024), <https://datausa.io/profile/geo/summerville-ga-31000US44900>.

The data from the preceding tables was vital because it showed a difference in the “kind” or “sort” of ministry conducted in the various locations. The author’s southern city church reaches a primarily poverty-laden demographic. Certain effects accompany poverty that may or may not accompany areas of greater affluence. Therefore, a ministry in an impoverished community can look very different from one in an affluent community. However, this study’s goal is not to identify characteristics that apply only within a specific demographic but to identify general characteristics of revitalization that will apply to any setting. Models for ministry may differ depending on cultural considerations, but the teaching and philosophy of Scripture should not differ.

5. Much of the background research material gleaned from this work comes from Southern Baptist and other Evangelical Protestant literature. These groups are perhaps the most conversant with the idea of church revitalization because they are facing a steep decline in the number of their churches. The author recently attended a Southern Baptist conference on revitalization and replanting (2020), in which a speaker gave the following statistic: “Southern Baptists are facing a fifteen percent church closure rate over the next five years. . . . That is about 7,050 churches. We have an average of 900 churches close every year.”¹⁸ These numbers have demanded that the Southern Baptist Convention address the decline.
6. Biblical characteristics for a New Testament church should be easily identified and understood, but one’s ministry context can skew those understandings. Therefore, caution must be used in interpreting contextual findings in church revitalization.

¹⁸ “Replant Conference,” North American Mission Board of the Southern Baptist Church, Atlanta Georgia, 2020.

7. The final limitation is memory recall. The participants were asked to remember the status of their churches when they had first arrived and during the years of their ministry in their churches. Their memory may have inaccuracies.

Delimitations

Delimitations are what a researcher chooses to include and what to exclude. The following is a list of delimitations in this study:

1. The primary focus of this research was on Independent Baptist churches. Applicability of findings will vary based upon underlying ministry philosophy and theological presuppositions.
2. Attention was focused on two churches, one in the Midwest and one in the South. This narrowing of attention (two researched churches) was done to extract and then extrapolate revitalization characteristics that apply to other churches. By comparing two churches in different geographic locations, the author provided enhanced (although limited) validity to the study's findings.
3. The retrospective cohort-case study method was used to acquire and express knowledge. This method seemed best suited to evaluate a group setting over time.

Assumptions and Presuppositions

Vhymeister states, “A presupposition is a basic understanding that undergirds one’s thinking on a given topic. Sometimes, presuppositions are called assumptions.”¹⁹ Assumptions in this research were as follows:

1. The Holy Bible is the manual providing instruction for revitalization. The Spirit of God is the agent, providing the power for renewal. The people of God are the medium, providing the vehicle for regeneration.
2. Christ founded the church. As the church's founder, Christ’s will concerning the church, as revealed in His Word, is paramount. Christ Jesus said in Matthew 16:18, “I will build my church.” No pastor owns the church that he leads. No leader or group of people owns the church. A genuine New Testament church has Christ as its leader.
3. The local church is to be primarily understood as a present, visible, called-out assembly of believers who have voluntarily organized themselves together under the leadership of Christ to carry out in this world the continued work of the Lord Jesus as identified in the Bible. Indeed, the local assembly of believers should consider themselves to be and function as Christ's visible presence in this world.
4. The local church is precious in God’s eyes, and He loves it. This fact should motivate all who are part of the church to love and cherish it.
5. The church and its health were important to the Apostle Paul. He gave the better part of his life, at the command of Christ, for the establishment and continued prosperity of the local church. Most New Testament churches had problems—some more than others, such

¹⁹ Vhymeister, *Your Guide to Writing Quality Research Papers*, 101.

as the Corinthian Church. The Apostle Paul lovingly and courageously nurtured them and sought to bring them to a fuller measure of Christlikeness. Paul's second and third missionary journeys were dedicated to strengthening and equipping the previously established Christians and churches (called *confirming* in the New Testament—Acts 14:21-23; 15:23, 41).

6. Churches can decline and even cease to exist, although they do not have to. The churches named in the second and third chapters of Revelation provide fascinating insight when considering church health in its biblical fullness. It is observed that Christ was fully willing to remove a church—"remove thy candlestick" (Rev. 2:5)—and forsake a church—"spue thee out of my mouth" (Rev. 3:16)—leaving it to its own devices. Technically, these churches would be separated from Christ, but potentially still existing. Amid this tragic circumstance, hope remains that Christ can return and bring healing to that body of believers, even if it be through one individual (Rev. 3:20). Revitalizers must be exceedingly wise. Reviving a church that Christ has removed or forsaken can be a destructive and debilitating lesson. Although the average church has a typical lifespan, the survival and vitality of a church can be lengthened by overcoming poor patterns of decline.
7. Christ can revive and restore any church at any time and place. From a philosophical, theological, and practical standpoint, ministry renewal among Independent Baptist churches is possible. A widespread cultural decline crisis among churches (Independent Baptist churches not excluded) exists today. This issue must be addressed with bibliocentric, Spirit-filled wisdom. Pastors and pastors in training must have their mindsets refreshed and their tools sharpened so that the Lord may use them to revitalize

churches in decline. Valid guidance and resources specific to the needs of Independent Baptist churches must be provided for the reclamation of individual churches and possibly global revival.

Definition of Terms

Recovered (Revitalized) Church: A recovered church in the context of this paper is a church that has experienced recovery after a severe decline. This recovery is objectively evidenced by the church having returned to a fully functioning, self-governing, self-supporting, self-propagating assembly. This recovery is, of necessity, a continuous and fluid process, yet it can also be objectively observed within the six primary categories of church health—Fellowship, Evangelism, Discipleship, Prayer, Ministry, and Worship—as mentioned in Rainer’s Church Health Report questionnaire.²⁰

Revitalization: Revitalization is the process of renewing a church that is declining. This process initiates and proceeds primarily by making changes from within that will enhance and improve the current church's health, vitality, and viability. This process may (and often does) include outside resources and help.

Replanting: The term replanting refers to closing a church and restarting another one. The church gives up its autonomy to an outside entity for the purpose of placing another church. This process is different from planting a new church. It is a radical form of church revitalization that requires the previous church to cease to exist in name and structure and surrender its autonomy and sovereignty to an outside agent (preferably another church). Still, once the church is

²⁰ Mark Clifton and Kenneth Priest, *Rubicons of Revitalization*, (Littleton, CO: Acoma Press, 2018), Table of Contents.

replanted, it exists alongside remnants of the previous church (buildings, property, members, etc.). This process could also be called *relaunching*.

Contribution to Ministry

This project has contributed to the author's personal growth, understanding, and skills in the following ways:

1. The project pulled together years of study and compiled the material in a comprehensive and organized format.
2. The project provided the opportunity to solidify and correct beliefs as the material was reviewed.
3. The project gave the author the opportunity to present a formalized understanding of Independent Baptist church revitalization, an understanding that he can now express formally with others in the future.
4. The project enabled the author to further his current church, a replant that has significantly struggled.
5. The project provided the opportunity to package the research in a way that can be presented in educational institutions or seminars, for group benefit and encouragement.
6. The project served as a thorough overview to other Independent Baptist churches that need instruction concerning revitalization. If a church can be revitalized rather than vilified and marginalized, it can offer hope and refreshment to its community once again.

7. The project provided a platform to develop two ministries that help support the work of Independent Baptist church revitalization: Hometown Hope Ministries and Ministry Medicine International.

Overview of the Rest of the Project

The rest of the project is organized to provide greater focus and clarity to Independent Baptist church revitalization efforts. Biblical and theological perspectives on revitalization are considered, and research and popular literature on revitalization are examined and summarized. This project also discusses methodology related to the current study, including data collection and results. Further, the project summarizes the research problem and question, including a discussion and interpretation of each finding. The strengths, weaknesses, and limitations of the study are also considered, and the extent to which each research goal was reached is evaluated and discussed. Finally, the author evaluates how completing the study contributed to his personal growth. Implications for broader ministry are later presented, and recommendations for further research are offered. Closing statements discuss different aspects concerning the significance of the study.

Chapter 2

The Project in Perspective

This research project aimed to identify the characteristics that contributed to the survival and revitalization of two Independent Baptist churches. Any study related to ministry requires a biblical foundation. In addition to a biblical foundation, this research study includes a review of recent literature related to the purpose of the research. This literature review assessed the current state of knowledge and the theoretical framework related to church revitalization, a framework that provides justification and contextualization for the current research effort.

Two considerations are offered in understanding the theoretical framework related to church revitalization: biblical and theological perspectives on revitalization and research literature focusing on this subject.

Theological Perspectives

Scripture provides three key pericopes and four key concepts to assist in the understanding of church revitalization. Three critical areas of Scripture that were studied are the book of Jeremiah, the Epistles of Paul, and the seven churches of Asia Minor mentioned in Revelation chapters two and three. The four fundamental concepts are *return*, *restoration*, *church*, and *order*. These four concepts will be explained later.

The Old Testament was written for learning and admonition, and it can serve as a foundational platform upon which to build an understanding of church revitalization (Rom. 15:4; 1 Cor. 10:11). Though the church is a New Testament phenomenon, the Old Testament book of Jeremiah was intended to teach and admonish and may be referred to when considering church

revitalization. Emphasizing the book of Jeremiah alongside the topic of church revitalization is not an attempt to establish any direct Old Testament connection with the New Testament church: it is intended to merely highlight an Old Testament revitalization principle and enhance an understanding of this biblical concept. In the book, Jeremiah ministers to a dying nation that is soon disbanded, only to be regathered and reinvigorated seventy years later. From start to finish, the book of Jeremiah is a manual on the efforts needed to initiate (or at least lay the groundwork for) the revitalization of a dying ministry.

Although the book of Jeremiah does not include the words *revive*, *revival*, and *reviving*, the English word *return* is found fifty-two times. The root of the word *return* is שׁוּב (šûb). The word means to “go back.”²¹ One of the many nuanced meanings of the word’s root is turning away from sin, conceived of as returning to God or returning from a location.²² Returning to the Lord is the essence of revival. Without the work of returning, there can be no revival blessing. An example of this root word being used is שׁוּבוּ (šûbû). This word is found four times in the book of Jeremiah (3:14, 22; 18:11; 25:5) and is translated as *turn* or *return*. This word is a command given to the children of Judah if the Lord is to respond to them favorably.

Another foundational word in Jeremiah's book concerning the nation's revitalization is *repent*. The word *repent* occurs in the book of Jeremiah but never in the context of the people repenting. The eleven times it appears (Jer. 26:3, 13, 19) shows the Lord repenting concerning the judgment He intends upon Judah if only they will return unto Him. Feinberg states concerning the Lord’s repentance: “With God, repentance is not a change of mind but his

²¹ David J. A. Clines, ed., *The Dictionary of Classical Hebrew* (Sheffield, England: Sheffield Academic Press; Sheffield Phoenix Press, 1993–2011), 273.

²² Logos Bible Study Software, Bible Sense Lexicon, accessed June 27, 2023.

consistent response according to his changeless nature to the nation's conduct."²³ Implied in the repentance of the Lord concerning Judah is the concept of *restoration*.

The word *restore* occurs only two times in the book of Jeremiah (27:22; 30:17). Restoration for Judah would be impossible until the nation was shut down and carried away into captivity. This experience may apply to church revitalization as well. Although replanting a church for it to live again is not always necessary, sometimes no restoration or renewal can come until the work is completely shut down.

The concept of the church is a central theme of the Bible. The local church is a New Testament phenomenon. The word *church* is found 114 times from Matthew to Revelation. In the New Testament, the concept of churches being assessed and strengthened is an underlying theme of the Apostolic work among churches (Acts 15:36), as revealed in the epistolary literature. The Apostle Paul constantly interacted with churches to keep them strong and healthy. For example, the Apostle Paul encouraged Titus, who was in a challenging ministry, to "set in order the things that are wanting" (Titus 1:5). This admonition may involve putting in place things that had not been placed or recovering and reordering items that had been lost. This principle of setting things in order runs through much of Paul's teaching on the church and was designed to remedy problems and restore churches to a greater level of vitality (as were his second and third missionary journeys).

Understanding the Greek word for *order* is helpful to properly understanding the order principle in the Pastoral Epistles. In Titus 1:5, the manuscript form of this word is ἐπιδιορθῶση (epidiorthōsē). The *Lemma* (dictionary listing) is ἐπιδιορθόω (epidiorthoō). Titus 1:5 is the only place this particular word is found in the Bible. As will be further clarified below, ἐπιδιορθόω

²³ Charles Feinberg, *Jeremiah: A Commentary*, (Grand Rapids: The Zondervan Corporation, 1982), 135.

(epidiorthoō) means to bring a higher level of order and organization to something so that it might operate at a more efficient and effective level. This word ἐπιδιορθόω does not imply temporality or causality. In other words, ἐπιδιορθόω (epidiorthoō) does not tell when, why, or how the disorder or disorganization occurred; it merely indicates that something is lacking and that this lack must be corrected. The Greek root of ἐπιδιορθόω (epidiorthoō) is ὀρθος (orthos), meaning “rightly or correctly.” This root word (ὀρθος) and its variations are found fifteen times in the New Testament and three times in the Pastoral Epistles.²⁴ These three references in the epistolary literature are listed here in Greek, with the Greek word of emphasis underlined and defined.²⁵ The references are from Scrivener’s *The New Testament in Greek*.²⁶

The basic understanding of this word for *order* is further clarified by various Greek authorities. Louw and Nida state the following: “62.4 - ἐπιδιορθόω (epidiorthoō): to cause matters to be ordered correctly—‘to set right, to correct, to put into order.’ ἀπέλιπόν σε ἐν Κρήτῃ, ἵνα τὰ λείποντα ἐπιδιορθώσῃ ‘I left you in Crete for you to put in order the things that still needed doing’ Titus 1:5.”²⁷ *Word Pictures in the New Testament*, by Archibald Thomas Robertson states concerning this word: “Things were out of order from the beginning (things left undone), or something happened to cause things to be out of order (things that survived).”²⁸

²⁴ The Lexham Analytical Lexicon to the Greek New Testament, Logos Bible Software, 2011.

²⁵ **2 Timothy 2:15** - σπούδασον σεαυτὸν δόκιμον παραστήσαι τῷ Θεῷ, ἐργάτην ἀνεπαίσχυντον, ὀρθοτομοῦντα (orthotomounta - “rightly dividing” - To guide along a straight path - to cut in a straight line) τὸν λόγον τῆς ἀληθείας. **2 Timothy 3:16** - πᾶσα γραφὴ θεόπνευστος καὶ ὠφέλιμος πρὸς διδασκαλίαν, πρὸς ἔλεγχον, πρὸς ἐπανόρθωσιν (epanorthōsin - “correction” - improvement, restoration, correcting), πρὸς παιδείαν τὴν ἐν δικαιοσύνῃ· **Titus 1:5** - Τοῦτου χάριν κατέλιπόν σε ἐν Κρήτῃ, ἵνα τὰ λείποντα ἐπιδιορθώσῃ (epidiorthōsē - “thou shouldst set in order” - set right), καὶ καταστήσῃς κατὰ πόλιν πρεσβυτέρους, ὡς ἐγὼ σοι διαταξάμην·

²⁶ F. H. A. Scrivener, *The New Testament in Greek*, (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1881).

²⁷ Johannes P. Louw and Eugene Albert Nida, *Greek-English Lexicon of the New Testament: Based on Semantic Domains* (New York: United Bible Societies, 1996), 611.

²⁸ Archibald Thomas Robertson, *Word Pictures in the New Testament*, vol. 4, The Epistles of Paul (Grand Rapids: Baker Book House, 1931), 598.

James Swanson's work records the following: "2114 ἐπιδιορθόω (epidiorthoō): vb.; ≡ Str 1930—LN 62.4 put into order, straighten out, correct (Tit 1:5)."²⁹ Alexander Souter states the following about ἐπιδιορθόω (epidiorthoō): "I put besides into a state of order, I put in order."³⁰ James Strong gives a helpful understanding of this word as well: his original description of the word in question (ἐπιδιορθόω - epidiorthoō) is given in Appendix C. Each word listed in his description is defined for a fuller and deeper understanding of ἐπιδιορθόω (epidiorthoō). He writes, "1930. ἐπιδιορθόω ἔπιδιόρθω, ep-ee-dee-or-thō'-o; from 1909 and a der. of 3717; to straighten further, i.e. (fig.) arrange additionally:—set in order."³¹ All of these descriptions provide a clearer picture of the understanding of this word.

Further insight is gained by studying the morphology of ἐπιδιορθόω (see Appendix D). So then, the entire meaning of this word, ἐπιδιορθόω, is to order things rightly so that the ordered things might be brought to a higher level of usefulness, efficiency, and effectiveness. This definition necessarily implies application. The application of this principle is seen throughout the Pauline epistles and specifically in the pastoral epistles. In the culture Paul, Titus, and Timothy ministered in, churches could easily become disordered in their practice. Titus went to Crete to set in order the things that were wanting. Timothy went to Ephesus, where much in that local assembly needed ordering. In the epistles, topics such as doctrine, leadership, church government, the home, false teaching and teachers, eschatology, the Christian life, worship, prayer, and the role of women in the church were dealt with to help the churches order themselves correctly.

²⁹ James Swanson, *Dictionary of Biblical Languages with Semantic Domains: Greek New Testament* (Oak Harbor: Logos Research Systems, Inc., 1997).

³⁰ Alexander Souter, *A Pocket Lexicon to the Greek New Testament* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1917), 92.

³¹ James Strong, *A Concise Dictionary of the Words in the Greek Testament and The Hebrew Bible* (Bellingham, WA: Logos Bible Software, 2009), 31.

The second and third chapters of Revelation also discuss the biblical concept of church revitalization. In this passage, the concept of revitalization is observed through the cycle of remembering, repenting, and returning. It also demonstrates that churches can decline and even cease to exist, as Christ was willing to *remove* a church—“remove thy candlestick” (Rev. 2:5)—and forsake a church, leaving it to its own devices—“spue thee out of my mouth” (Rev. 3:16). Technically, these churches would be separated from Christ but potentially still existing. Amid this tragic circumstance, hope remains that Christ can return and bring healing to that individual body, even if it be through one individual (Rev. 3:20).

If revitalization characteristics are biblical then they must of necessity be timeless and universal. Biblical truths are not bound by chronological, denominational, cultural, national, geographical, racial or ethnic barriers. In the various studies that will be considered next, one must make this qualifying observation: both Bible doctrines and biblical revitalization principles are being dealt with. There must be discernment between the principles and the doctrines.

Conclusion of Theological Perspectives

This study's biblical framework for church revitalization includes three key pericopes and four key concepts. Jeremiah ministered to a dying nation. Jeremiah's message to his nation was to *return* to God. If the people did so, God would *repent* concerning the impending judgment upon the nation, and the people would be restored and blessed. In the epistles he penned, Paul urged the churches to arrange things in the church's life properly. This biblical order was designed to bring those churches to a more effective level of service and secure them from influences and issues that would lead to their decline. The seven churches of Asia Minor

mentioned in the second and third chapters of Revelation needed counsel and direction from the Lord. As these churches repented and engaged the Lord's direction, they were preserved, and the potential for decline and demise was averted. This biblical framework encourages the understanding that, although decline and demise are an ever-present reality, God has placed within His Word directions that can lead to recovery and revitalization.

As one returns to the four key concepts, he is reminded that *return*, *restoration*, *church*, and *order* support the basic underlying theme of revitalization found throughout the Old and New Testament Scriptures. Grounding the work of revitalization in biblical theology is important to creating the proper motivation and approach to this important expression of faith.

Foundational Literature on Revitalization

Although Scripture presents revitalization as a theological concept, this current investigative effort is also informed by thinkers and practitioners of revitalization and upon previous academic research on the subject. The material discussed next provides an understanding of the history and application of church revitalization in various contexts. It provides valuable content to continue building a theoretical paradigm of Independent Baptist Church revitalization.

This literature review employed a systematic search across relevant academic databases, including but not limited to Proquest and Google Scholar, with some studies appearing in both. The investigation used keywords such as *church revitalization*, *church lifecycle*, *church assessment*, *revitalization leadership*, *revitalization strategies*, and *revitalization theology*. The review was initially limited to include scholarly works published within the last five years (2018–2023) to ensure recent research and insights were included. However, older studies were

also included in this review. The reason these older studies were included is two-fold. First, although contexts change, biblical doctrines never change. Biblical principles have to be interpreted and applied based upon their context; each biblical principle is guided by overarching and unchanging Bible doctrines, (e.g., the holiness of God). Second, reviewing older studies allows for a historical perspective. Including older studies with newer ones showed consistency in revitalization themes and revealed four themes related to revitalization: (1) church lifecycle, (2) church assessment and health, (3) revitalization leadership, and (4) revitalization strategies.

Church Lifecycle Literature

Church lifecycle is a term used to describe a church's predictable pattern of existence, going through various stages that are patterned after the stages of human existence. Study of a church's lifecycle grew out of research in the corporate world "with the theory that organizations tend to mirror human lifecycles."³² The local church lifecycle follows this human lifecycle pattern unless direct interventions are employed to alter it.

In his 2021 dissertation, Young discusses the importance of what he terms a congregation's "single lifecycle" but then added the concept of "multiple health cycles" within the lifetime of that church.³³ In this context, Young was referencing the book *To Dream Again* (1981) by Robert Dale, who mentions a church lifecycle of five stages (birth, growth, maturity, decline, and death) but then adds to this understanding a "health cycle." Multiple "health cycles"

³² Greg Wiens, "A Season for Everything – Life Cycle of a Church," *Healthy Growing Churches*, HGC Blog, last modified May 15, 2018, accessed April 21, 2023, <https://healthygrowingchurches.com/a-season-for-everything-life-cycle-of-a-church/>.

³³ Nathan Young, "The Development of an Assessment Plan for the Leaders of Grace Church of Alpharetta, Georgia to Begin a Church Revitalization Initiative," 70–71.

can occur within the single lifecycle of an individual church. The health cycle includes the following stages: (1) Dream, (2) Beliefs, (3) Goals, (4) Structure, (5) Ministry, (6) Nostalgia, (7) Questioning, (8) Polarization, and (9) Dropout. After *To Dream Again* was published, two significant men in the field of church lifecycle (Jere Allen and George Bullard) began collaborating with Dale on the study of church lifecycle.

Bullard's work on the lifecycle of the church has been the gold standard in this area, and his investigations into the organizational lifecycle of churches began in the 1970s and crystalized in 1981 with his first version of the congregational lifecycle, called *Shaping a Future for the Church in a Changing Community*, in which he worked with Jere Allen. Bullard identified that there are time-related patterns in the life of churches, barring any major dysfunctional events or dramatic divine intervention.³⁴ Bullard recently explained, via email communication, the history and emphasis of his church lifecycle interest, and he summarized the development and validation of his church lifecycle theory. He states,

I first developed it (the church lifecycle idea) in the mid-to-late 1970s with a colleague at the Home Mission Board of the Southern Baptist Convention. We field-tested it with dozens of churches. We and others have used it with thousands of churches. I have been the primary owner of the various versions since the mid-1980s. It was updated every several years based on things we learned through our field testing and through new research and books published by others, particularly in the business world, about organizational life cycles. In recent years I have applied the pattern of Leviticus 25:1-12 to the various stages. The original design was inspired by Carl Dudley (then with McCormick Seminary in Chicago) in the mid-1970s who wrote an article on the stages of decline and death of churches reflecting the stages of death and dying popularized by Elizabeth Kubler-Ross. It was not developed by a left-brained scientific model, but by our initial hunches, continual field testing, and then modifying over the years. Around 1994 we did have a researcher spend a year testing the validity of the life cycle as to where congregations found themselves on the life cycle at any given time. It showed that how we presented it to congregations was highly accurate and our guess of a congregation's

³⁴ George Bullard, "The Life Cycle and Stages of Congregational Development," accessed January 7, 2023, http://archive.bwcumc.org/toolbox/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/stages_of_church_life_bullard.pdf.

position on the life cycle from our years of experience was consistent with what the congregation said following a presentation and dialogue with them.³⁵

According to Bullard's assessment of a church's lifecycle, churches do not always fit neatly into one of the categories mentioned. Still, there usually exists a predominating trend within the church's life that identifies its stage. Year markers are associated with each stage, but age markers alone must not be used to identify stages. The lifecycle of the average church is broken down, by Bullard, into four organizing principles (Visionary Leadership, Relationship Experiences, Programmatic Emphases, and Accountable Management), ten stages (Birth, Infancy, Childhood, Adolescence, Adulthood, Maturity, Empty Nest, Retirement, Old Age, and Death), nine seasons, and seven-year patterns that reflect sabbatical and jubilee years as recorded in Leviticus 25:1–12.³⁶ According to Bullard, the church's lifecycles are pictured in Figure 2.

³⁵ George Bullard, email correspondence, April 22, 2023 (3:34 p.m.).

³⁶ George Bullard, *The Congregational Lifecycle*, last modified 2020, <https://reports.denominee.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Bullard-Congregational-Life-Cycle-03.08.21-Edition.pdf>.

Figure 2. The Lifecycle and Stages of Congregational Development, 2021

Source: Data from George W. Bullard Jr., *The Congregational Life Cycle*, <https://reports.denominee.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Bullard-Congregational-Life-Cycle-03.08.21-Edition.pdf>.

Patterson, in his study on *Common Procedures for Revitalization Leaders*, references a 2009 work by Gray and Drumond titled *Legacy Churches*, which offers the following steps for determining a church's location on the lifecycle spectrum.³⁷ First, he recommends charting the church's attendance records for the last three to five years. Decline is calculated as a 10 percent or more decrease in attendance over the past three years. Conversely, a decrease of over 25 percent in attendance indicates imminent death if quick solutions are not discovered and implemented. His second step is determining how many first-time guests are returning. Statistically, a church must be able to keep about 16 percent of its first-time guests to experience

³⁷ Stephen Gray and Franklin Drumond, *Legacy Churches* (St. Charles, IL: Churchsmart Resources, 2009).

average growth rates. Next, pastors should chart the church's average age of regular attendees. Decline is inevitable if the average age is over 50 and the church is not experiencing at least 25 percent of new growth through young families. Last, he recommends that the church take a congregational lifecycle survey (one is included in his study).³⁸

Conclusion of Church Lifecycle Literature

The concept of the church lifecycle has been studied for decades and has been used in various ways.³⁹ First, it has been used as a general awareness tool. Understanding a church's limited existence allows pastors to see that, if a church is to live longer than what is typical (30–50 years), specific measures (new lifecycle processes) must be taken. The church lifecycle is a general concept that informs ministry leaders about the typical lifecycle of a church and provides awareness that appropriate engagement and intervention is necessary to prevent a church's natural tendency of decline. Second, the lifecycle theory has been used explicitly as a diagnostic or assessment tool to help pastors know where their church is on the typical lifespan. Understanding a church's location on the lifecycle scale can motivate the church to prepare for what may lie ahead. Third, the lifecycle theory provides suggested measures for intervention to help pastors and churches begin to consider their needs regarding directed engagement to prolong its life and enhance its ministry.

³⁸ Sherwood Patterson, "Identifying Common Procedures for Revitalization Leaders When Initiating Turnaround Strategies in Declining Churches" (Biola University, 2019), 81.

³⁹ For various other overviews and interpretations of the congregational life cycle, see Martin F. Saarinen, *The Life Cycle of a Congregation* (Washington, D.C.: Alban Institute, 1986); Arlin J. Rothauge, *The Life Cycle in Congregations: A Process of Natural Creation and an Opportunity for New Creation*; Alice Mann, *Can Our Church Live?: Redeveloping Congregations in Decline* (Bethesda, Md.: Alban Institute, 1999).

Further, the subject of church revitalization requires added clarification in the following areas:

Church Health and Assessment Literature

The current emphasis in church work is church health. To assist a pastor or a congregation in adequately defining the health of its church, various assessments can be done. Also, these assessments help churches define where they need to be, thus providing a pathway forward. In medicine, an assessment is done of the patient, which leads to a diagnosis. A patient's assessment usually includes a physical exam and diagnostic tests (e.g., labs, x-rays, etc.). When the diagnosis (or working diagnosis) is made, proper treatment can be implemented. But, at times, the diagnosis can be questionable. When uncertainty exists, more assessment data is usually sought, and a specialist may be consulted. In these instances, treatments are based on the patient's condition. In the same way, a church cannot improve until it recognizes its current condition and how to treat it, making church health assessments valuable.

When considering the characteristics of a healthy church, the first challenge is to define what a healthy church is. If a pastor cannot adequately describe a healthy church, he cannot direct a struggling church to become one. If a pastor has a faulty definition of what constitutes health in a church, he may continue to lead his church in a way that furthers its decline and eventual demise. A church never arrives at a state of perfect health. All churches must be constantly renewed. Church health is a work of progressive corporate sanctification based on progressive individual sanctification. Efforts must be continuously engaged to keep the body strong.

In his 2020 study, Young defines a healthy church, which he gleaned from Macchia. A healthy church is defined as one that is “prayerful in all of the following aspects of church life and ministry, is reliant on God’s power and the authority of His Word and values: 1) God’s empowering presence, 2) God-exalting worship, 3) Spiritual disciplines, 4) Learning and growing in community, 5) A commitment to loving and caring relationships, 6) Servant leadership development, 7) An outward focus, 8) Wise administration and accountability, 9) Networking with the Body of Christ, and 10) stewardship and generosity.”⁴⁰ According to this understanding, if a church follows all the criteria mentioned (1–10) and yet is not prayerfully relying upon God’s power and the authority of His Word, then the church is not considered healthy.

Another study conducted by Hyung Woo Park (see page 65) also emphasizes throughout his paper that church revitalization is not primarily about church growth but about church health. Park states, concerning his research, “This project will not deal with all aspects of church renewal. It will be concerned with (and) focused on transitioning an unhealthy church into a healthy church.”⁴¹

Another doctoral project study from 2016 chronicled the revitalization of the New Life Praise Church with a specific focus on the Southern Baptist Sandy Creek Association. The healthy church was a vital focus of this study. This research follows the deployment of the small-group-mentality efforts promoted by many church-renewal advocates and specifically championed by Ed Stetzer and Mike Dodson. This project states that “approximately 1000

⁴⁰ Young, “The Development of an Assessment Plan for the Leaders of Grace Church of Alpharetta, GA to Begin a Church Revitalization Initiative,” 51.

⁴¹ Hyung Woo Park, “An Effective Strategy for Church Revitalization through a Case Study of Hosanna Church” (Doctoral Thesis, Liberty Baptist Theological Seminary, 2009), 6.

churches disappear from the Southern Baptist Convention database annually because of their dissolution. Churches will continue to close at the progressive rate of 25% by 2030.”⁴² When this study was conducted, the accepted response to this deplorable condition was to plant new churches. Today, there is greater interest in the revitalization of those declining churches.⁴³

Based on the apparent need to intervene in the lives of so many declining churches, this study was performed to help analyze the process of decline and offer an avenue of support, which included revitalization through the development of small groups. Using Rainer’s work, Chappell evaluated the research of that time concerning what constitutes a dying church. According to Rainer, a dying church is a church where attendance gradually declines. The church ministries lack vibrancy. The past is the glory of a church in decline. Also, a declining church is no longer relevant to the community in which it finds itself. To survive, declining ministries must cut outreach and community ministries. Next, a church in decline is characterized by a membership that is turned inward and focuses on the desires, needs, and preferences of the people who attend it. Dying churches generally have short pastoral tenures and lack prayer. Since there is no unifying vision or mandate, there is no direction. Finally, a declining church usually places an enlarged emphasis on its facilities. Facilities often break down, and the church has little to no money to repair them.

In his study, Patterson also references the characteristics of a dying church by citing the work of Mark Clifton in *Reclaiming Glory*. He records eight common features for diagnosing dying churches.

⁴² Jeffery C. Chappell, “Dead Bones Rising: A Strategic Plan for Revitalizing Declining Churches through a Church Renewal Journey” (Doctoral Thesis, Liberty University School of Divinity, 2016), ii.

⁴³ Chappell, “Dead Bones Rising” 4.

1. Dying churches value the process of decision more than the outcome of decision.
2. Dying churches value their own preferences over the needs of the unreached.
3. Dying churches have an inability to pass leadership to the next generation.
4. Dying churches cease, often gradually, to be part of the fabric of their community.
5. Dying churches grow dependent upon programs or personalities for growth or stability.
6. Dying churches tend to blame the community for lack of response and, in time, resent the community for not responding as it once did.
7. Dying churches anesthetize the pain of death with an overabundance of activity and maintain a less fruitful governance.
8. Dying churches confuse caring for the building with caring for the church and the community. They tend to see no difference between the building and the church and pour their time, attention, and resources into the church's property and facilities.⁴⁴

Chappell states, "Definitions of church health are not commonly found in the written work regarding this subject."⁴⁵ In his research, the section on what constitutes a healthy church brings together several categories of understanding concerning health and dramatically adds to a complete understanding of this critical topic. The health of a church is delineated by looking at a church's emotional, theological, and relational health.⁴⁶ The ultimate goal of Chappell's study is church health, not church growth.

In Chappell's work, Mark Dever offers a working definition that is a good starting point for understanding the concept of a healthy church and its dynamic nature. According to Dever, a healthy church is "a congregation that increasingly reflects God's character as his character has

⁴⁴ Patterson, "Identifying Common Procedures for Revitalization Leaders When Initiating Turnaround Strategies in Declining Churches," 81–84.

⁴⁵ Chappell, "Dead Bones Rising," 3.

⁴⁶ Chappell, "Dead Bones Rising" 27–37.

been revealed in his Word.”⁴⁷ According to these studies, church health is corporate-level progressive sanctification, which must be based upon individual progressive sanctification. A church will be as healthy as the bulk of its individual members.

Scazzero, Dever, and Macchia reveal three understandings of what a healthy church is. This threefold understanding gives a multifaceted knowledge of church health.⁴⁸ First, Peter Scazzero’s principles of an emotionally healthy church will be considered. An emotionally healthy church looks beneath the surface. People look deep in their hearts, asking, “What is Jesus Christ trying to change?” They invite God to bring to their awareness and to transform those beneath the surface layers that hinder them from becoming like Jesus. They break the power of the past by understanding how their history affects their present ability to love Christ and others. People in an emotionally healthy church live and lead out of brokenness and vulnerability; they understand that leadership in the kingdom of God is from the bottom up, not grasping, controlling, or lording over others. It is a noticeably different way of life. The gift of limits is also a characteristic of an emotionally healthy church. This means that people understand the boundaries God has given them. They joyfully receive the one, two, seven, or ten talents God has graciously distributed. They also embrace their limits with the same joy and contentment, not attempting to be like another church. When a church learns to embrace loss, it is becoming healthier emotionally. People embrace grief as a way to become more like God. They understand what a critical component of discipleship, grieving our losses is. It is a crucial pathway to becoming a passionate person like our Lord Jesus. Finally, an emotionally healthy church has

⁴⁷ Chappell, “Dead Bones Rising,” 3.

⁴⁸ The works of these three men can be found in the following locations:
 Peter Scazzero, *The Emotionally Healthy Church* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2010).
 Mark Dever, *Nine Marks of a Healthy Church* (Wheaton, IL: Crossway Books, 2004)
 Stephen A. Macchia, *Becoming A Healthy Church: 10 Traits of a Vital Ministry* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Publishing Co., 1999)

learned the art of incarnational living. People intentionally follow the model of Jesus. They focus on loving well, recognizing that the indispensable mark of spiritual maturity is not about recognition, numbers, spiritual gifts, or biblical knowledge. The essence of a genuine spiritual life is to love—God, ourselves, and other people.⁴⁹

Next to be considered is the theological health of the church. Mark Dever and his Nine Marks ministry reveal the nine components he believes represent a healthy church. Those nine components are expositional preaching, biblical theology, the gospel, a biblical understanding of conversion, evangelism, church membership, biblical church discipline, a concern for discipleship and growth, and biblical church leadership.⁵⁰

According to Dever, these nine particulars must be engaged for a church to be healthy. The preaching style needs to be expositional, meaning the point of the particular passage forms the idea of the sermon. God in His various aspects (e.g., holiness, sovereignty, love, and faithfulness) must be adequately understood. With all of its implications, the gospel must be seen as the most crucial theological consideration of the church. Conversion must be understood as a divine transformational event mediated by preaching the gospel. Conversion, thus experienced, profoundly influences a person's moral, mental, and spiritual aspects. Since the gospel is so important, evangelism (the spreading of that gospel) must be prioritized. The importance and significance of church membership must be clearly defined. Church discipline and discipleship is vital to obtaining and maintaining a healthy church. Converts need to be taught to follow Christ. Servant leadership is the last of the “Nine Marks.”⁵¹

⁴⁹ Chappell, “Dead Bones Rising,” 32–33.

⁵⁰ Nine Marks, “9 Marks of a Healthy Church,” accessed April 23rd, 2021, <https://www.9marks.org/about/the-nine-marks/>.

⁵¹ Chappell, “Dead Bones Rising,” 34–35

The third category of a healthy church involves the church's relational health. According to Macchia's research, ten characteristics define relational health, and these are listed in order of importance. Each type of relational significance has several features. How the believer relates to God involves the spiritual disciplines of God-exalting worship and God's empowering presence. How the believer relates to the family of God also includes three chief characteristics. These are learning and growing in community, a commitment to loving and caring relationships, and the development of servant leadership. The last area of relational significance references the church leader's connection to the ministry. Do the ministers have an outward focus? Are they engaging in wise administration and accountability within the body? Is the leadership generous and engaging in good stewardship of that which the church has been given? Last, does the leadership engage healthily with the local assembly and the larger body of Christ? These are all marks of a healthy church.⁵²

Following is an explanation concerning the historical understanding of the critical elements of a healthy church. Warren, Gangel, Law, and Schwarz variously gave these descriptors.⁵³ Warren identified these characteristics of a healthy church as "purposes": worship, ministry, evangelism, discipleship, and fellowship. Gangel listed his understanding as "factors": winning the lost, building the believer, equipping the worker, multiplying the leader, and sending the called one.⁵⁴ Law's "characteristics" of a healthy church were as follows: engaging worship,

⁵² Chappell, "Dead Bones Rising," 36–37.

⁵³ Christian A. Schwarz, *Natural Church Development: A Guide to Eight Essential Qualities of Healthy Churches* (Carol Stream: Church Smart Resources, 1996), 22–48.

⁵⁴ Kenneth O Gangel, "Marks of a Healthy Church," *Bibliotheca Sacra*, Oct.–Dec. 2001.

mobilized laity, intentional evangelism, and transforming discipleship.⁵⁵ Finally, Schwarz listed the eight “qualities” of a healthy church: empowering leadership, gift-oriented ministry, passionate spirituality, functional structures, inspiring worship services, holistic small groups, need-oriented evangelism, and loving relationships.

Rodney Sprayberry, whose study is further reviewed later (see page 74), realized a valuable truth concerning church revitalization during his research study. He stated,

The pastor has assumed that he had been called to the church to help it grow. This has been replaced with the idea God has uniquely equipped him to help the people of NZBC become holistic followers of Jesus Christ.⁵⁶

The aim of the project was stated in the following words,

God may not want NZBC to be a megachurch, but God wants it to be healthy, growing, and on mission with God. The aim of this project is to help NZBC become such a church. It should also help other small churches that are not growing, to become healthy churches as well.⁵⁷

Also pertinent to the material on church health and assessment is the work of Jim Barber. He has identified six organic areas (which he presents as a fishbone diagram) related to church health. The elements are as follows: worship, fellowship, discipleship, evangelism, ministry, and prayer. Supporting the organic areas of church health are six organizational factors: strategy, structure, leaders, outreach, onboarding, and resources.⁵⁸ Jim Barber has recently turned this work over to Mark Lenz. The Society for Church Consulting has a certification program for

⁵⁵ Allen Brian Law, “The Relationship between Church Health and Church Growth in United Methodist Churches in the West Ohio Annual Conference” (Doctoral Ministry Dissertation, Asbury Theological Seminary, 2002).

⁵⁶ Rodney Merrill Sprayberry, “The Revitalization Process in a Small Rural Plateaued Southern Baptist Church” (Doctoral Thesis Project, Liberty Baptist Theological Seminary, 2010), 116.

⁵⁷ Sprayberry, “The Revitalization Process in a Small Rural Plateaued Southern Baptist Church,” 5.

⁵⁸ Jim Barber, “Online Revitalization Training,” accessed October 15, 2020, <https://1ctixv1rnf663rscij20wsee-wpengine.netdna-ssl.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/summary-of-online-training-.pdf>.

people to become church consultants. Two tracks are involved in this training: a generalist track, which gives vital instruction in being a church consultant; and a revitalization track, which focuses explicitly on those involved in church revitalization (pastoral or consultant). This ministry, as well as the next two, are not Independent Baptist training centers. Areas of doctrinal difference will be apparent. However, valuable revitalization principles (related to church assessment and health) can still be gleaned and applied.

Another popular revitalization book and church health program is *The Nine Marks*.⁵⁹ This program, led by Mark Dever, is described on their website: “We help pastors, future pastors, and church members see what a biblical church looks like, and to take practical steps for becoming one. Our goal is to see churches characterized by nine biblical marks of a healthy church. Why these nine? Because sadly, they’re too often assumed or ignored in evangelical churches.”⁶⁰ These nine marks of a healthy church are as follows: (1) expositional preaching, (2) biblical theology, (3) biblical understanding of the gospel, (4) conversion, (5) evangelism, (6) membership, (7) church discipline, (8) leadership, and (9) promotion of Christian discipleship.⁶¹

Nathan Young, in his work, presents an overview of five different models for church assessment: consultant, self-discovery, systems, group, and concept.⁶² Although many other church consultant groups exist, Young focuses on evaluating Lyle Schaller’s Consultancy Model. Schaller was once identified by the magazine *Christianity Today* as the “dean of church

⁵⁹ Mark Dever, *Nine Marks of a Healthy Church* (United States: Crossway Books, 2021).

⁶⁰ Nine Marks, “About,” accessed April, 23, 2021, <https://www.9marks.org/about/>.

⁶¹ Nine Marks, “9 Marks of a Healthy Church,” accessed April 23rd, 2021, <https://www.9marks.org/about/the-nine-marks/>.

⁶² Nathan Young, “The Development of an Assessment Plan for the Leaders of Grace Church of Alpharetta, Georgia to Begin a Church Revitalization Initiative,” (Southeastern Baptist Theological Seminary, 2020), 47.

consultants.”⁶³ The Self-discovery Model focuses on Stephen Macchia, who leads “Leadership Transformation” meetings where he encourages the spiritual development of leaders and teaches spiritual discernment. Macchia offers a six-month self-discovery process with team discussion guides, assessment questions, and other support materials. The Systems Model focuses on the work of Richard Southern and Robert Norton. Their assessment book is called “Cracking Your Congregations Code.” The tools in this assessment help churches discover their core values, unique missions, and future visions. The Group Model discussion explores the work of Ed Stetzer and Thom Rainer who surveyed 7000 churches, interviewed 4006 of the leaders of these churches, and did onsite in depth interviews of 250 of the churches. From all of this work, the men developed a questionnaire tool that has seven elements (Fellowship, Evangelism, Discipleship, Prayer, Ministry, Worship, Doctrine) and various questions per element. The Concept Model focuses on the church health work of Will Mancini who wrote *Church Unique* and *God Dreams*.

One of the ministries previously mentioned that assists with church assessment is Kenneth Quick and Mark Barnard’s. Their ministry is called Blessing Point Ministries. They have developed a series of materials that deal with a wide range of church renewal and revitalization emphases. Three books are the core of their ministry: *Diagnosing the Heart of Your Church*,⁶⁴ *Healing the Heart of Your Church*,⁶⁵ and *Sustaining The Heart of Your Church*.⁶⁶ These

⁶³ David Neff, “CTI’s Modest Dynamic Duo,” *Christianity Today*, published March 14, 2007, <https://www.christianitytoday.com/ct/2007/april/8.96.html>.

⁶⁴ Mark Barnard, *Diagnosing the Heart of Your Church*, (Createspace Independent Publishing Platform, 2015).

⁶⁵ Kenneth Quick, *Healing the Heart of Your Church*, (Churchsmart Resources, 2003).

⁶⁶ Barnard, *Sustaining the Heart of Your Church*, (Createspace Independent Publishing Platform, 2015).

reference works can be found on their website.⁶⁷ Blessing Point Ministries' central contribution to church revitalization is its developed assessment of underlying issues and sins, which if not dealt with effectively, can lead to decline and repetitive corporate dysfunction. An email to Mark Barnard requesting an overview of the programs and seeking clarification can be found in Appendix E.⁶⁸

Diagnosing The Heart Of Your Church is written to help leaders recognize their churches' need for corporate healing. This book describes five areas (corporate pulse, trust in leadership, mission/vision fulfillment, communication, and historical wounds) where systemic problems appear in a local church. A diagnostic tool to help leaders assess their churches' health is provided in the book and online.

The next book is *Healing the Heart of Your Church: How Ministry Leaders Can Facilitate Corporate Healing* by Dr. Kenneth Quick. This guide assists churches when they find themselves experiencing repetitive corporate dysfunction. Intending for churches to achieve corporate healing, the book leads readers toward addressing any underlying spiritual issues that may not be readily apparent.

The third reference is *Sustaining the Heart of Your Church – Twenty Exercises to Help Church Leaders Overcome Lingering Corporate Dysfunction*. Once a church has dealt with its underlying spiritual problems, this book helps readers achieve sustained healing rather than falling back into negative patterns. This book is designed to support a church in navigating the recovery period that follows corporate healing. This third book in the series provides some critical suggestions or ingredients on the concept of revitalization, such as organizing small

⁶⁷ Kenneth Quick and Mark Barnard, "Blessing Point Ministries Incorporated," accessed 12/17/2020, <https://blessingpoint.org/resources/books/>.

⁶⁸ Mark Barnard, email message to author, June 26, 2023.

groups, developing leaders, and incorporating new mindset ideas that improve and enhance corporate culture.

Although this program does not deal comprehensively with some critical ingredients of church revitalization and church health, as does Nine Marks or the Church Answers program, it does bring to mind critical points often overlooked in revitalization, specifically the church's spiritual relations and sin. These often overlooked components can lead to cyclical corporate dysfunction. In his email interview, Barnard mentions that his program deals primarily with the “internal relational and spiritual functioning of a church and not the more common church growth or church health paradigms.”⁶⁹ Confession of sin, if overlooked, neglected, or minimized, can block the church's desire for revitalization. As did Samson of old, the church may try to “shake itself” and go out to battle, only to find that its power is gone.

Another church ministry focused on church health is Thom Rainer’s “Church Answers” ministry. This ministry provides a broad-ranging program dealing with all aspects of church health, growth, and revitalization. The ministry’s website lists Rainer’s “statistically valid” church health assessment. The author of this research used Rainer’s assessment when analyzing the two churches introduced in Chapter 1.

For more than 20 years, churches across North America have been using the Church Health Report to analyze and improve their church health. The Church Health Report consists of a 160-item questionnaire that measures a church's perceived health in six purposes of the church: worship, evangelism, fellowship, discipleship, prayer, and ministry. Church leaders choose a sampling of the church membership to complete the 15-20 minute survey, and we provide a detailed health report for the church. The process and directions are self-explanatory, and the final report includes suggestions for addressing concerns raised.⁷⁰

⁶⁹ Mark Barnard, email message to author, June 26, 2023.

⁷⁰ Know Your Church Report, “Church Health Report,” accessed January 10, 2021, <https://churchhealthreport.com/about/>.

According to Rainer, the “six purposes of the church” encapsulate what constitutes a church. Ideally, in a healthy church, these six purposes must be functioning. The degree to which they are functioning determines the health of the church. In revitalization work, these six parameters give focus to the task. Defining a church's health according to these bullet points is critical to attaining a diagnostic overview of the individual church.

Conclusion of Church Assessment and Health Literature

Much has been written on the subject of church health, assessment, and revitalization. The concept of church health is not as easily definable as one might think. Specifically, Mark Dever (Nine Marks ministry) and Thom Rainer (Church Answers ministry) help to keep minds focused on the characteristics of a healthy church. In approaching church work with the qualities of a healthy church in mind, pragmatic ministry (“do what works”) can be avoided, goals can be established, and drifting can be avoided.

The work of Kenneth Quick and Mark Barnard draws attention to the ultimate and underlying cause of church decline: sin. The church's work is spiritual; theoretically, nothing should be able to stop that work because the Spirit of God energizes it. Sin can interfere with the powerful relationship that Jesus has with his church. In the second and third chapters of Revelation, Jesus constantly calls his churches to repent. The church belongs to Jesus and must be organized and maintained according to the Scriptures.

The ultimate purpose of a church health assessment tool is to define the church's current state of health and prescribe a method of recovery. In medicine, a common acronym that guides a clinician's patient care flow is APIE, in which the letters stand for *assessment*, *plan*, *intervention*, and *evaluation*. The assessment phase is critical to the rest of the patient care flow. A client's

health is reliant on a physician's plan and intervention. Evaluation is also an important step, as it determines whether the original diagnosis or treatment is, in fact, beneficial.

Because revitalization programs specifically designed for Independent Baptist churches are not readily available, such churches must be prudent and selective when choosing programs. They must also demonstrate wisdom when administering printed assessments. Approaching church revitalization as an academic matter using evaluations, statistics, and research may appear to the average church goer as detrimental or even foolish, as such academic resources are often new and foreign to their understanding of the life and work within the church. Although research on this topic is helpful, it must not be paraded as the answer. Many Independent Baptists have a deep spiritual understanding of the work of God in the church, an understanding that has been informed by a long history of powerful and influential leaders in the movement. Revitalization in Independent Baptist churches is certainly necessary, but the effort can often be squandered if approached from a sterile, academic, or solely scientific perspective.

Revitalization Leadership Literature

Leadership is one of the keys to the success of church revitalization. Since popular secular thinking on leadership may or may not line up with biblical truth, averse philosophies may creep into the church and create a man-centered environment of leadership rather than a biblical, God-centered view. The pastoral leadership studies discussed here focus primarily on the qualities of leadership and the training of leadership.

Matthew Gilmore, in 2020, conducted a study that sought to develop a leadership training program for pastors to improve their leadership ability (competency focus) in some critical areas

related to revitalization.⁷¹ Through research and the use of an expert panel, the project director sought to identify obstacles to revitalization and then provide strategies to overcome those obstacles. He then prepared a training seminar dealing with four aspects of revitalization to assist pastors in understanding and navigating revitalization.

A doctoral project study that was also reviewed under the category of church health and assessment will be examined further under the strategies heading (see page 78). It chronicles the revitalization of the New Life Praise Church with a specific focus on leadership within the Southern Baptist Sandy Creek Association of churches. This 2016 research follows the deployment of the small-group-mentality efforts promoted by many church-renewal advocates and historically championed by Ed Stetzer and Mike Dodson.

Believing that revitalization must begin in the pulpit, Chappell extracted from Ross that there are “ten non-negotiable from the pulpit” items that must true for revitalization to occur: (1) a high view of God, (2) the absolute authority of Scripture, (3) sound doctrine and pure gospel, (4) biblical authority, (5) mutual accountability, (6) holiness of lifestyle, (7) the priority of prayer, (8) commitment to excellence, (9) loving focus on people, and (10) revival and reformation.⁷² For these things to become true in any church, it must have strong leadership. Therefore, Chappell emphasizes leadership in this section on revitalization.

In his 1992 study, Jeffery Wells also emphasizes leadership as a critical ingredient to church revitalization. Wells worked under the assumption that many local churches are staffed

⁷¹ Matthew Gilmore, “Developing a Strategy and Training for Pastors in the South Florida Baptist Association to Identify Challenges and Solutions for Church Revitalization,” Doctor of Ministry Research Project, Southeastern Baptist Theological Seminary, 2020.

⁷² Chappell, “Dead Bones Rising: A Strategic Plan for Revitalizing Declining Churches through a Church Renewal Journey,” 45.

with people who have been “given the position of leader without ever demonstrating that ability in their life.”⁷³ Wells used a questionnaire, evaluation tool, onsite observation, and church documentation to research five areas comprising what he felt were the essential components of an effective Christian leader. This research was built on the leadership theory that “an effective Christian leader maximizes his strengths, minimizes his weaknesses, and develops in biblical character to attract others to accomplish a common biblical vision.”⁷⁴ For his research project, he studied one church, involving the senior pastor, his wife, two staff associates, two members of the board of the church, and several members of the church, who were randomly selected.

The study Wells performed approached leadership from a strength-based perspective (natural gifting). In his practical application, Wells sought to develop tools to help pastors in the following areas: “self-analysis of their gifts and life vision, assessment of their developmental needs for character and ministry skills, and assessment of action steps that need to be taken toward the improvement of leadership.”⁷⁵ Each of these tools was designed to help improve the leadership abilities of pastors.

The utility of this research, in its relation to the current study, must be balanced alongside a unique factor. Wells’s research approaches the subject of revitalization with the idea that there is a plurality of leadership, thus helping to provide “cover” for the senior pastor’s weaknesses. The average Independent Baptist church does not usually have a plurality of leadership (Elders and Pastors). The standard model is the solo pastor. For a lone pastor to minimize his weaknesses is difficult. Usually, his strengths and weaknesses are eventually on display for everyone to see.

⁷³ Jeffery H. Wells, “Case Studies of Pastoral Leadership in the Church, #2” (Dissertation, Dallas Theological Seminary, 1992), 2.

⁷⁴ Wells, “Case Studies of Pastoral Leadership in the Church, #2,” 1–2.

⁷⁵ Wells, “Case Studies of Pastoral Leadership in the Church, #2,” 6.

When a solo pastor takes the responsibility of revitalizing a church, the people attending that church must recognize that the pastor is not a perfect man, nor does he have a perfect family. However, his example in diligently improving his practical sanctification and pastoral leadership should be encouraging to others in doing the same. The pastor should also emphasize that he will need grace and help for the ministry to continue.

The research project Wells engaged in was designed to be an ongoing project with more doctoral students using the protocol contained therein to conduct research similarly. The goal was to achieve at least fifty such case studies. In repeating this study in multiple churches, the nature and importance of Christian leadership would be more clearly defined and refined. Wells's belief that leadership is a crucial ingredient in revitalizing plateaued or declining churches made this study particularly valuable. Though the measurement tool used for this author's current research did not precisely quantify leadership, leadership was heavily referenced in the pastoral interviews. As seen in some of the subsequent studies, leadership was a fundamental interest in revitalization.

In 2011, a qualitative study by Mays encouraged a focus on the core leadership practices of turnaround churches. At the time, the plateaued or declining church rate stood at 85 percent. The viability of churches was of great concern, and interest in church revitalization was growing in many denominations. Mays examined one rural Kentucky church where he conducted participant observations, and evaluated documents. He also interviewed the pastor, three part-time staff members, and twenty-four members. This church had experienced a 289 percent growth rate over the previous fourteen years. The introduction of transformational leadership in school settings was also examined to show the cross-contextual applicability of leadership principles.

In his study, Mays suggests that turnaround leadership is “not so much a product of individual, charismatic leadership as it is the product of consistent, sustained attention to sound leadership behaviors.”⁷⁶ The lead pastor’s “turnaround” leadership was described in this research, in summary, as follows. The pastor was a people person and a detail person who engaged, primarily, five intentional behaviors: (1) developing a community presence, (2) providing quality, meaningful worship, (3) educating and equipping members, (4) providing a vision for the future, and (5) empowering and mobilizing the laity.⁷⁷

These findings related to Mays’s leadership qualities were compared with others’ research findings.

Table 2.1. Leadership Qualities by Various Researchers, 1993–2004

Researcher	Year	Findings
Barna	1993	a) team builders, (b) vision providers, (c) seekers of personal spiritual growth, (d) encouragers, (e) strategic thinkers, (f) risk-takers, and almost all of them were (g) youthful (45 or younger), (h) workaholics, (60 to 80 hours per week), (i) strong personalities, and (j) potential visionaries-having not given prior evidence of being a visionary.
Crandall	1995	(a) loving people, (b) displaying people skills, (c) preaching, and (d) being a visionary and motivator

⁷⁶ Ronald Brent Mays, “Comparing Turnaround Leadership in a Rural Church and in Schools” (Ph.D. Dissertation, Graduate School of the University of Louisville, Graduate Studies and Research at Western Kentucky University, 2011), 9.

⁷⁷ Mays, “Comparing Turnaround Leadership in a Rural Church and in Schools,” 8–9.

Researcher	Year	Findings
Frazer	1995	being a "persuader." These types of people (a) work with and through people to win their own objectives, (b) possess an outgoing interest in people and have the ability to gain their respect and confidence, (c) exhibit mobility while preferring challenging and varied work assignments, (d) exude optimism, almost to a fault, (e) need analytical data on a systematic basis to keep from being impulsive, and (f) require alerting to the importance of "little things." Additionally, these "change agents" enjoy bringing order out of chaos and target energy creating discontent with the status quo so that constituents are motivated to enlist in pursuing a new direction.
Rainer (the numbers in parentheses represent percentages)	2001	(a) the ability to cast vision (72), (b) sense of humor (68), (c) work ethic (67), (d) persistence (65), (e) leadership by example (59), (f) integrity (57), (g) change agent (57), (h) love of God's word (54), (i) communication skills (53), (j) faith/optimism, (k) relational skills/love of people (52), and (l) team building/mentoring (50). It was also interesting to note that the top five weaknesses listed all revealed an awareness of the importance of dealing with people: (a) pastoral ministry (73), (b) lack of patience (71), (c) dealing with staff (70), (d) dealing with criticism (67), and (e) always task-driven (64).
Wood	2001	(a) willing to confront conflict, (b) possessing high energy-energized by work, (c) maintaining good physical shape, (d) making family a priority, (e) growing personally, (f) understanding church-life instinctively, and (g) thinking strategically.
Rainer and Lawless	2003	(a) a dependence on God; (b) a commitment to stay, (c) wisdom in initiating change, (d) an attitude of encouragement, and (e) a love for people. They delineated those findings by describing five prices pastors desiring church growth must be willing to pay: (a) assume responsibility for growth, (b) work hard, (c) willingly share their ministries and develop the lay ministries of the church, (d) accept that they cannot personally pastor every member and thus create small groups with accountability, and (e) realize that a desire for church growth is biblically and theologically sound.
Nixon	2004	(a) a capacity for authentic relationships; (b) personal authenticity-including the capacity to share ministry, foster creativity, and mobilize laity; (c) personal autonomy; (d) an allocentric attitude; and (e) a strong sense of self-efficacy.

Researcher	Year	Findings
Page	2008	The turnaround pastor must be possessed of a purpose greater than himself, a constant caster of a vision with enthusiasm, conviction, and dedication to the goal of making disciples for Christ. He must be trustworthy, credible, and consistent, as well as adept at managing and investing in relationships with members and church leaders. The turnaround leader must be confident and secure enough to share ministry and be skilled at securing and positioning the right people in the ministries that are suited to their gifts and the goals of the congregation.

Source: Data adapted from Ronald Brent Mays, "Comparing Turnaround Leadership in a Rural Church and in Schools" (Ph.D. Dissertation, Graduate School of the University of Louisville, Graduate Studies and Research at Western Kentucky University, 2011), 78–83

Mays's study highlights the importance of leadership. Quantifying leadership based on the pastor's personality and behaviors was clarifying and directive. Mays encouraged "intentional behaviors," such as developing a community presence and worshiping. Over nine years, the worship style of the Kentucky church was changed: there was a move away from exclusive hymn singing. Also, a focus on youth and children's ministries was evident in Mays's practice and highlighted in his study.

A 2006 study by Bryan Miller analyzed some of the primary problems small churches face.⁷⁸ His research adds to the understanding of typical small church problems. Also, it provides possible answers to those problems, emphasizing leadership as the mechanism whereby these problems can be navigated. Although not always true, many churches that need to be revitalized are small and unhealthy. Lifeway research states, "While the average U.S. congregation gathers in a building that seats around 200, only 65 attend the median church each week. This means that

⁷⁸ Bryan Miller, "Pastoral Leadership Problems in Small, Established Churches of under 100 People," (Doctoral Thesis, Liberty Theological Seminary, 2006), 4.

half of all churches have fewer than 65 people in their weekly worship service.”⁷⁹ As a pastor engages with a smaller church needing revitalization, problems generally beset the effort.

This research grew from Miller’s experience pastoring small churches and from his literature review. He discovered five different issues that pastors of smaller churches face: (1) bi-vocational ministry, (2) dominant-personality people and family churches, (3) tradition, (4) finances, and (5) unqualified volunteers or personnel. Miller also gives various suggestions for dealing with the individual problems discussed. For example, a bi-vocational ministry can combine events with other churches or mobilize lay leadership within the church; and pastors with dominant-personality people within their church have the options of working with them, fighting them, or working around them. Miller goes on to list suggestions for solving the other discussed issues. Studies such as Miller’s can encourage others to approach potential and actual problems with the current church leadership before a pastor takes over the church, or give guidance and suggestions concerning what to do once one is the pastor and after the problems are discovered .

Joseph Hudson’s research, published in 2017, attempted “to develop a competency model for church revitalization that could be used to help churches and seminaries assess and develop church leaders to serve in plateaued and declining churches.”⁸⁰ Competencies would be defined as helpful leadership characteristics that aid in church revitalization. Hudson’s research grew from the practical church experience of that day (decline), the statistical data that clarified the church’s need (renewal), and a lack of academic research on revitalization.

⁷⁹ Aaron Earls, “Small Churches Continue Growing—but in Number, Not Size,” *Lifeway Research*, published Oct. 20, 2021, research.lifeway.com/2021/10/20/small-churches-continue-growing-but-in-number-not-size/#:~:text=While%20the%20average%20U.S.%20congregations. Accessed 2 May, 2023.

⁸⁰ Hudson, “A Competency Model for Church Revitalization in Southern Baptist Convention Churches: A Mixed Methods Study,” 2.

The findings of this study were presented in two phases and several tables. The first phase was the qualitative interview phase. Eight pastors were chosen to participate based on inclusion criteria. The Behavioral Event Interview (BEI) protocol was used to gather qualitative data from these pastors. The second phase was the quantitative portion of the study, in which a modified Delphi technique was used to develop a competency model. The Delphi method is identified as “a technique that uses multiple rounds of questionnaires to reach a consensus among a panel of experts.”⁸¹ Using the same criteria that defined the eight pastors of the first phase, nineteen participants were selected to participate in this panel.

The results of these investigative efforts yielded one hundred and twenty-seven competencies, which were broken into three categories.

The statistical analysis of the Delphi portion of the study yielded a competency model that characterized some competencies as (1) “expert competencies,” or those competencies that differentiate superior performers from average performers, (2) “core competencies,” or those that are necessary for the role of church revitalizer and (3) “supplemental competencies,” which may be helpful but perhaps not necessary.⁸²

Thirty-six expert competencies, seventy-six core competencies, and fifteen supplemental competencies were listed. Readers may view these competencies listed in Appendix F.

In his research study, Hudson reveals a common tendency among researchers. The common tendency is to borrow philosophies and approaches from secular models. This study states, “Competency modeling was born out of the observation that traditional methods of

⁸¹ Hudson, “A Competency Model for Church Revitalization in Southern Baptist Convention Churches: A Mixed Methods Study,” 9.

⁸² Hudson, “A Competency Model for Church Revitalization in Southern Baptist Convention Churches: A Mixed Methods Study,” 124.

gauging aptitude are often poor predictors for job performance. Human resource management professionals have used competency models since the early 1970s.”⁸³ Hudson goes on to state,

Specifically, competencies of motive, trait, self-concepts, knowledge, and skill dimensions were in view. Examining a larger set of competency types expands the current research on leadership profiles for church revitalization and provides data on leadership competencies, which are useful for developing models for assessment, selection, and training.⁸⁴

After reviewing the voluminous amount of data in this study (127 competencies), Hudson does not deny that although each pastor should be improving in personal and pastoral qualities, God’s list of qualifications for a Bishop is much shorter (1 Tim. 3:1–7; Titus 1:5–9). Hudson mentions these verses once in his study, with a reduced emphasis. Quoting Bartlet in the section dealing with secular competency models, Hudson states, “Nowhere in Scripture is there a specific curriculum, of course, and even the well-crafted list in 1 Timothy 3:1-7 has a far greater focus on personal and spiritual characteristics than on an academic course of studies.”⁸⁵ Presented in this way, these “personal and spiritual characteristics” appear deemphasized in importance when compared to unique courses of study designed to enhance leadership skills.

Hudson’s approach to leadership is a trait-based approach, one that can become discouraging and defeating because of the diversity of factors required for good leadership. As he said, seventy-six core competencies are “necessary for the role of church revitalizer.”⁸⁶

⁸³ Hudson, “A Competency Model for Church Revitalization in Southern Baptist Convention Churches: A Mixed Methods Study,” 5.

⁸⁴ Hudson, “A Competency Model for Church Revitalization in Southern Baptist Convention Churches: A Mixed Methods Study,” 20, 146.

⁸⁵ Hudson, “A Competency Model for Church Revitalization in Southern Baptist Convention Churches: A Mixed Methods Study,” 5.

⁸⁶ Hudson, “A Competency Model for Church Revitalization in Southern Baptist Convention Churches: A Mixed Methods Study,” 124.

Strength-based (giftedness) leadership models exist, providing a reasonable balance to the competency-based approach to ministry leadership.

Another interest in this study was the digest of information derived from a review of five studies that dealt explicitly with revitalization factors as found in “breakout churches.”⁸⁷ Researchers have attempted to characterize “breakout churches” and what causes them to revive. The churches in these studies were characterized by specific emphases. Hadaway (1991) lists the following: evangelism, goal orientation, facilities, and settings; congregational structure, congregational character, planning and goal setting, pastor and staff, evangelism and outreach, Sunday School, worship, other church programs, integration and assimilation, morale and desire for growth, spiritual emphasis and renewal. Samelson (1999) discovered these traits: strong pastoral leadership, positive personality, good preaching skills, vision, and planning skills, being accessible to the congregation, modeling faithfulness, new worship services, attracting young people and children, quality ministerial staff, creating small groups, renewal programs, development of lay leadership. Stroh (2014) discovered the following factors: new pastor, focus on outreach, new or expanded facilities, deliberate ministry planning, more member ministry, added staff, quality worship or worship variety, and new ministries. Bond (2015) uncovered the following factors: missionary mentality, vibrant leadership, relational intentionality, prayerful dependence, worship, community, and mission. Shelton (2015) emphasized only one characteristic but certainly one that influenced the whole: the pastor and his leadership.

Concerning the above lists, Hudson makes the following comment, adding a quote from Hadaway: “While some of these factors are uncontrollable variables, pastoral leadership still was shown to have a profound impact on a church's ability to ‘breakout.’ Hadaway observed,

⁸⁷ Hudson, “A Competency Model for Church Revitalization in Southern Baptist Convention Churches: A Mixed Methods Study,” 41–49.

‘Breakout growth tends to occur with a new pastor, and it tends to occur rapidly if it is to occur at all. What these new pastors are doing (other than evangelism) remains somewhat unclear, but it would seem that the primary role of the pastor in leading a church to growth is that of a catalytic motivator, who leads the church in the proper direction and can motivate lay members to do the necessary work.’⁸⁸ This particular factor (that revitalization usually occurs early and rapidly with a new pastor) is a key insight when considering a church’s current revitalization potential.

Jarvis Baker’s 2018 work attempts to analyze the topic of revitalization from the early church's experience and glean revitalization principles directly from the Word of God. He disseminated these principles in a planned leadership retreat. As with many other researchers, Baker’s interest in this subject grew from realizing the difficulties that local churches in America faced. At the beginning of the study, Baker gave multiple statistics to reveal to those reading that revitalization is a current and crucial need that needs to be solved. Baker states, “After the sheer shock of these numbers radiates within the leaders, it should move leaders to make adjustments within their own declining churches, such was the case in the Cornerstone Baptist church.”⁸⁹ For his research emphasis, Baker focused on the importance and value of leadership in the recovery process.

Quoting Mims, Baker states that when one considers the early church leaders, three characteristics are revealed: “They walked according to the Spirit, not the flesh (human inclinations). Second, they considered God's purposes, not people's priorities. Third, they acted

⁸⁸ Hudson, “A Competency Model for Church Revitalization in Southern Baptist Convention Churches: A Mixed Methods Study,” 42–43.

⁸⁹ Jarvis Baker, “Leadership Matters: The Process of Leading a Declining Church to Revitalization Utilizing Early Church Principles,” (Doctoral Thesis, Liberty University School of Divinity, 2018), 12.

according to God's methods, not their own."⁹⁰ This summary statement by Baker encapsulates the emphasis of his work:

The purposes of God in the local church were identified as follows: "A balanced church will have a balanced purpose statement centered on the same purposes of the first New Testament church. The church's purpose statement is to be: "Our church will find people for the Lord Jesus (evangelism), feed them on the Lord's Word (discipleship), fasten them to the Lord's people (fellowship), focus them on the Lord's wonder (worship), and send them to do the Lord's work (ministry)." This purpose statement encompasses all the purposes of the first New Testament Church.⁹¹

Baker also clarifies the local church's mission in the book of Acts by initially analyzing Acts 2:42-47. Quoting Mims again, Baker states there were "four foundational qualities" of the New Testament church's practice: "They were an evangelizing, learning, loving, and worshipping church."⁹² Baker refers to relevant Scriptures to support his contention that there are "four foundational qualities of the New Testament church." He also considers prayer an essential part of the revitalization process.

The practical aspect of Baker's research involved a retreat for Christian leaders where seven revitalization topics would be discussed. In an informal discussion, church leaders identified potential issues that they would like to see included in a leadership retreat. After these informal discussions, a questionnaire seeking to identify or isolate possible revitalization topics was submitted to ten church leaders. The seven issues for inclusion in the retreat were thus identified: (1) evangelism, (2) discipleship, (3) vision statement, (4) mission statement, (5) conflict resolution, (6) keys to revitalization, and (7) ministry of the Word.

⁹⁰ Baker, "Leadership Matters: The Process of Leading a Declining Church to Revitalization Utilizing Early Church Principles," 67.

⁹¹ Baker, "Leadership Matters: The Process of Leading a Declining Church to Revitalization Utilizing Early Church Principles," 98.

⁹² Baker, "Leadership Matters: The Process of Leading a Declining Church to Revitalization Utilizing Early Church Principles," 67.

Seventy people eventually participated in the retreat. These leaders included associate pastors, deacons, ruling elders, teaching elders, Sunday school teachers, praise team leaders, and music ministers. Although each of the seven topics listed above is important, this researcher was particularly drawn to the sections on “Keys to Revitalization,” “Evangelism,” and “Discipleship,” as these sections most closely align with this author’s research focus. The session on “Keys to Revitalization” followed “The Seven Pillars of Revitalization,” written by Tom Cheney. The seven pillars are described as follows.

In the first phase, “Revitalization and Realignment,” the church realizes its need for revitalization. The second is “Refocusing,” a phase that highlights the growth of the church and its need to seek new challenges. The church must look for new opportunities to expand its gospel witness into its target area. Third, the “Re-Visioning” phase helps churches dream new dreams and accomplish new goals. Fourth, the “Renewing” stage encourages the church to realize its need to get back on track and return to what was working. The fifth phase, “Reinvention,” emphasizes tools and techniques to assist the church when it must reinvent itself in a changing community. The sixth phase, “Restoration,” calls attention to the things a church must go through when circumstances necessitate a restoration. Last comes the “Restarting” phase, the hardest of all.⁹³

The second section of interest to this author was “Evangelism.” This section discussed the lack of evangelism in the average church and sought to explain a simple New Testament method to revitalize evangelistic interest. That method was to concentrate on family and friends.

⁹³ Baker, “Leadership Matters: The Process of Leading a Declining Church to Revitalization Utilizing Early Church Principles,” 85-86.

In this section, a research study was referenced that showed the importance of this approach to evangelism.

Research conducted by Church Growth, Inc. of Monrovia, California, supports the notion that the oikos process is at work today. Over forty-two thousand laypeople were asked the question, what or who was responsible for your coming to Christ and your church? One of the following eight responses was given: “1) Some [1-2 percent] said a “special need” brought them to Christ and the church; 2) Some [two to three percent] responded they just “walked in.”; 3) Some [five to six percent] listed the “pastor.”; 4) Some [one to two percent] indicated “visitation; 5) Some [four to five percent] mentioned “Sunday school.”; 6) Some [one-half percent] listed “evangelistic crusade or television.”; 7) Some [seventy-five to ninety percent] responded that a “friend/relative” was the reason they are now in Christ and the church.”⁹⁴

The section on “Discipleship” revealed the crucial nature of discipling the memberships that remain, as well as the new people who enter the church, in a revitalization effort. This reality is seen in Baker’s and Park’s studies, which follow. An emphasis was placed not on information remembered, but on a lifestyle that is practiced. The process of discipleship encourages “a lifestyle of absolute abandonment to loving God and obeying his commands.”⁹⁵ Discipleship thus reflects a living, loving, growing relationship with Jesus Christ.

Although Baker’s research did not include practical strategies that churches could follow in the revitalization process, it does present the key ingredients involved in revitalization from a biblical perspective. The Scriptures are sufficient in all matters concerning faith and practice, including issues related to revitalization.

⁹⁴ Baker, “Leadership Matters: The Process of Leading a Declining Church to Revitalization Utilizing Early Church Principles,” 91-92.

⁹⁵ Baker, “Leadership Matters: The Process of Leading a Declining Church to Revitalization Utilizing Early Church Principles,” 93.

Patterson weighs in again, this time on the importance of leadership in the revitalization process. At the beginning of his discussion, he makes a statement on leadership that is important to remember. He states,

Rising from this research is a general consensus that pastors and churches that want to grow, are willing to pay the price, prioritize evangelism, and bravely address illnesses are poised to experience the reviving work of God. None of this comes easy and those who are leading change have a unique and significant role in the process. However, if a history of chronic illnesses and splits are present in a church, it is much more difficult for pastors and leaders to initiate true spiritual reform. Selfishness, pain, bitterness, and a loss of respect for leadership and love for guests can create a culture that is in desperate need of repentance and change.⁹⁶

Patterson admits here the difficulties a revitalization pastor faces in the revitalization process. A pastor and church can “want growth, pay the price, prioritize evangelism, and bravely address illnesses.”⁹⁷ However, they may still meet insurmountable challenges that can only be overcome by corporate repentance and change, which may never come. He says later, “Since a church’s growth depends so much on leadership, the lack of qualified leaders in so many churches, along with the unique revitalization leader profile needed for effective transformation prevents the potential of more comeback churches.”⁹⁸ Though leadership is key to revitalization, not every leader pursues that goal.

As research on revitalization continues, a unique leader profile emerges, showing the characteristics of preachers that can lead in revitalization work. That leader is more “task-oriented” (sodalic) than “people-oriented” (modalic). According to Patterson, referencing a lecture by Gary McIntosh, “Revitalization leaders tend to lead less through consensus and

⁹⁶ Patterson, “Identifying Common Procedures for Revitalization Leaders When Initiating Turnaround Strategies in Declining Churches,” 66.

⁹⁷ Patterson, “Identifying Common Procedures for Revitalization Leaders When Initiating Turnaround Strategies in Declining Churches,” 66.

⁹⁸ Patterson, “Identifying Common Procedures for Revitalization Leaders When Initiating Turnaround Strategies in Declining Churches,” 69.

affirmation and more by initiating vision and proactively pursuing the desired mission.”⁹⁹ This fact should not diminish the importance of a pastor’s being loving, approachable, and inspirational.

Conclusion of Revitalization Leadership Literature

Leadership is a critical component in ministry and especially in church revitalization. The leadership mantra, “Everything rises and falls on leadership,” must be qualified. Predictably, the emphasis of these studies was the leadership of the pastor. However, every church’s leadership is different and not found in just the pastor. Although the pastor should be the prime leader, there will be other leadership within the church (and some of that other leadership may not be healthy leadership). Also, something must also be said concerning *follow-ship*. Any military commander knows that his success on the battlefield largely depends on the soldiers put onto the field. If the church and the work of the church are not in the people’s hearts, a pastor will find that defection and trouble come more quickly than advancement and growth.

These studies deal primarily with leadership from a technical aspect, seeking to identify the type of leader who can revitalize a church successfully. The studies focus primarily on leadership approaches—giftedness and trait-based competencies—and seek to show how both aspects of leadership behavior might affect church revitalization. Although each method of leadership has benefits and drawbacks, a pastor should consider an eclectic approach to maximize his particular giftedness. Still, at the same time, he should be cultivating leadership traits in areas he lacks and hiring or recruiting people who have those traits.

⁹⁹ Patterson, “Identifying Common Procedures for Revitalization Leaders When Initiating Turnaround Strategies in Declining Churches,” 67.

Although this study is not on pastoral theology, serious consideration must be given to the current model of single-elder rule in the average Independent Baptist church. The solo-pastor model lends itself to potential abuses and difficulties. Even in revitalization work, when the solo-elder rule might seem preferable, strong consideration should be given (initially or as soon as possible) to a team approach of pastoral leadership. One of the reasons a team approach is valuable is that, according to these research studies, revitalization work is complex and multi-faceted. A broader multi-gifted leadership base (more than just a solo pastor) could potentially provide a more well-rounded opportunity for the church to recover effectively.

Revitalization Strategies Literature

Another topic of recurring emphasis in the literature about church revitalization is strategies. Knowledge of church lifecycles is helpful information as one approaches a church needing renewal. Having the right leader in a revitalization effort is not just beneficial but also crucial. Leaders must not only be present and know the situation of the church, but they must also know what to do. It is also important for leaders to have the necessary tools at their disposal for the recovery of the church. Although the literature is replete with suggested avenues of revitalization, the challenge involves more than just picking one and applying it for everything to turn out well. Each church is a unique living organism. Each church has a unique history. Each church has a unique set of problems. Leadership requires discernment and discipline, and strategies should be implemented through experience, prayer, and sometimes trial and error. Followers (church members) must be invested and engaged in the church's recovery. Opportunity must be seized and seized early. There must be a mutual commitment to do what

God leads the church to do. Consider some of the research on this most crucial aspect of revitalization.

Three items prompted Hyung Woo Park to engage in his particular research study. First was the observation of an overall decline in the Korean church. A report published by “the Korea National Statistical Office revealed an alarming trend in the Christian church in South Korea. Over twelve years starting in 1995, the percentage of Christians in Korea dropped from 25.03% to 20.7% of the overall population.”¹⁰⁰ The second prompt that encouraged his research study was a survey of 17,060 lay Christians about the state of the Korean Church. One question asked, “Do you believe there is need for renewal or revitalizing in the current Korean Church?” Almost half of the respondents, 49.2 percent, said they “Strongly Agree,” and 47 percent said they “Agree.”¹⁰¹ The third prompt that began Park’s study was his own church’s need of revitalization.

Park, in this research study, evaluated the experience of the Hosanna Church in its revitalization process. He identified ten concepts related to revitalization: (1) preparation for revitalization is essential; (2) strong pastoral leadership is necessary; (3) revitalization ultimately occurs by vision; (4) teamwork makes a robust framework for successful revitalization; (5) effective systems of communication are essential; (6) the importance of making disciples must be considered; (7) the timing of revitalization must be considered; (8) the power of small groups should be noticed; (9) effective management of resistance is crucial; (10) ongoing evaluation must be embraced.

¹⁰⁰ Hyung Woo Park, “An Effective Strategy for Church Revitalization through a Case Study of Hosanna Church” (Doctoral Thesis, Liberty Baptist Theological Seminary, 2009), 1.

¹⁰¹ Park, “An Effective Strategy for Church Revitalization through a Case Study of Hosanna Church,” 2.

The revitalization of Hosanna Church followed a specific process, targeting four parts of the church. First, the process focused on the pastor. His revitalization occurred through the informal personal mentoring of a retired pastor. Second, the process focused on the renewal of individual lay leadership through discipleship training. Third, the revitalization of small groups occurred through the renewed and revitalized lay leaders; and fourth, the revitalization of the congregation itself occurred naturally through the above three processes.

Hosanna Church's revitalization initially involved three aspects: the revitalization of (1) personal life, (2) follow-up system and church policy [which included the development of an elder training system], and (3) church culture [which included a change in worship style as well as a new modern style for church decorations].¹⁰² Park further states, "Hosanna Church's successful revitalization was not a coincidence but rather resulted from the combination of God's grace for His church coupled with practical strategies including spiritual leadership, discipleship training, small group ministry, and evangelism."¹⁰³ A multi-faceted target-specific approach to revitalization is presented in this research.

This researcher offers the following observations concerning Park's research. Park conducted his study with a South Korean church, thus providing a cross-cultural understanding of revitalization principles applied in non-Western contexts. This context gives evidence that biblical revitalization principles are stable across cultural contexts.¹⁰⁴ Throughout his work, Park emphasizes that church revitalization is not primarily about church growth but church health. Park states, "This project will not deal with all aspects of church renewal. It will be concerned

¹⁰² Park, "An Effective Strategy for Church Revitalization through a Case Study of Hosanna Church," 55-56.

¹⁰³ Park, "An Effective Strategy for Church Revitalization through a Case Study of Hosanna Church," 117.

¹⁰⁴ Park, "An Effective Strategy for Church Revitalization through a Case Study of Hosanna Church," 1.

with (and) focused on transitioning an unhealthy church into a healthy church.”¹⁰⁵ Church health is the current, modern emphasis and understanding of church revitalization

Dennis McCullough engaged in a research study published in 2020 that dealt with a strategy related to women in the revitalization process. He states,

America’s churches are in crisis. Studies show that churches are filled with a majority of women and children, and the men are nowhere to be found. Besides, these churches have programs and ministries focusing on growing “mega,” ignoring the cries of the people, and not intentionally focusing on the women within the church. Unfortunately, women are suffering in silence, and the church is not hearing their sound. This discrepancy is no different within this author’s church, which comprises 90% women, 8% children, and 2% men and have been operating this way for several years.¹⁰⁶

The project aimed to “expose the need that specific ministries for women are lacking, and churches must design programs to meet their needs and grow the church effectively.”¹⁰⁷ The researcher’s objective was church growth by 10% after implementing a successful women’s program and meeting women's needs. A SWOT analysis was performed to initiate the process of research. SWOT is a method to identify an organization's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats.

Thirteen ladies from the researcher’s church were interviewed and asked twenty open-ended questions. Six other questions were asked on a Likert Scale to measure the success of the church in meeting the needs of women. After the interviews were completed and analyzed, several themes emerged as important to women—trust, confidentiality, unity, safety, consistency, leadership, and outreach. After the research project was concluded, the researcher stated, “Even though the intervention plan did not yield the expected results of growing the church by 10%

¹⁰⁵ Park, “An Effective Strategy for Church Revitalization through a Case Study of Hosanna Church,” 117.

¹⁰⁶ Dennis McCullough, “Church Revitalization through Effective Women’s Ministry” (Doctor of Ministry Research Paper, Liberty University School of Divinity, 2020), 13.

¹⁰⁷ McCullough, “Church Revitalization through Effective Women’s Ministry,” 55.

through effective women's ministry, it did reveal that senior leadership has a profound consequence on the effectiveness of a successful women's ministry."¹⁰⁸ The presence and influence of women within the local church is important, but this study pertains to the emphasis that the Bible places on the patriarchal nature of New Testament leadership for the growth and health of the church.

Although McCullough's research did not yield the "expected results," his approach is vital as a revitalization strategy. In the literature reviewed, no other research specifically targeted women as a critical revitalization factor. This finding should be placed in the context that women often attend churches that need revitalization. Although the importance of men and their leadership cannot be overestimated, neither should the role that women play in revitalization be underestimated. Appropriate strategies for women within the church should be further investigated.

In his 2014 research, Wayne Rogers focused on declining Southern Baptist Churches. Concerning the purpose of his study, Rogers notes,

Pastors, denominational leaders, and a congregation who have been involved in revitalizing churches will be surveyed and interviewed to gather their recommendations, pitfalls to avoid, and strategies to employ. The thesis will conclude with a plan to be presented to pastors and other denominational leaders to encourage them to consider investing in established churches.¹⁰⁹

¹⁰⁸ McCullough, "Church Revitalization through Effective Women's Ministry," 91.

¹⁰⁹ Wayne E. Rogers, "Overcoming Church Euthanasia: A Plan to Revitalize Dead and Dying Churches within the Southern Baptist Convention," (Doctoral Thesis, Liberty University Baptist Theological Seminary, 2014), ii.

Rogers states that there are “five keys of fundamental foundation” for Southern Baptist Churches and that each is crucial to the revitalization process.¹¹⁰ Those keys derived from Scripture are (1) leadership, (2) teaching and preaching the Bible, (3) the priesthood of the believer, (4) the ordinances of baptism and the Lord’s Supper, and (5) intimacy with God through prayer. Rogers states, “These five foundational keys are essential in overcoming church euthanasia and developing a plan to revitalize dead and dying Southern Baptist Churches.”¹¹¹ As other researchers did, Rogers also emphasizes the goal of revitalization as health, not growth. He states, “Reintroducing dead and dying Southern Baptist churches to the keys of church health, if implemented, will produce good health, which will produce growth. A healthy church is the first step into becoming a revitalized church.”¹¹² The natural result of a healthy church is growth.

The basic methodology of this study involved conducting personal interviews with pastors who lead revitalized churches. Surveys of individual churches, as well as denomination leaders, were also conducted. After collecting and analyzing the data, an action plan involving 14 steps was developed to help others understand how to revitalize dead and dying Southern Baptist churches.

The recommended plan for revitalization is described in the following steps, some of which apply only to Southern Baptist Convention churches: (1) Southern Baptist Convention entities will communicate better with churches; (2) it will develop a database that provides assessments and initiates workshops [The data indicated that over 97.7 percent of SBC leaders

¹¹⁰ Rogers, “Overcoming Church Euthanasia: A Plan to Revitalize Dead and Dying Churches within the Southern Baptist Convention,” 6.

¹¹¹ Rogers, “Overcoming Church Euthanasia: A Plan to Revitalize Dead and Dying Churches within the Southern Baptist Convention,” 9.

¹¹² Rogers, “Overcoming Church Euthanasia: A Plan to Revitalize Dead and Dying Churches within the Southern Baptist Convention,” 18.

want a database of healthy, growing churches willing to help dying churches.]; (3) it will begin a national revitalization emphasis; (4) the North American Mission Board (NAMB) website will be friendlier to declining churches [At the time of this research, there were only four options for declining churches: close, replant, become a campus location for a multi-church plant, or merge with another church.]; (5) the Southern Baptist identity must be preserved [The SBC church must maintain its heritage of doctrinal understanding and the implications that follow.]; (6) the church needs to learn how to exercise Scripture-fed or worship-based prayer as defined by Daniel Henderson; (7) the church must create plan and vision, for without a plan and vision, the church may suffer early setbacks that could imperil the church's revitalizing efforts; (8) the gospel message must be preached [SBC churches need to preach the text of Scripture. It is essential for a church needing revitalization that it calls a godly man who is a text-driven preacher]; (9) churches in revitalization must trust the pastoral leadership [This is not only essential, but it is crucial for success in the revitalization process.]; (10) a revitalized church must be committed to caring relationships, servant leadership, and keeping an outward focus; (11) loving church discipline must be essential in many and maybe all SBC churches that are in decline or dying [Statistics reveal that church dysfunction, bad habits, and sinful spiritual issues have led to the decline and eventual death of many churches]; (12) God must call the senior pastor to lead the church [This is one of the most overlooked, essential steps that must be followed if the church truly seeks a successful revitalization process]; (13) pastors and churches must be re-educated on the biblical and historical importance of the two ordinances of the Lord's Supper and baptism; (14) churches need to be re-educated about the priesthood of the believer.

Also helpful in this study is a brief analysis of five different approaches to, and understandings of, church revitalization strategy. These five approaches are listed on pages 45–63 of Roger’s research paper.¹¹³

1. The church revitalization method – Tom Cheney’s *Thirty-Eight Church Revitalization Models for the Twenty-First Century* centers on seven pillars to renovate the church: revitalization, refocusing, revisionizing, renewal, reinvention, restoration, restart, and repotting).
2. In Kevin G. Harney and Bob Bouwer’s *The U-Turn Church: New Direction for Health and Growth*, eleven factors for a revitalized church are identified: “Holy Zeal, Urgency, Crystal- Clear Vision, the Power of Prayer, commitment to apostolic [biblical] teaching, unleashing leaders, high expectations, tough skin and soft hearts, taking holy risks, looking out, and the wow factor.”¹¹⁴
3. Harry Reeder’s *From Embers to a Flame: How God Can Revitalize Your Church* gives a helpful summary of this model:

Reeder’s theory, model, or method is a ten-point strategy which is listed as one. [First], connect to the past by learning from the past without living in the past. Second, a call to repentance by not covering up but fessing up. Third, [One must be] Gospel-driven. [This] drives a person to live a Christ-filled life. Fourth, personal Gospel formation expands the discipline of grace. Fifth, the priority of intercessory prayer produces the ministry of prayer. Sixth, the primacy of preaching sets in place a Word-based ministry. Seventh, staying on mission with a vision requires simplicity and focus. Eighth, servant leadership multiplication is the most neglected strategy for church vitality. Ninth, small group discipleship is the biblical delivery system for the local church. Tenth, to be a W.E.L.L. Church, a church must have a great commitment to the Great Commission.¹¹⁵

¹¹³ Rogers, “Overcoming Church Euthanasia: A Plan to Revitalize Dead and Dying Churches within the Southern Baptist Convention,” 45–63.

¹¹⁴ Rogers, “Overcoming Church Euthanasia,” 51–53.

¹¹⁵ Rogers, “Overcoming Church Euthanasia,” 54.

4. Mark Devine and Darrin Patrick's *Replant: How a Dying Church Can Grow Again* model is a basic description of merging two churches: a struggling or dying congregation and a vibrant or growing congregation.
5. Ed Stetzer and Mike Dodson's model in *Comeback Churches: How 300 Churches Turned Around and Yours Can Too* makes the following connections: foundations (without the proper foundation, nothing stands long term); leadership (essential for any success), faith factors (a necessity for any turn-around), worship and preaching (these are extremely important); evangelistic focus (at home and internationally), spiritual maturity (Christian growth), motivation (a passion and vision), connecting people (through small groups).

Exposure to these different approaches is helpful because each church and each situation is spiritually and practically unique. Remembering this fact helps revitalizers and churches avoid cookie-cutter approaches to church revitalization. Spiritual wisdom and discernment are paramount.

One final point from Rodger's paper is the reflective section on what causes a church to decline.¹¹⁶ Learning how a church arrived at a need of revitalization provides a helpful roadmap for returning to the place of vitality! The ten points Rodgers identifies as the cause of church decline are (1) a slow decline in outward focus and community neglect, (2) a decline caused by the success of the past's glory years, (3) a rejection of hospitality to the community, (4) a failure of stewardship and generosity to meet sacrificial levels for the sake of Christ, (5) a slowing or stopping of evangelism throughout the world, (6) a partaking in pleasure while rejecting the

¹¹⁶ Rogers, "Overcoming Church Euthanasia," 40–45.

cross, (7) a poor pastoral call and lack of Spirit-filled preaching, (8) a wrong perspective on prayer as something to do instead of something done, (9) a loss of direction for the church, (10) an allowance of laziness and fatness to enter the church. These findings correlate loosely with the findings of another researcher previously mentioned, Patterson, who observed the following six causes of decline: loss of vision, aging congregation, inward focus, poor leadership, spiritual unhealthiness, and internal power struggles.¹¹⁷

A 2009 research paper by Johnny Kendrick reveals his efforts to identify reproducible principles or strategies for revitalizing small to medium-sized, plateaued, or declining traditional churches.¹¹⁸ Kendrick pastored two churches that needed revitalization, one for five years and one (at the time of his thesis) for six years. During his work in these churches, Kendrick identified four important principles as key to revitalization: “1) the importance of preparing for Sunday morning worship and Sunday School, 2) the importance of developing leadership, 3) the importance of evaluating and implementing successful ministries, and 4) the importance of identifying with the community.”¹¹⁹ These foci became the areas of interest in his research project.

After identifying these four areas in his ministry, Kendrick examined the literature for information about these concepts and “what was said about them.”¹²⁰ After the literature review,

¹¹⁷ Patterson, “Identifying Common Procedures for Revitalization Leaders When Initiating Turnaround Strategies in Declining Churches,” 125.

¹¹⁸ Johnny Lamar Kendrick, “Narrow Your Focus: A Strategy for Revitalizing Small to Medium Sized Plateaued or Declining Traditional Churches” (Doctoral Thesis Project, Liberty Baptist Theological Seminary, 2009), i.

¹¹⁹ Kendrick, “Narrow Your Focus: A Strategy for Revitalizing Small to Medium Sized Plateaued or Declining Traditional Churches,” i.

¹²⁰ Kendrick, “Narrow Your Focus: A Strategy for Revitalizing Small to Medium Sized Plateaued or Declining Traditional Churches,” 19.

Kendrick met with two other churches or leaders to discuss these four principles and whether they apply to another church. No specific information was listed on what these meetings with other church leaders looked like or entailed.

In the concluding chapter, the author digests much of the previous material and distills it into the following observations: “Revitalization takes a special leader. Revitalization requires a commitment of time (five to ten years). Revitalization often requires a narrowing of ministry focus for a time. Spiritual revival must not be overlooked in the process of revitalization.”¹²¹ Each of these observations became valuable conclusions in his research concerning the nature of revitalization.

A case study by Rodney Sprayberry focuses on a rural Southern Baptist church that needed to be revitalized. The paper reflects the metamorphosis of the researcher’s understanding concerning the revitalization of this church. In this study, the researcher engaged (on two separate occasions) with a church that had been stagnant for three decades. During the second pastorate, he began the research program, intent on administering a strategic revitalization plan. However, during the study, he determined that another revitalization process was required, which included the church embracing an identity as a “relational, biological, organic community.”¹²² According to Sprayberry, this identity contrasted with the traditional, rationally structured, task-driven, goal-oriented organization. Sprayberry deemed it better to have this church positioned as a “strategic mission post” in the modern world and embrace its small-church orientation.¹²³

¹²¹ Kendrick, “Narrow Your Focus: A Strategy for Revitalizing Small to Medium Sized Plateaued or Declining Traditional Churches,” 122–123.

¹²² Sprayberry, “The Revitalization Process in a Small Rural Plateaued Southern Baptist Church,” v.

¹²³ Sprayberry, “The Revitalization Process in a Small Rural Plateaued Southern Baptist Church,” 5.

In 2006, Sprayberry and the church began working on a strategic plan for NZBC. During this strategic planning process, the study's goal was changed. The revitalization idea propounded in this study—that a church be considered a “mission post. . . embracing its small church orientation, rather than change it”—was a unique observation and approach among the research studies.¹²⁴

If revitalization is the goal, then remaining stagnant is neglectful, especially if the church needs to change. However, Sprayberry is not suggesting that the church be left as is, but that it be recognized for what it is: “a relational, biological, and organic community,” and not “a rationally structured, task-driven, goal-oriented organization.”¹²⁵ Sprayberry certainly helped the church make changes. For example, the church changed the worship style. The church hired a part-time secretary. Record-keeping services were upgraded. A children’s ministry program was renewed. Also, a building program that had been previously started was finished. A special meeting was held for the renewal of core values and priorities. An attempt to establish a new constitution and bylaws was engaged. Committees were replaced with ministry teams. Small group in-home Bible studies were started as an outreach tool.¹²⁶

Though 2007 and 2008 were statistically significant years for the church, recurring undercurrents of disharmony began to manifest themselves again. Spayberry writes, “The constitution and bylaws committee became deadlocked over personal, doctrinal, and organizational disagreements.” Christian school conflicts began to manifest themselves again,

¹²⁴ Sprayberry, “The Revitalization Process in a Small Rural Plateaued Southern Baptist Church,” v.

¹²⁵ Sprayberry, “The Revitalization Process in a Small Rural Plateaued Southern Baptist Church,” v.

¹²⁶ Sprayberry, “The Revitalization Process in a Small Rural Plateaued Southern Baptist Church,” 63–65, 69–71.

and soon, attendance and giving began to drop off, and the initial “energy and excitement” basically “dried up by 2009.”¹²⁷ These factors led to Sprayberry’s gaining new insights.

Eventually, Sprayberry realized the mistakes that he had made in the process and shared those realizations with his readers. First, he realized that he had been too quick in attempting to change the church culture. Second, he realized that he had primarily tried “organizational change” rather than “organic change.”¹²⁸ At the end of a four-year process, the researcher made the following painful admission:

For a little over two years, the statistics suggested growth. Baptisms, attendance, and financial support were all increasing. But, life transformation was scant. People were joining, but most were coming from other churches. Some of them were good solid mature believers that have become important parts of the church family. But, most were simply church hoppers. . . . As a whole, though painful to admit, most of the growth and activity has been superficial.¹²⁹

According to Sprayberry, the pastor who attempts to revitalize a church must know that moving forward will take prolonged stages. Sprayberry references this timespan while discussing the problem of short pastoral tenures in this church. He states,

This history of NZBC suggests the truthfulness of an observation that Warren makes. ‘Healthy churches are led by a pastor who has been there a long time. A long pastorate does not guarantee a church will grow, but changing pastors every few years guarantees a church won’t grow.’ Dan Sutherland is even more pointed. ‘If you are on your way to another ministry do not dare make changes. If you are not willing to stay, if you are not willing to go slow then don’t make changes.’¹³⁰

After this research project, Sprayberry came to several conclusions.

Good organization is important in revitalization but it is not the key. . . . Small churches need to cultivate kingdom thinking rather than church thinking. . . . Small churches move

¹²⁷ Sprayberry, “The Revitalization Process in a Small Rural Plateaued Southern Baptist Church,” 72.

¹²⁸ Sprayberry, “The Revitalization Process in a Small Rural Plateaued Southern Baptist Church,” 82, 88.

¹²⁹ Sprayberry, “The Revitalization Process in a Small Rural Plateaued Southern Baptist Church,” 103–104.

¹³⁰ Sprayberry, “The Revitalization Process in a Small Rural Plateaued Southern Baptist Church,” 52.

ahead through exploration of the past. . . . Small churches are organized around the assumption of scarcity of resources. . . . Small church leaders must NOT do it all, on purpose. . . . Indigenous leadership is crucial in the small church. . . . Discipleship, evangelism, and ministry occur best through existing relationships.¹³¹

Another researcher, Lisa Marie Sullivan, studied the revitalization of multiple Methodist churches from an urban perspective. Sullivan writes,

This study was conducted to assist in the understanding of church revitalization among Methodist churches. The study included the major geographical areas of the United States. Churches of differing sizes, located in communities or cities of varying sizes, created a heterogeneous cross-section of the churches included in the study. . . . All of the churches were . . . existing churches that had experienced revitalization following a period of decline. Four churches participated in case study (surveys and) interviews by telephone, with both the senior pastor and a lay member in congregational leadership interviewed at separate times.¹³²

Revitalization factors discovered through this research were consistent with other studies.

Sullivan states,

Analysis of commonly shared key factors in the turnaround process revealed the necessary foundational components of revitalization. Major findings revealed a list of recurrent factors and common denominators necessary for a successful turnaround. The change process was more flexible and organic in nature and required a large investment of time, effort, and physical, emotional, and spiritual perseverance to achieve new vitality and church health.¹³³

During the multi-case study, some common factors among the cases correlated with the revitalization process, as found in other studies. These factors were as follows:

Changes made in the worship style or format were made to become invitational and connect in relevant ways with the changing demographics of the surrounding community. Outreach to the community addressing felt needs was an essential bridge to reconnect with the neighborhood outside the walls of the church. Structural changes of some sort

¹³¹ Sprayberry, "The Revitalization Process in a Small Rural Plateaued Southern Baptist Church," 104–113.

¹³² Lisa Marie Sullivan, "Revitalization of the Urban Church: A Multi-case Study of Turnaround Churches" (Doctoral Dissertation, Asbury Theological Seminary, 2009), 6.

¹³³ Sullivan, "Revitalization of the Urban Church: A Multi-case Study of Turnaround Churches," 1.

occurred to the interior and in some instances the exterior of the church. These changes had symbolic meaning for the church and were visible signs to the surrounding community. Visibility in the community increased as the church made turnaround changes. Staff and pastoral changes were catalysts for revitalization. Leadership training was essential to facilitate transition and to achieve success in revitalization. A new missional focus facilitated lay leadership development. Strategies for how to proceed with revitalization were not always clear from the onset and were intentional and organic at the same time. Acceptance of loss (of the past) and letting go were important turning points for achieving a new forward momentum toward revitalization.¹³⁴

Another doctoral project study, reviewed under the category of church health and assessment and the leadership heading, chronicled the revitalization of the New Life Praise Church among the Southern Baptist Sandy Creek Association of churches. This 2016 research follows the deployment of the small-group-mentality efforts promoted by many church-renewal advocates and specifically championed by Ed Stetzer and Mike Dodson. When this study was conducted, the accepted response to the deplorable condition of declining churches was to plant new churches. Today, there is greater interest in the revitalization of those declining churches.¹³⁵

An eight-step renewal process was employed, which utilized the “Church Renewal Journey” development of small groups. All eight steps grew primarily from the theoretical foundations of three men’s works: David Jeremiah’s *Reset: Ten Steps for Spiritual Renewal*, Thom Rainer’s *Simple Church*, and the *Church Renewal Journey program*, which is a five-weekend program that plays out over five years.¹³⁶ The eight-step strategy outline of revitalization includes (1) prayer and discernment concerning God’s desire, (2) planning and processing with key leadership which initiates discipleship, (3) strategic planning to create or recreate a mission or vision statement, (4) preaching for revitalization, which involves preaching

¹³⁴ Sullivan, “Revitalization of the Urban Church: A Multi-case Study of Turnaround Churches,” 78.

¹³⁵ Chappell, “Dead Bones Rising,” 4.

¹³⁶ Chappell, “Dead Bones Rising,” 64–68.

for transformation, expository preaching, and preaching that includes praise, passion, and relevance, (5) evaluation, (6) establishing small groups with lay leadership, (7) observation and learning, and lastly (8) educating the group leaders and celebrating successes.

Realizing that small group development is an option for church revitalization is helpful, but it must be recognized, as it is in this study, as nonessential. It is an optional tool to be used by the revitalization pastor as needed. Small groups can be restructured in more than one way to initiate and achieve revitalization.

A 1991 study was conducted on what was termed “breakout churches.” These are churches that experience rapid growth after years of statistical plateaus. Revitalization variables (strategies) were identified. Of the breakout churches, 97.5 percent were determined by twelve variables, two of the most reproducible being *evangelism* and *goal orientation*.¹³⁷ The twelve variables as given in this study are as follows: facilities and setting, congregational structure, congregational character, planning and goal setting, pastor and staff, evangelism and outreach, Sunday school, worship, other church programs, integration and assimilation, morale and desire for growth, and spiritual emphasis and renewal.

The top five categories, which allow the highest levels of discrimination and predict “breakout” growth, are as follows:

1. Congregational structure (83.1 percent). This section dealt with five variables: the age structure of the church, the size of the church in 1983, the percentage of members attending church on a given Sunday, the year the church was organized, and the percentage earning under \$15,000. The strongest correlation with breakout growth was

¹³⁷ C. Kirk Hadaway, “From Stability to Growth: A Study of Factors Related to the Statistical Revitalization of Southern Baptist Congregations,” *Journal for the Scientific Study of Religion* 30, no. 2 (1991): 181–192.

the age structure scale. Churches that were dominated by the elderly were less likely to experience breakout growth than were those that had more baby-boomer adults. Another important concept in this category was the size of the church. Smaller churches, although not defined in this study, were better positioned for growth than larger churches.

2. Morale and desire for growth (73.5 percent). Optimism, purpose, and belief that growth is possible were strongly correlated with breakout growth.
3. Evangelism and outreach (73.3 percent). Biological percentage of additions is typical of plateaued churches, while a church that truly escapes the plateau must engage in conversion growth.
4. Spiritual emphasis and renewal (72.6 percent). This section dealt with prayer and the spiritual growth of members. This emphasis tended to result in a renewal of confidence and commitment. This scale was strongly correlated with breakout growth.
5. Pastor and staff (71.6 percent). Specific identifiers related to the pastor predicted breakout growth. A new pastor tended to be associated with breakout growth. The pastor of breakout churches usually generates enthusiasm and challenges thinking. The percentage of the church budget for salaries also correlates with breakout growth. Pastors of breakout churches tend to have a vision, be hard-working, and exhibit patience. Breakout pastors view the Bible as inerrant. The pastor can motivate the church members to engage in the work necessary for growth.

These five variables were identified in 85 percent of breakout churches. These findings, among others, are relevant to the current case study. The common denominators of church revitalization are being sought to assist in the recovery of Independent Baptist churches. If the pattern is consistent, these factors should be evident in the case study and should support future revitalization works among Independent Baptist churches. For example, evangelism and outreach, as well as pastoral leadership, are critical to revitalizing all churches evaluated in these studies.

Conclusion of Revitalization Strategies Literature

The most prominent topic that researchers evaluate concerning revitalization is strategy studies. Pastors want to know how to keep a church alive and thriving. This section has described a selection of relevant research related to factors that may predict successful revitalization. However, none of them come specifically from the perspective of an Independent Baptist church.

Though this section is perhaps the most robust in a discussion of revitalization, the results of these studies are relatively predictable. Based on the review of the literature, one of the chief characteristics needed for church revitalization is biblically qualified, spirit-gifted, and adequately trained leadership. Furthermore, understanding a church's context and where a particular church may be in terms of its lifecycle provides a platform from which to initiate change. Following the biblical pattern of evangelism and discipleship in their current context, leadership should be able to attain and maintain a church moving forward. However, the specifics are more complicated than that. Many confounding factors interplay in the revitalization of a church. Many things can go wrong, from sin issues, personality conflicts, poor community culture, and deliberate saboteurs or troublemakers.

More data is needed on Independent Baptist churches that have succeeded in overcoming obstacles while honoring the teachings of the Bible in every area. This data needs to include all areas targeted in the current literature (i. e., leadership preparation and strategy) and those particularly related to Independent Baptist churches (i.e., navigating issues related to holiness and worldliness, translation and preservation issues, and music and worship).

Interpretive Summary of Literature

An increasing wealth of biblical and practical revitalization data is becoming available. When considering and attempting to understand the Bible's emphasis on this matter, the foundational examples are (1) Jeremiah's ministry with its focus on decline and renewal, (2) the Pauline method of establishing and strengthening churches, and (3) the Lord Jesus' emphases with the churches in the second and third chapters of the book of Revelation to prevent them from being spewed out of his mouth (or having their candlestick removed). Further, these passages reveal the true meaning of church revitalization ministry. The Bible, as well as the literature, establish that church revitalization ministry is not about church growth but rather church health. The Bible's theological emphasis on this area of revitalization is, if properly understood and presented, one of the central factors that establish the credibility of this movement.

Literature on revitalization reveals an attempt to understand and overcome the decline witnessed among churches. As the data on church revitalization is reviewed, it becomes clear that significant areas of emphasis are church lifecycle, church assessment or health, leadership, and strategy. Please see Appendix G for a thorough list of all revitalization characteristics, minus the Leadership characteristics listed in Appendix F that were discovered in the literature review.

These areas of emphasis are what past and current revitalization research has focused on. These areas would also, potentially, be evident in the revitalization of Independent Baptist churches.

Each of the above categories (church lifecycle, church assessment or health, leadership, and strategies) are unique, but characteristics often overlap within the various categories. This overlap is to be expected since the nature of revitalization and those who participate in its process is organic, integrative, and interconnected. The following summary of characteristics in each category is not comprehensive, but it will cover literature-suggested subcategories. As a clear statement of categories and subcategories, the following is given:

1. Church lifecycle. Three concepts will be considered—purpose, vision, and mission—as well as four organizing principles—leadership, relationship experiences, programmatic emphases, and accountable management.
2. Church Assessment or Health. The two subcategories that will be covered are worship and community engagement.
3. Leadership. The two subcategories to be discussed are goal-driven leadership and pastoral leadership.
4. Strategy. The two subcategories are evangelism and discipleship.

Church Lifecycle

As mentioned previously, the church lifecycle theory was not developed specifically with church revitalization in mind. It was designed as a generalized overview of the organizational life process of a church from birth to death. Along with an understanding of organization lifecycles, one must also keep in mind the concept of individual health cycles. Health cycles are individual starts or restarts within an existing ministry designed to breathe new life into that work and

enhance its effectiveness. A true revitalization work requires more than just a new ministry or emphasis. Notwithstanding, these lifecycle or health cycle theories can be used to identify and examine characteristics that will be present during the renewal process.

First, when a new church starts, it usually has a sense of purpose, vision, or mission. If a work is in a persistent state of decline, then its mission, vision, and purpose have often been lost or severely diminished. In revitalization work, a renewal of mission, purpose, and vision is expected. It is also expected that a truly biblical revitalization process would include foundational teachings of the Bible that strongly support those three concepts.

Second, the lifecycle of the church has been described as having four organizing principles: leadership, relationship experiences, programmatic emphases, and accountable management.¹³⁸ These four organizing principles are operative throughout the congregation's life process. Leadership is listed first because all of the other elements hinge upon it. Leadership is so prominent in the literature that it will be considered as its own category. Although not all churches can be revived even with good leadership, if a church has been successfully revitalized its success would be due, in part, to competent leadership.

Church Assessment and Health

The next important segment to be summarized from the literature (and one that will be considered during the research project itself), is church assessment and health. Many sources emphasize that growth in a church is not the goal. Although a healthy church will indeed grow both spiritually and numerically, a church may grow numerically and yet not be healthy. A

¹³⁸ George Bullard, *The Congregational Life Cycle: A Spiritual Strategic Journey* (Playbook Resource, 2021), 3–6.

struggling, weak, declining church is evidence of a health problem. In either instance, an unhealthy church must be brought back to a state of health for it to effectively fulfill the purpose, mission, and vision of the church as mandated by Christ and clarified in the Bible. For a church to be successfully revitalized, its emphasis must be understanding the health of the congregation in its various parts. As one looks at the health of the congregations from various aspects, eventually, the overall health of the congregation will be evident and undeniable.

One element of a church's health is worship. Worship is at the center of the life of the church. Everything that the church does should grow out of its worship to God. Throughout the literature, worship was listed as an important factor when assessing a church's health. It was even identified as one of the chief methods of revitalization. The literature always emphasized a change to a contemporary style of worship to connect with those who attend. The idea is that this change in worship will induce vitality.

Another element of health leading to a revived church is its involvement in the community. Often, declining churches have an inward focus detached from the community around them. A church cannot change its community without engaging that community. A church's outreach efforts, community involvement, and its impact on addressing local needs must be considered in the revitalization of the church. When a church turns inward and fails to realize and engage its primary purpose of world transformation through the power of the gospel, it is in great danger and needs revitalization. Conversely, when the church is alive and vibrant, it will be actively pursuing and engaged in this primary purpose.

Leadership

Coursing throughout each stage of the church's lifecycle and heavily influencing the strategic ministry of the church is leadership. Leadership is heavily referenced throughout the literature on church revitalization. Leadership should be considered in its comprehensive aspect. Leadership is not just vested in the pastor or pastoral staff. During revitalization work, all forms of leadership manifesting within the church should be considered, consolidated, and coalesced for the health, security, and forward progress of the church. Errant leadership is devastating to the work of revitalization. Two separate aspects of leadership must be considered.

First, leadership must be considered in its ability to establish and achieve goals. Leadership is not just charisma. Leadership is not just good ideas. Good ideas and charisma are not enough in revitalization work. Leadership must have the ability to wisely determine goals, consistent with the current state of the church, and then implement measures to achieve those goals. Small goals, easily achieved, are much better than large goals that are difficult to achieve. Early successes provide momentum and a positive spirit. Leadership is also important in another sense. Many struggling churches find it difficult to trust their leaders. A lack of trust in the pastor is devastating to the work of revitalization. The ability of the pastor to effectively lead, even in small, basic, and foundational matters will help the people build trust in him.

Second, leadership must be pastoral. When all of the characteristics of leadership are considered, this aspect of leadership (although not effectively communicated in the literature) is perhaps the most important characteristic to consider. The revitalization of a church is a spiritual and organic experience, not an academic one. Although the academics (the core components necessary to achieve revitalization) can be pedantically understood and diligently applied, only a

pastor's loving and caring heart, sensitive to the leadership of the Holy Spirit, can effectively revitalize a church.

Strategy

The literature review is heavily weighted toward strategy in revitalization. It has been the desire of researchers to understand the building blocks of revitalization; and this desire, of necessity, has led to an evaluation of the strategic mechanisms variously applied and the effectiveness of the mechanisms in studied ministries. The bulk of strategy studies deal with two broad overarching categories: evangelism and discipleship. Evangelism involves all aspects of church work that convert individuals from unbelief to belief. Discipleship, an integral part of evangelism, is any activity designed to lead that convert to greater devotion and dedication to Christ and His work. A healthy church will conduct all of its ministries with these two goals in mind. In revitalization work, evangelism and discipleship are key ingredients.

Chapter 3

Project Narrative

Although much study concerning church revitalization has been done, little valid research has been conducted on Independent Baptist church revitalization. This current researcher sought to answer the question, “What characteristics of the two churches led to their successful revitalization?”

The goal of this study was to determine the core revitalization characteristics that led to the revitalization of two Independent Baptist churches. It is the desire of the researcher that these identified characteristics then be used, broadly, as the foundation for revitalizing Independent Baptist churches.

Research Methodology

The research methodology chosen for this project was the retrospective cohort case study. Both of the studied churches are still being pastored by the same pastors whom the Lord used to revitalize the churches. One has been at his church for almost twenty-five years, and the other pastor has been at his church for nearly ten years. The cohort case study methodology is well-suited for evaluating groups over time. In this method, the researcher analyzed, historically, two churches and their leaders, as a basis for drawing inferences and preliminary conclusions for similar ministry situations. The researcher may use his analysis to suggest ways to improve or guide a similar situation in ministry.

Data Collection

The primary data sources for this research were two lead pastors as well as four other people in the church who answered questions and made themselves available for interviews. These people were knowledgeable about the history of the studied church.

This research used personal interviews with the lead pastors and the Church Health Assessment questionnaire of Thom Rainer. A copy of the adapted questionnaire has been placed at the end of this paper (see Appendix A). No major problems in collecting the data occurred. The lead pastoral interviews were recorded and transcribed. The transcription of the recorded conversations is also included as Appendix H.

Study Results

The results of the study have been compiled using a software program called Dedoose. This software is useful for data management, excerpting, coding, and analysis in qualitative and mixed-methods research. The results of this inquiry about the revitalization of Independent Baptist churches will begin with a few charts and a discussion about the charts.

As has been previously stated, the goal of this research was to identify characteristics that were involved in the revitalization of two Independent Baptist churches. During this research, composed of questionnaires and personal interviews, the following four key characteristics of revitalization were identified as well as the related supplementary characteristics.

Table 3.1: List of Codes/Characteristics of Revitalization

Leadership	Church Lifecycle	Church Assessment (Health)	Strategy
Goal Driven Leadership	Programmatic Emphases	Community Engagement	Evangelism
Pastoral Leadership	Leadership	Worship	Discipleship
	Mission		
	Purpose		
	Relationship Experiences		
	Vision		

Source: Current Research Study

As mentioned before, each interviewee filled out the questionnaire twice, once while remembering what the church was like when he first arrived and once while describing how the church is currently. The characteristics identified in the questionnaire were key influencers in the revitalization process of the studied churches.

A *code* in the Dedoose software program is a designated study area. In this research, there were four major (parent) codes identified relating to church revitalization. These codes were *leadership*, *church lifecycle*, *church assessment (health)*, and *strategy*. Each of these parent codes was further divided into separate and distinct categories. Leadership was further divided into *goal-driven leadership* and *pastoral leadership*. Church lifecycle was divided into six subcategories: programmatic emphases, leadership (lifecycle), mission, purpose, relationship experiences, and vision. Church assessment (health) was further divided into *community engagement* and *worship*. The final parent code (strategy) was further divided into *evangelism* and *discipleship*.

Another name for a code application chart is *frequency table*. The following table presents the frequency with which codes (rows) were applied to excerpts in each media-file interview (columns). The interviews were analyzed three times to enhance the accuracy of consistency and coding. Tables such as these are useful in visualizing how a code system has been applied across media files or other data.

Table 3.2. Code Applications

	First Pass LP 1	First Pass LP 2	Second Pass LP 1	Second Pass LP 2	Third Pass LP 1	Third Pass LP 2	Totals
Leadership	31	41	19	21	26	24	162
Goal-driven Leadership	12	8	6	4	16	5	51
Pastoral Leadership	15	33	14	17	13	19	111
Church Lifecycle	44	61	26	39	35	58	263
Programmatic Emphases	12	9	3	7	13	15	59
Leadership (Lifecycle)	28	35	18	20	21	22	144
Mission	8	13	8	7	10	10	56
Purpose	3	2	4	7	5	10	31
Relationship Experiences	1	8	2	11	4	18	44
Vision	7	18	6	2	7	7	47
Church Assessment - Health	26	22	16	22	20	25	131
Community Engagement	16	19	10	12	15	22	94
Worship	10	3	6	10	5	3	37
Strategy	12	38	13	23	15	32	133
Discipleship	4	27	3	17	6	21	78
Evangelism	8	13	12	7	14	16	70
Totals	237	350	166	226	225	307	0

Source: Code Applications To Excerpts – Current Research Evaluation

If these factors are ranked in order of frequency mentioned, the Church Lifecycle is first at 263, and Leadership is next at 162. Strategy is identified by 133 code applications, and Church Assessment Health is last with 131 applications. Looking a bit deeper, one can see that

Leadership (combined) is ranked as the number one factor in the revitalization of these churches (306 times). The next highest category is Community Engagement (94 times). Discipleship is ranked third in mentions (78), followed by Evangelism (70). Completing the top five is Programmatic Emphases (59).

These results were also represented in a Packed Code Cloud. Here, all of the codes are listed with bigger or smaller words depending on the number of times this particular code was attached to specific statements gathered during the interview process. The number of code applications is also present within each of these codes. When the cursor is hovered over the words (in the actual Dedoose program), numbers are presented.

Figure 3. Packed Code Cloud Representing Frequency of Code Application

Source: Data from a Packed Code Cloud featuring words from interview statements.

Church Lifecycle, including parent and child codes, appears largest on the cloud with 644 matching excerpts. The Leadership code, including parent and child codes, is the second largest with 324 excerpts. The Strategy code was third largest with 281 matching excerpts. The fourth largest was the code Church Assessment - Health, with 262 codes. The interviewees indicate by their statements that leadership is key to revitalization during any lifecycle stage. The revitalization of these churches was heavily influenced by strategy (Discipleship and Evangelism) as well as by fostering the health of the church (through Community Engagement and Worship).

Another chart is the Code Co-occurrence chart. This chart is important for several reasons. One reason is that it shows all of the individual parent codes as well as the child codes in an organized fashion. Each number on the table represents a single excerpt from the interviewee. This chart also represents what was considered important to the interviewees, as evidenced by the numbers listed. The higher the number, the higher frequency at which these items were discussed. Again, the top three revitalization emphases discussed were Leadership - Pastoral/Goal-directed/Lifecycle (1434), Strategy (696), and Church Assessment - Health (546).

The purpose of this table is to show the frequency with which each code (and corresponding excerpt) coexists with other codes. Examining each code helps researchers achieve the goal of identifying leading revitalization characteristics in the studied churches. In turn, this engagement with the data reveals interesting findings such as connections among these variables. Following are the individual tables describing the code co-occurrences. The complete chart is large; therefore, it has been broken down into its individual parent codes (Leadership, Church Lifecycle, Church Assessment/Health, and Strategy).

Table 3.3. Code Co-occurrence Table, Leadership

	Leadership	Goal-Driven Leadership	Pastoral Leadership
Leadership	0	51	110
Goal-Driven Leadership	51	0	5
Pastoral Leadership	110	5	0
Church Lifecycle	153	50	104
Programmatic Emphases	15	10	5
Leadership - Lifecycle	139	44	96
Mission	23	15	8
Purpose	12	8	4
Relationship Experiences	13	5	8
Vision	32	20	12
Church Assessment - Health	35	25	10
Community Engagement	29	23	6
Worship	6	2	4
Strategy	67	26	42
Discipleship	48	11	37
Evangelism	26	20	7
Total	759	315	458

Source: Code Co-occurrence - Leadership Category - Current Research Evaluation

Table 3.4. Code Co-occurrence Table, Church Lifecycle

	Church Lifecycle	Programmatic Emphases	Leadership Lifecycle	Mission	Purpose	Relationship Experiences	Vision
Leadership	153	15	139	23	12	13	32
Goal-Driven Leadership	50	10	44	15	8	5	20
Pastoral Leadership	104	5	96	8	4	8	12
Church Lifecycle	0	59	142	56	31	43	47
Programmatic Emphases	59	0	11	15	6	1	8
Leadership - Lifecycle	142	11	0	19	8	8	25
Mission	56	15	19	0	28	1	18
Purpose	31	6	8	28	0	1	14
Relationship Experiences	43	1	8	1	1	0	5
Vision	47	8	25	18	14	5	0
Church Assessment - Health	89	35	31	29	11	27	20
Community Engagement	83	35	25	29	11	27	19
Worship	6	0	6	0	0	0	1
Strategy	114	32	57	51	27	6	32
Discipleship	64	16	44	10	5	6	17
Evangelism	66	27	20	48	25	2	18
Total	1107	275	675	350	191	153	288

Source: Code Co-occurrence - Lifecycle Category - Current Research Evaluation

Table 3.5. Code Co-occurrence Table, Church Assessment (Health)

	Church Assessment (Health)	Community Engagement	Worship
Leadership	35	29	6
Goal-Driven Leadership	25	23	2
Pastoral Leadership	10	6	4
Church Lifecycle	89	83	6
Programmatic Emphases	35	35	0
Leadership - Lifecycle	31	25	6
Mission	29	29	0
Purpose	11	11	0
Relationship Experiences	27	27	0
Vision	20	19	1
Church Assessment - Health	0	94	37
Community Engagement	94	0	0
Worship	37	0	0
Strategy	47	44	3
Discipleship	18	15	3
Evangelism	38	38	0
Total	546	478	68

Source: Code Co-occurrence - Church Assessment (Health) Category - Current Research Evaluation

Table 3.6. Code Co-Occurrence Table, Strategy

	Strategy	Discipleship	Evangelism
Leadership	67	48	26
Goal-Driven Leadership	26	11	20
Pastoral Leadership	42	37	7
Church Lifecycle	114	64	66
Programmatic Emphases	32	16	27
Leadership - Lifecycle	57	44	20
Mission	51	10	48
Purpose	27	5	25
Relationship Experiences	6	6	2
Vision	32	17	18
Church Assessment - Health	47	18	38
Community Engagement	44	15	38
Worship	3	3	0
Strategy	0	78	70
Discipleship	78	0	16
Evangelism	70	16	0
Total	696	388	421

Source: Code Co-occurrence - Strategy Category - Current Research Evaluation

Leadership

The Leadership parent code co-occurred with all other codes a total of 759 times. If all the leadership categories are combined, the total number of code co-occurrences is 1434. Leadership is by far the largest code connection in the study. Although leadership permeated every other code (parent as well as child), the highest parent code connection was with the Church Lifecycle (153). The Strategy code was next at 67. The final highest parent code connection with Leadership was Church Assessment - Health at 35.

Church Lifecycle

Lifecycle was the second most connected code (1,107). The Lifecycle code was connected to the three other parent codes the following number of times: Leadership (153), Strategy (114), and Church Assessment - Health (89). The key to the whole process of revitalization at these churches (to achieve optimum health) was the ability of the pastor to primarily lead his flock back into ministry, helping them to keep their eyes focused on discipleship and evangelism. Ministry is central to the whole process of revitalization. Many churches that decline acquire an inward or a problem-oriented focus, which is debilitating. This inward focus must be corrected by leadership. The pastor, as well as the people, must actively engage in ministry, specifically, discipleship and evangelism for successful revitalization to occur.

Strategy

The Strategy code totaled 696 code co-occurrences. The three parent codes with which it occurred were Church Lifecycle (114), Leadership, (67), and Church Assessment - Health at 47. The largest child code that Strategy was associated with under the Church Lifecycle parent code was Leadership at 57 co-occurrences. Discipleship and Evangelism, as the two key strategies of the church revitalization (health) process, are dependent upon leadership.

Church Assessment - Health

This code was identified/connected 546 times and most closely occurred with the Evangelism code (38). The Worship Code was the second-highest code co-occurrence at 37. Programmatic Emphases of the Church Lifecycle code were third highest at 35. A healthy church will be a community-engaged church that focuses on evangelism. A healthy church's work and programs grow out of its worship.

Questionnaires Measuring Change Over Time

The following tables present the findings from the questionnaires given to the two lead pastors and two other church members in each church. Each participant completed this questionnaire twice, keeping in mind the two time periods. When data is considered in this way, areas of change toward revitalization are recognizable. The first table (see Appendix I) represents data from the midwestern Church. The second table (see Appendix J) represents data from the southern church. The eight areas studied were Fellowship, Evangelism, Discipleship, Prayer, Ministry, Worship, Doctrine, and Unique. The following table summarizes changes in answers, over time, among the three interviewees of the midwestern church.

Table 3.7. Percentage Change of Answers on Questionnaire, Midwestern Church

	LP1 24-year timespan 1998–2022	FSM1 14-year timespan 2008–2022	FSM2 10-year timespan 2012–2022
Fellowship	25 questions 24 answers change 1 does not change 94% change	25 questions 19 answers change 6 do not change 76% change	25 questions 21 answers change 3 do not change 84% change
Evangelism	25 Questions 18 answers change 7 answers do not change 88% change	25 questions 6 answers change 19 answers do not change 16% change	25 questions 18 answers change 7 answers do not change 72% change
Discipleship	25 questions 22 answers change 3 do not 94% change	25 questions 6 answers change 19 answers do not change 16% change	25 questions 17 answers change 8 answers do not change 68% change
Prayer	25 Questions 18 answers change 7 answers do not change 72% change	25 questions 1 answer changes 24 answers do not change 4% change	25 questions 4 answers changes 21 answers do not change 16 % change
Ministry	25 questions 22 answers change 3 do not change 88% change	25 questions 15 Answers change 10 do not change 60% change	25 questions 19 answers change 6 do not change 76% change
Worship	30 questions 21 answers change 9 answers do not change 70% change	30 questions 4 answers change 26 answers do no change 13% change	30 questions 25 answers change 5 answers do no change 83% change
Doctrine	9 questions 8 answers change 1 answer does not 88% change	9 questions 0 answers change 9 answers do not change 0% change	9 questions 0 answers change 9 answers do not change 0% change
Unique	6 questions 4 answers change 2 answers do not change 66% change	6 questions 2 answers change 4 answers do not change 33% change	6 questions 3 answers change 3 answers do not change 50% change

Source: Data from Current Research - Midwestern Church Evaluation.

Again, collating the data for the southern church questionnaires, the changes in answers over time are evidenced in Table 3.8.

Table 3.8. Percentage Change of Answers on Questionnaire, Southern Church

	LP2 10 year timespan 2012–2022	RSM1 7 year timespan 2015–2022	RSM2 7 year timespan 2015–2022
Fellowship	25 questions 10 answers change 15 do not change 40% change	25 questions 14 answers change 11 answers do not change 56% change	25 questions 8 answers change 17 answers do not change 32% change
Evangelism	25 questions 11 answers change 14 answers do not change 44% change	25 questions 9 answers change 16 answers do not change 36% change	25 questions 7 answers change 18 answers do not change 28% change
Discipleship	25 questions 22 answers change 3 do not 94% change	25 questions 1 answers change 24 answers do not change 40% change	25 questions 8 answers change 17 answers do not change 32% change
Prayer	25 questions 18 answers change 7 answers do not change 72% change	25 questions 1 answer changes 24 answers do not change 4% change	25 questions 9 answers changes 16 answers do not change 36 % change
Ministry	25 questions 22 answers change 3 do not change 88% change	25 questions 8 answers change 17 do not change 32% change	25 questions 12 answers change 13 do not change 48% change
Worship	30 questions 21 answers change 9 answers do not change 70% change	30 questions 6 answers change 24 answers do not change 20% change	30 questions 7 answers change 23 answers do not change 23% change
Doctrine	9 questions 3 answers change 6 answer do not change 33% change	9 questions 0 answers change 9 answers do not change 0% change	9 questions 0 answers change 9 answers do not change 0% change
Unique	6 questions 2 answers change 4 answers do not change 33% change	6 questions 1 answers change 5 answers do not change 16% change	6 questions 1 answer changes 5 answers do not change 16% change

Source: Measuring the percentage of change among interviewees - Current Research - Southern Church

Summary of Research

This research aimed to examine two Independent Baptist churches to determine core revitalization characteristics that could be used to model universal renewal characteristics for Independent Baptist churches. This evaluation achieved a clearer understanding of Independent Baptist church renewal and revitalization. The key characteristics identified were as follows, in their order of importance in this study:

Table 3.9. Key Revitalization Characteristics in Two Independent Baptist Churches

Leadership	Church Lifecycle	Church Assessment (Health)	Strategy
Pastoral Leadership	Leadership	Community Engagement	Discipleship
Goal Driven Leadership	Mission	Worship	Evangelism
	Vision		
	Programmatic Emphases		
	Purpose		
	Relationship Experience		

Source: Current Research - Revitalization Characteristics in Independent Baptist Churches - Order of Importance

Chapter 4

The Project Concluded

The main purpose of this study was to develop a greater understanding of Independent Baptist church renewal and revitalization by researching the literature and conducting an independent research project. The researcher found this project to be particularly necessary when he discovered that no sources specifically target the revitalization of Independent Baptist churches. The goal of this study was to determine core revitalization characteristics in the experience of two Independent Baptist churches. One church was located in the Midwest. The other church was located in the South. The retrospective cohort research method was used to acquire the data necessary to form valid conclusions. Questionnaires were distributed to six participants, and personal interviews with the two lead pastors assisted in the acquisition of data.

Interpretation of Results

During this research, a clearer understanding of Independent Baptist church renewal and revitalization was achieved. The research discovered these five characteristics of revitalization to be associated with the survival and recovery of the two studied churches (ranked by importance): Leadership, Community Engagement, Discipleship, Evangelism, and Programmatic Emphases.

Although leadership was not a characteristic mentioned in Rainer's Church Health Inventory, it was certainly a key factor that permeated every aspect of the recovery process of the two studied churches. Leadership was emphasized in various ways, and it became apparent that this characteristic must be added to the list of characteristics influencing church health and

revitalization. The mantra “everything rises and falls on leadership” is certainly true in this case, as no church can be successfully revitalized without effective leadership.

Ministry (community engagement, programmatic emphases, and evangelism), in its many and varied forms, is identified as an integral part of the revitalization process. Everything living and healthy grows. Sometimes the growth is obvious and sometimes it is not; but there is always action, movement, and growth in any living thing that is healthy or that is becoming healthier. Properly established and managed ministry helps to remove an inward focus. Well-designed ministry helps with the satisfaction and growth of the church. Ministry in a church that is being revitalized must be carefully and prayerfully chosen. The ministry (or ministries) chosen must be appropriate for the church in its present condition and, if at all possible, be a ministry that leads to conversions. Ministries targeting specific community needs are best. Discouraging ministries that are difficult, fatiguing, and largely ineffective for the average Christian (i.e., door-to-door visitation/soul-winning), unless done in a purposeful, natural, or engaging way is very difficult and can quickly produce the perception of failure.

Evangelism or outreach is a needed ingredient in church revitalization. If a church is not growing in this area, eventually the church will decline except for the transfer of membership growth. Interestingly, according to verbal statements made by both pastors, church growth happened mostly by transfer of membership rather than by evangelism. If at all possible, a children’s ministry should be started, and reaching and discipling youth should be emphasized. Other methods of outreach should target adults in the community.

Discipleship, a part of all true evangelism, is important for the viability and sustainability of the body. An active discipleship process must be present to help people grow in Christ. This

process may or may not be an established program of discipleship, but it should always involve leadership modeling proper behavior.

Strengths, Weaknesses, and Limitations

The present study evaluated two churches for revitalization characteristics. Although studies of revitalization characteristics have been done before, to the author's knowledge this study is the first to have been done referencing revitalization characteristics of Independent Baptist churches. The only other study discovered in the literature review was done by Richard Carns, titled *A Rationale For An Independent Baptist Church To Clarify Its Mission, Analyze Its Program, Prioritize Its Objectives and Revitalize Its Ministry*.

Although the present study is groundbreaking in the above sense, it is a small study. More recovered Independent Baptist churches should be studied to provide a greater level of testimony supporting these results. This type of investigation would prove challenging. Originally, the author desired to find churches that had been replanted (shut down and reopened) and had, by this method, been successfully revitalized. The researcher contacted seven individuals who have many years of experience in Independent Baptist church ministry, seeking to find a church that had recovered from a complete closure because of sin (as is the experience of the author's current church) through successful replanting. Not a single person could give the name of one such church.

The author then determined that a church that was in significant decline and that had been revitalized would be the next area to consider. It was also difficult to find an Independent Baptist church that had experienced a successful revitalization while also maintaining a solidly biblical

approach to ministry, not veering off into a “contemporary” philosophy or approach to ministry. Also, both churches discovered in the research were revitalized by full-time pastors from the beginning of the recovery process, a fact not to be overlooked.

This study and its findings are consistent with other research studies of its kind but which come from different religious perspectives. In other words, church revitalization is contingent upon biblically qualified, spirit-gifted, and properly trained leadership following the biblical pattern of evangelism and discipleship in their current context.

Conclusions

In summary, the author feels, based on the previously mentioned data, that this study met its goal of discovering some of the key revitalization characteristics of two Independent Baptist churches. The principles of church revitalization are biblical. The extent to which any church implements the principles of the Bible in its revitalization process will be the extent to which God will bless their efforts. The results of this study find companion support in the works of other researchers who have studied the same thing. One of the unexpected findings in this study, which was mentioned previously, was the fact that a church’s health is not based on size. The churches under study in this research revealed that a church of 10 can be healthier and better positioned for recovery than a church of 110.

Upon reviewing this study and comparing its findings to the author's circumstance, he believes that three engagement criteria help forward the process of revitalization. First, the author’s church would be wise to engage a full-time minister. Both pastors in the research study were able to be full-time from day one. One church could support its pastor, and the other pastor

had raised funds to be full-time. Although this point was not highlighted in the research, it is nonetheless important. The ability to give oneself completely to prayer and the work of the ministry is critical at any time but especially in a revitalization work. Second, the author's current church would benefit from targeted consistent ministry outreaches that are appropriate for the setting of the church, in a rural county. Some of these ministries should be long-term engagements, such as the establishment of a regular program of evangelistic outreach, as well as ministries that target certain needs in the community. For example, starting a youth outreach ministry is an option. Also, a ministry to unwed mothers would be helpful because of the large number of unwed mothers in the community. Another ministry that would be effective in the author's community is a recovery ministry (like Reformers Unanimous). Other ministry opportunities could be short-term, such as high-impact outreach events. Hosting fall festivals, hosting monthly youth rallies, entering a float in the annual Christmas parade, hosting the local football team for dinner, or hosting an annual sportsman's dinner outreach are several ideas for this category.

Third, it would be recommended that the author enhance his leadership skills. Enhancement of leadership skills should be an ongoing process, always seeking to improve. The doctoral program in which the author has been engaged has been and continues to be a part of that process. Also, the author is currently engaged in a counseling certification program to enhance his ability as a pastor.

Implications for Broader Ministry

As a result of this doctoral program and research effort, it has been the author's privilege to develop two ministries that will target the revitalization of Independent Baptist churches. One is called Hometown Hope Ministries. This program is a comprehensive church revitalization outreach. Another ministry developed during this program is Ministry Medicine International, a telemedicine practice dedicated primarily to ministry and ministry-related personnel. A portion of the proceeds from this business will be used to support the activities of Hometown Hope. The focus of the researcher's future ministry will center on traveling (teaching, preaching, and assisting churches in revitalization), as well as writing on the subject of revitalization (among other topics).

The research effort engaged here has also stimulated the author to seek engagement in a more defined way, in the education of pastoral students. After investigation, there appears to be no educational system in the Independent Baptist Movement that specifically prepares future pastors for the unique work of revitalization. With so many Independent Baptist churches in need of revitalization, this type of training is crucial. Master and Doctoral level training would be the best place for this type of training, but this revitalization emphasis could also be made throughout a student's undergraduate studies. The researcher is now attempting to engage with Independent Baptist training centers with the hope of assisting them in developing such programs.

Recommendations for Further Study and Use

Further study, by the author, of individual revitalized churches would add greater weight, and also greater fine-tuning, to the findings of this research. Research of this type needs to be

replicated to ensure that the individual principles of revitalization are consistently and repetitively identified. Other researchers could also follow the pattern of this research and reproduce it for confirmation of findings. A researcher could also study each one of the individual revitalization criteria in greater detail. The specific roles that these components play in the revitalization process could be further delineated and clarified.

A research study such as this one is helpful to see the biblical principles of revitalization confirmed in the recovery of an actual church. It is also helpful to realize that although there are usually multiple problems to be encountered during a church revitalization, some of which are unique to Independent Baptist churches, it is not impossible to overcome these problems. The process requires biblical wisdom and an understanding of how to navigate those difficulties while consistently applying the principle of revitalization.

It would also be wise to engage pastors/pastoral students on a deeper level about other issues which are also a part of the revitalization process, but which were not considered (some not at all, and others as just a mention) in this study. For example, the person, work, and leading of the Holy Spirit, the management of church debt, Interpersonal conflicts, and decaying facilities. Social media presence and advertising in revitalization could be other areas of study, as could reclaiming a good reputation when a church has lost theirs in a community. Each of the factors that indicate a healthy revitalized church could be further studied to see the unique application of these principles as they play out in local congregations around the world. Other factors that could be considered are *The Role of Women in the Revitalization of Churches*; *Congregational Attitudes (Pastoral/Parishioner) That Hinder Church Revitalization*; *Navigating Doctrinal Distinctions in Independent Baptist Churches That Hinder Revitalization*; *Academic Deficiencies in the Current Method of Ministerial Training*, etc. The need for such work as this is

obvious. The demand is here and growing. What is required now is the vision and resources (by individual researchers, pastors, as well as academic institutions) to develop the necessary components.

Further research could also include targeted data on Independent Baptist churches themselves. Researchers and research facilities would have to be developed, but having high-quality data about the starting of Independent Baptist churches, the number of churches, the closure of churches, and the size of churches would be invaluable as well.

Closing Statements

This research study, specifically related to Independent Baptist churches, is unique in its singularity. The hope is that this research effort will not be the last of its kind. Although singularity, in itself, does not make it significant, the subject matter of the research is highly significant. Independent Baptist churches are not immune to the decline that other churches have experienced. The struggles are real. The help and support need to be real as well. As a result of the educational program that has been engaged, as well as the current research effort, there has developed a myriad of concrete ways to do long-term and substantive work in the field of revitalization offering practical help for pastors, churches, and educational centers at the point of need.

Appendices

Appendix A. Adapted Church Health Inventory

Adapted Church Health Inventory		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Fellowship Aspect						
1	We have several cliques in our church.	0	1	2	3	4
2	Becoming a part of existing groups in our church is hard.	0	1	2	3	4
3	The priority focus of the church should be meeting the needs of the members.	0	1	2	3	4
4	People in our church are willing to start new groups and classes.	0	1	2	3	4
5	Our church has been recently involved in conflict between members.	0	1	2	3	4
6	A number of the people in our church are angry with one another.	0	1	2	3	4
7	We have unresolved conflict in our church.	0	1	2	3	4
8	The people in our church enjoy being together.	0	1	2	3	4
9	I have fellowship or social times with church members outside of church activities at least once a quarter.	0	1	2	3	4
10	New members are quickly invited to different groups in the church	0	1	2	3	4
11	Our church is unified.	0	1	2	3	4
12	One of the reasons I come to church is because I enjoy the fellowship of other members.	0	1	2	3	4
13	I believe my voice is heard in this church.	0	1	2	3	4
14	A healthy relationship exists between the pastor (and other church staff) and the people.	0	1	2	3	4
15	Our church deals quickly with open, flagrant and unrepentant sin of church members.	0	1	2	3	4
16	I am a part of a group or class that attempts to reach other people.	0	1	2	3	4
17	I am excited to be a part of this church.	0	1	2	3	4
18	Coming to church on a regular basis is becoming increasingly difficult for me.	0	1	2	3	4
19	The community outside of our church sees us as a very unified church.	0	1	2	3	4
20	Our church has a good reputation in the community.	0	1	2	3	4
21	I feel like I belong in this church.	0	1	2	3	4
22	I think visitors to our church sometimes feel unwelcome.	0	1	2	3	4
23	Our church is more interested in ourselves than in reaching out to unchurched people.	0	1	2	3	4
24	One purpose of fellowship in our church is to encourage one another to live faithfully before God.	0	1	2	3	4

Adapted Church Health Inventory		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
25	I felt quickly loved and accepted when I began attending this church.	0	1	2	3	4
Evangelism Scoring						
1	People in our church share their faith regularly.	0	1	2	3	4
2	Our church supports missionaries generously.	0	1	2	3	4
3	Our church seeks ways to reach people in our area.	0	1	2	3	4
4	Visitors feel welcome in our church.	0	1	2	3	4
5	Our Sunday school classes or small groups seek to reach people outside of our groups.	0	1	2	3	4
6	Our church emphasizes church planting as a means of reaching people.	0	1	2	3	4
7	I have certain fears and apprehensions that keep me from sharing my faith.	0	1	2	3	4
8	Our church sends people regularly to do mission work around the world.	0	1	2	3	4
9	We have a known plan for regularly reaching out in our community.	0	1	2	3	4
10	A church should meet the needs of its own members before it reaches to others.	0	1	2	3	4
11	A church should not start a new church until it has adequate surplus in the budget.	0	1	2	3	4
12	Only people who have the gift of evangelism should be expected to share their faith.	0	1	2	3	4
13	I regularly attempt to establish relationships with people who do not have a church home.	0	1	2	3	4
14	Our church provides regular opportunities for evangelism training.	0	1	2	3	4
15	I have at least a few friendships/relationships with people who are not Christians.	0	1	2	3	4
16	Our church sees people accept Christ on a regular basis.	0	1	2	3	4
17	I believe you have to be called to be a lifetime missionary to do international missions.	0	1	2	3	4
18	I believe that one of the purposes of Sunday school classes or small groups is evangelism.	0	1	2	3	4
19	Our church has a portion of its budget allocated for mission work around the world.	0	1	2	3	4
20	When I see a new person in our church, I make every effort to introduce myself to him/her.	0	1	2	3	4
21	I share my faith regularly with lost persons.	0	1	2	3	4
22	My pastor models personal evangelism for our church.	0	1	2	3	4
23	I would be willing to do more personal evangelism if I had more training.	0	1	2	3	4
24	There are enough churches in our community.	0	1	2	3	4
25	Our church is growing more by transfer members from other churches than by reaching lost people.	0	1	2	3	4
Discipleship Scoring						

Adapted Church Health Inventory		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	I am involved in regular Bible study in my church.	0	1	2	3	4
2	I am growing in maturity as a Christian in my church.	0	1	2	3	4
3	Most attending our church are in regular Bible study.	0	1	2	3	4
4	New Christians are disciplined immediately after conversion in our church.	0	1	2	3	4
5	Children in our church have opportunities to grow in maturity as Christians.	0	1	2	3	4
6	I would rate the level of knowledge of the Bible as high in our church.	0	1	2	3	4
7	Our Sunday school/small groups are very strong in Bible study.	0	1	2	3	4
8	We tend to lose members within a few months after they have joined.	0	1	2	3	4
9	Our church seems to lose more people than we gain.	0	1	2	3	4
10	I would describe the commitment level of the majority of our members as low.	0	1	2	3	4
11	The people in our church understand the church's doctrine, or what we believe.	0	1	2	3	4
12	New members receive good training and information when they join our church.	0	1	2	3	4
13	Our church does a very good job at discipling members.	0	1	2	3	4
14	We have many people involved in one-on-one discipling or mentoring.	0	1	2	3	4
15	I have grown as a Christian since being at this church.	0	1	2	3	4
16	People in our church are given good training on how to develop a prayer life and quiet time.	0	1	2	3	4
17	People in our church are given many opportunities to learn how to share and defend their faith.	0	1	2	3	4
18	The lifestyles of the members at our church are significantly different than the world's lifestyle.	0	1	2	3	4
19	I know what I believe as a Christian, and why I believe it.	0	1	2	3	4
20	The more mature Christians in our church have a strong desire to help the less mature Christians in our church.	0	1	2	3	4
21	Someone personally disciplined me, teaching me how to follow Christ and grow as a Christian.	0	1	2	3	4
22	I feel adequately prepared to disciple a new believer.	0	1	2	3	4
23	Our church does a good job of training believers to give financially to the church.	0	1	2	3	4
24	I have been trained how to read and interpret the Bible correctly.	0	1	2	3	4
25	Discipleship classes in our church are usually boring or irrelevant.	0	1	2	3	4

Adapted Church Health Inventory		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Prayer Scoring						
1	Our church has an intercessory prayer ministry with many participants.	0	1	2	3	4
2	The leadership in my church regularly emphasizes the importance of prayer.	0	1	2	3	4
3	In today's busy world, Christians setting aside thirty to sixty minutes a day for prayer is nearly impossible.	0	1	2	3	4
4	Before we attempt any major effort in our church, we bathe it in prayer.	0	1	2	3	4
5	Our church prays for non-Christians by name.	0	1	2	3	4
6	Prayer is a central facet of our worship services.	0	1	2	3	4
7	We have special prayer emphases in our church.	0	1	2	3	4
8	Our church makes available to everyone a list of prayer needs.	0	1	2	3	4
9	Prayer is an integral part of our Sunday school classes or small groups.	0	1	2	3	4
10	We pray regularly for world missions in our church.	0	1	2	3	4
11	Our church regularly prays for the ministries of the church.	0	1	2	3	4
12	I believe that it is vital to have people praying during the worship services.	0	1	2	3	4
13	I pray regularly for my pastor / minister / clergy, their family(ies), and the staff of our church.	0	1	2	3	4
14	Prayer meetings in our church are boring.	0	1	2	3	4
15	Prayer meetings in our church tend to be gossip times.	0	1	2	3	4
16	When we pray in our church, nothing happens.	0	1	2	3	4
17	We have a prayer room or place in our church where many people pray each week.	0	1	2	3	4
18	I believe the Bible teaches that prayer should be a daily part of every Christian's life.	0	1	2	3	4
19	I pray regularly during the day.	0	1	2	3	4
20	Our church communicates answered prayers to the people of the church.	0	1	2	3	4
21	I believe that prayer works.	0	1	2	3	4
22	I feel adequately trained in prayer.	0	1	2	3	4
23	I pray regularly for missionaries.	0	1	2	3	4
24	I pray regularly for non-believers.	0	1	2	3	4
25	Sometimes our church is so busy "doing church" that we pray too little.	0	1	2	3	4
Ministry Scoring						
1	Our church has a good youth ministry.	0	1	2	3	4
2	Our church has a good music ministry.	0	1	2	3	4
3	Our church has a good preschool and children's ministry.	0	1	2	3	4

Adapted Church Health Inventory		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
4	Our church does a good job of ministering to different ages of adults.	0	1	2	3	4
5	When there is a need in our church, many people respond.	0	1	2	3	4
6	I believe the pastor / minister / clergy (and staff) should do most of the ministry.	0	1	2	3	4
7	I am regularly involved in doing ministry in our church.	0	1	2	3	4
8	Most members in our church know their spiritual gifts.	0	1	2	3	4
9	Most members in our church use their spiritual gifts in ministry.	0	1	2	3	4
10	Whenever a job needs to get done, many people in our church volunteer.	0	1	2	3	4
11	It is difficult for me to get involved in ministry in my church.	0	1	2	3	4
12	It is difficult for new members to get involved in ministry in our church.	0	1	2	3	4
13	Most of the ministry in our church is done by a small number of people.	0	1	2	3	4
14	Our church members have freedom to be creative in ministry.	0	1	2	3	4
15	I receive fulfillment by doing ministry in our church.	0	1	2	3	4
16	The leadership of our church does a good job of equipping people to do ministry.	0	1	2	3	4
17	Our church is strong in benevolence ministry.	0	1	2	3	4
18	We reach many people in our church by ministering to them.	0	1	2	3	4
19	Our church is willing to minister to people regardless of ethnic background.	0	1	2	3	4
20	People in our church have someone to turn to when they need counseling.	0	1	2	3	4
21	I am willing to serve in the church.	0	1	2	3	4
22	Our pastor regularly challenges us to get involved in the ministry of the church.	0	1	2	3	4
23	Our church has a clearly defined strategy for ministering to people in times of sickness or death.	0	1	2	3	4
24	Sometimes I get tired of doing ministry because my responsibilities at church are probably too many.	0	1	2	3	4
25	I can count on my church to minister to me if I am in need.	0	1	2	3	4
Worship Scoring				2	3	4
1	When I come to my church, I truly sense that I worship God.	0	1	2	3	4
2	I learn a lot about the Bible from the pastor's sermons.	0	1	2	3	4
3	The music in our worship services leads me to worship.	0	1	2	3	4
4	The pastor's sermons are mostly topical.	0	1	2	3	4

Adapted Church Health Inventory		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
5	The pastor's sermons are mostly expository (verse by verse / book by book).	0	1	2	3	4
6	The pastor's sermons are mostly textual (preaching through a passage of the Bible, but not through entire books).	0	1	2	3	4
7	Disagreement exists among the members at our church about the type of music and worship style.	0	1	2	3	4
8	The pastor's sermons are relevant to my needs and real life situations.	0	1	2	3	4
9	We have a good way of greeting guests in our worship services.	0	1	2	3	4
10	I like the blend of music and worship styles in our worship services.	0	1	2	3	4
11	The music and worship style in our services would be considered traditional.	0	1	2	3	4
12	The worship service time and length are just right.	0	1	2	3	4
13	The length of the sermons is just right.	0	1	2	3	4
14	Our sanctuary/worship center is a good facility in which to worship.	0	1	2	3	4
15	I have trouble finding a parking place when I come to church.	0	1	2	3	4
16	I like the order in which we go through worship.	0	1	2	3	4
17	Our worship services are prayerful experiences.	0	1	2	3	4
18	We have good participation in singing in our worship services.	0	1	2	3	4
19	A non-Christian would be comfortable in our worship services.	0	1	2	3	4
20	I like all the elements of our worship services.	0	1	2	3	4
21	There are too many distractions in our worship services.	0	1	2	3	4
22	I have been to other churches, and I think our worship services are among the best.	0	1	2	3	4
23	The Holy Spirit uses our worship services to lead people to make decisions for God.	0	1	2	3	4
24	There is the right emphasis on money and stewardship in our worship services.	0	1	2	3	4
25	We have plenty of room for growth in our worship facility/auditorium.	0	1	2	3	4
26	We regularly have guests (visitors) in our worship services.	0	1	2	3	4
27	Even as a church grows, it is best to keep everyone together in one morning worship service.	0	1	2	3	4
28	My faith in God is strengthened by our worship services.	0	1	2	3	4
29	I would excitedly invite an unchurched friend to a worship service at our church.	0	1	2	3	4
Doctrine Scoring						

Adapted Church Health Inventory		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	People of non-Christian faiths can worship God in the same way Christians do.	0	1	2	3	4
2	The Bible is the word of God, perfect as it was originally written.	0	1	2	3	4
3	God intervenes regularly in the lives of Christians.	0	1	2	3	4
4	The only way to heaven is through a personal relationship with Christ.	0	1	2	3	4
5	Because we all are sinners, we can have fellowship with God only through the shed blood of Jesus Christ.	0	1	2	3	4
6	God is trinity: the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit.	0	1	2	3	4
7	A good person of another faith other than Christianity may go to heaven.	0	1	2	3	4
8	Hell is a literal place.	0	1	2	3	4
9	God is in total control of our world.	0	1	2	3	4
10	Jesus is the Son of God.	0	1	2	3	4
Unique Challenge Scoring						
1	We exclusively use and require the use of the KJV in all ministry of our church.	0	1	2	3	4
2	Our church requires lady church workers (S.S. Teachers, Choir Members, etc.) to wear dresses / skirts at all church and church related events.	0	1	2	3	4
3	Our church is led by one pastor. If not, list leadership style in comments.	0	1	2	3	4
4	Our church engages church discipline when necessary (even putting people out of the church if required).	0	1	2	3	4
5	The pastor preaches often on Biblical standards and separation.	0	1	2	3	4
6	Our church body has regular business meetings to make decisions.	0	1	2	3	4

Appendix B. Church Scan Inventory

Church Name:

Denomination:

Year Church Founded:

How Long Have You Attended This Church?

Sunday AM Average Attendance Number (When you arrived / presently):

Which of the following best describes your church's location?

Rural

Urban

Suburban

Your Name:

Your Position:

Email:

Phone:

	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Corporate Pulse				
Our congregation often has fun together, and joy is in the "atmosphere" when gathered.	1	2	3	4
Our lay leaders are excited and enthusiastic about the ministry of the church.	1	2	3	4
Our church leaders (pastoral, lay and staff) enjoy unity and love among themselves.	1	2	3	4
Our church has many former leaders who are willing and eager to serve in the future.	1	2	3	4
Pastors at our church feel respected and enjoy long, positive tenures.	1	2	3	4

	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Trust in Leadership				
Lay leaders and the congregation are open to pastoral initiatives.	1	2	3	4
The pastoral staff and congregation are open to board initiatives.	1	2	3	4
Our church is free from reactive, resistant behavior toward leadership.	1	2	3	4
Our church business meetings are pleasant, positive, and non-conflicted.	1	2	3	4
Our church's leaders are free from a need to control the congregation.	1	2	3	4

	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Mission / Vision Fulfillment				
Our church regularly sees conversions from its services and individual evangelism.	1	2	3	4
God calls a good number of young people from our church into full-time ministry.	1	2	3	4
Our pastor and his family are free from unhealthy stress related to his role in the church.	1	2	3	4
Our church enjoys a consistent sense of ministry effectiveness and momentum.	1	2	3	4
Our church is accomplishing what Christ put it in our community to do.	1	2	3	4

	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Communication				
Our pastor, staff and lay leaders feel safe discussing difficult issues with each other.	1	2	3	4
When leaders know real problems exist they talk about them. No "elephants are in the room."	1	2	3	4

	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Communication				
Our leaders resolve their interpersonal conflicts in a godly and timely manner.	1	2	3	4
Our church's leaders courageously and consistently address church discipline issues.	1	2	3	4
We are currently free from unhealthy/destructive interpersonal tension within the church.	1	2	3	4

	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Historical Crises				
Our church was birthed without controversy or from a split.	1	2	3	4
Our church history is free of injuries/wounds committed against previous pastors, boards or staff.	1	2	3	4
Our church's history is free of stories of bad behavior by previous pastors, boards or staff.	1	2	3	4
Our church is free from any repetitive history (cycle) of corporate pain.	1	2	3	4
Our church is currently free of trauma or corporate pain[1].	1	2	3	4
[1] Corporate pain is defined as a crisis or unresolved issue that negatively impacts the leadership and/or a congregation as a whole.				

Appendix C. Midwestern Church Scan (LP1), Past–Present

Church Scan Inventory, Midwestern Church (LP1), Past–1998

CSI - Midwestern Past–1998 LP1				
	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Corporate Pulse				
Our congregation often has fun together, and joy is in the "atmosphere" when gathered.			√	
Our lay leaders are excited and enthusiastic about the ministry of the church.				√
Our church leaders (pastoral, lay and staff) enjoy unity and love among themselves.			√	
Our church has many former leaders who are willing and eager to serve in the future.			√	
Pastors at our church feel respected and enjoy long, positive tenures.			√	

CSI - Midwestern Past–1998 LP1				
	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Trust In Leadership				
Lay leaders and the congregation are open to pastoral initiatives.			√	
The pastoral staff and congregation are open to board initiatives.		√		
Our church is free from reactive, resistant behavior toward leadership.		√		
Our church business meetings are pleasant, positive, and non-conflicted.			√	
Our church's leaders are free from a need to control the congregation.			√	

CSI - Midwestern Past - 1998 LP1				
	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Mission / Vision Fulfillment				
Our church regularly sees conversions from its services and individual evangelism.				√
God calls a good number of young people from our church into full-time ministry.				√
Our pastor and his family are free from unhealthy stress related to his role in the church.				√
Our church enjoys a consistent sense of ministry effectiveness and momentum.				√
Our church is accomplishing what Christ put it in our community to do.				√

CSI - Midwestern Past - 1998 LP1				
	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Communication				
Our pastor, staff and lay leaders feel safe discussing difficult issues with each other.			√	
When leaders know real problems exist they talk about them. No "elephants are in the room."			√	
Our leaders resolve their interpersonal conflicts in a godly and timely manner.			√	
Our church's leaders courageously and consistently address church discipline issues.			√	
We are currently free from unhealthy/destructive interpersonal tension within the church.				√

CSI - Midwestern Past - 1998 LPI				
	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Historical Crises				
Our church was birthed without controversy or from a split.			√	
Our church history is free of injuries/wounds committed against previous pastors, boards or staff.				√
Our church's history is free of stories of bad behavior by previous pastors, boards or staff.				√
Our church is free from any repetitive history (cycle) of corporate pain.				√
Our church is currently free of trauma or corporate pain[1].	√			

[1] Corporate pain is defined as a crisis or unresolved issue that negatively impacts the leadership and/or a congregation as a whole.

Midwestern Church Scan Inventory Results, Past–1998

Welcome to your personalized ChurchScan results. Please contact us with questions or inquiries about next steps for your church. Submitted by: hometownhopeministries@gmail.com.

Corporate Pulse: Your church's corporate pulse refers to those qualities normally found in healthy churches where Christ is present, honored, listened to, and followed. Passages like Acts 2:42-47 and 4:32-35 reveal the wonderful atmosphere God intended for your church (as a whole) to experience.

- *Low Pulse – 8:* Churches that score low in corporate pulse face real danger. They often go through the motions of doing church, without the joy, momentum, and unity we see described in the book of Acts. They exhibit all the activities of the New Testament

church, but lack its sense of blessing. The church sees few conversions and lacks a sense of awe at what God is doing in their midst. They likely reside on the downhill side of their life expectancy and may have experienced great pain/trauma. Something painful has usually happened in the church's history to compromise the spirit which Christ intended the church to enjoy.

- *Action Point:* A low score should be cross-referenced with a church's score for Historical Crises. Those events often give insight into why the church continues to struggle to enjoy unity and fruitfulness. As you reflect on the pulse of your church, ask the Lord to help you discern what drives your church's heartbeat and fuels your church's ministries. Christ is our life (Colossians 3:4). We need His life and resurrection presence to fuel our ministries. Begin to seek Him about what might have negatively impacted the pulse of your church's corporate heart.

Trust in Leadership: Whether your church body trusts its leadership (or not) speaks volumes about the health of your church. Trust is the currency of leadership, the "coin" of God's realm, and an absolute necessity for churches to function in a healthy way. Sometimes though, a congregation will not trust current leaders, or boards won't trust pastors because of wounds received from other leaders in the past. The crux of this is that, if people do not trust their leaders, they will not follow them, so every leadership initiative gets resisted or openly opposed.

- *Medium Trust - 12:* Signs of mistrust exist for leaders in your church, but the culture of your church may not yet have been redefined by it. Leaders enjoy some degree of trust except, perhaps, in certain areas. There may be "hot button topics," minefields that leaders have learned to avoid, which are explained when one understands the history of

the church. Unaddressed, these trust issues tend to increase until there is a major rift or blow-up.

- *Action Point:* The issue here is severity of the event(s) where trust may have been violated in your history. Review the history of your church to identify any such breaches of trust by current or former leaders. Even things suspected but unproven need to be addressed for trust to be restored. If leaders act to heal these wounds, trust will get “credited” to their account. Leaders will also have to make deposits into that account themselves with their behavior and in their communication with the congregation. If there are concerns about your ability to facilitate healing related to trust for leaders in your church, a consultant could help, so don’t be afraid to ask for help.

Mission/Vision Fulfillment: How well are you fulfilling your church’s mission/vision—the reason why Christ put you where you are? This is a great indicator of either God’s blessing on your ministry or a red flag revealing His unhappiness with you. Do you as leaders know, pray about, and pursue with commitment the mission/vision God has laid upon your hearts or on your founders’ hearts? Failure to do so can be a clear symptom of the fabric of your church starting to unravel. Churches that are sick tend to use their energy and resources to get better—i.e. focus on themselves and not on reaching out. Underlying issues can subvert your best, most creative efforts at fulfilling all that God has in mind for your congregation.

- *Low Fulfillment - 6:* Jesus cares about mission/vision fulfillment. He told the church at Sardis, “I have not found your deeds complete in the sight of my God” (Revelation 3:2). If you score low in this area, the reasons can be three-fold: (1) You don’t have a clearly defined mission/vision; (2) Your leaders are too worn out dealing with pain and problems

to expend the necessary energy to pursue the mission/vision right now; or (3) The congregation resists leadership initiatives so you can seem to get untracked. You may be suffering from any or all of these issues, and thus, “your deeds are incomplete.” A lack of mission/vision fulfillment can cause high degrees of stress and discouragement if you as leaders keep trying to do the right things, yet cannot seem to get past the energy drain or congregational resistance.

- *Action Point:* Many churches think that, if they have failed with one mission/vision, the answer is to create or redefine another one! Before embarking on a venture into identifying and implementing a new vision for your church, you must address the issues you have. Ask God to reveal to you the real nature and reasons for the challenges you face (2 Samuel 21:1-3). The good news is that, if you really want to know, God can and will tell you. You must as leaders act to address these things first before God will help you achieve your mission/vision.

Communication: Healthy communication is crucial to a healthy church, like the life-blood circulating in a body or nerve signals which permit all parts to operate as they should without paralysis or insensitivity. Moreover, in a healthy church, the head (leadership) listens to the body. On the other side, without an atmosphere characterized by open, truthful communication, conflicts seldom get resolved or reconciled and bad feelings build and go underground, fueling the engines of gossip and criticism. Unhealthy churches always have unhealthy and/or painful patterns of communication. These expressions and behaviors move back and forth from overt to covert, distorting how your church functions. In its worst expressions, “elephants” fill whatever room you are in and no one will talk about the things that desperately need to be addressed.

- *Low Communication - 9:* People do not feel free to discuss difficult topics in your church because they don't feel safe doing so. Unresolved conflicts prevent grace-filled communication! A cycle of increasing isolation and alienation ensues, seriously damaging and limiting any loving culture your church may possess. Because unresolved issues linger and build, reactive behavior will exhibit itself in informal and even formal church meetings. People may tolerate this only because they have never known the church to be any different.
- *Action Point:* Handle with care, as churches with low scores are often a minefield for leaders! Before you can restore open communication and resolve conflicts in a healthy way, you must return to the source of the bad communication, the event(s) which started this way of behaving. Then you must take responsibility and confess this bad behavior to Christ and one another. Serious reflection is needed to evaluate exactly how the church arrives at this place. If leadership feels that might not be able to control the unhealthy or critical communication to find out these things, an outside, objective, facilitator can help lead your church through the healing process it needs.

Historical Crises: Historical crises, and especially a pattern or cycle of unresolved trauma, represent the single most significant indicator of a need for healing in your church. These wounds seldom get addressed in churches because leaders are not trained to do it and seldom realize how churches carry such damage going forward. Your church may be in crisis now, but you may also know of crises it has faced in the past. An unresolved crisis acts like a tear in the fabric of your church that, unmended, can further unravel with each new problem. If your church also scores low in the “Trust in Leadership” category, crises can result in splits, firings, petitions, or other highly unhealthy corporate behaviors.

- *Much Evidence of Historical Crises - 9:* There is a high probability that your church has a painful past. The congregation may have experienced split(s), abuse of or by a church leader, sinful reactivity (i.e. lashing out), shameful events (i.e. racial prejudice or moral failure by a leader). All these, unrectified, have a long-term impact on your church body and its willingness to follow leadership. Your answers indicate that the wounds from these types of events in your church's history have yet to be healed. They prevent you from gaining any kind of traction in fulfilling your mission.
- *Action Point:* Seek the Lord for courage to face and repair the damage your church may have experienced. Ask Him to give you the courage to walk through a process of corporate healing. Such a process holds great hope for restoring your church to proper functioning.

Total ChurchScan Score - 44

INTERVENTION REQUIRED: Your church is likely experiencing or has experienced in the past a high degree of congregational pain, and you need to do something about it *immediately* to get your church healthy again.

General Assessment: Churches that score in the 25–50 range are in need of corporate healing. Such churches manifest a variety of symptoms which often seem bewildering to the people who lead them. Symptoms can include irrational levels of resistance to change, anxiety about the future, distrust between lay and pastoral leaders and between leaders and congregation, all of which makes leading difficult if not impossible. Schisms can form around lightning rod issues - worship, associate staff, the pastor. Offenses become magnified. Bad behavior often precedes

splits or exoduses. Those who visit the church don't stay long. Church members "acclimatize" to the environment and see all this as "normal." Unaddressed, these painful symptoms usually increase in intensity and frequency.

Leaders and members often misdiagnose the true nature of their corporate problems and blame the pastor, staff member(s), or particular lay leaders. Leaders often attribute the problems to the inadequate policies or ineffective programs. Shepherds who minister in these contexts often feel like failures, and they blame themselves or others for the church's stalemate. Their personal health often suffers, sometimes severely. They carry heavy burdens and, despite their best efforts to make progress, they keep slipping back. The pressure of leadership also bears down on the pastor's spouse and children.

What We Suggest: We highly recommend you purchase copies of *Healing the Heart of Your Church* for your leaders to read. If the message of Dr. Quick's book resonates with your leaders, you may take one of the following steps.

1. If you know your church needs healing and you are a transitional/interim pastor with facilitating skills, or have led the Healing the Heart of Your Church process in the past, consider purchasing *The Healing the Heart of your Church Facilitators Guide* and *Participant Workbooks*. You can then begin to lead the church through the healing process in-house.
2. If you recognize your church needs healing but feel that you need an outside, objective, trained facilitator, contact us about helping to heal your church.

Church Scan Inventory, Midwestern Church (LP1), Present–2022

CSI - Midwestern Church Present–2022 LP1				
	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Corporate Pulse				
Our congregation often has fun together, and joy is in the "atmosphere" when gathered.	√			
Our lay leaders are excited and enthusiastic about the ministry of the church.	√			
Our church leaders (pastoral, lay and staff) enjoy unity and love among themselves.	√			
Our church has many former leaders who are willing and eager to serve in the future.	√			
Pastors at our church feel respected and enjoy long, positive tenures.	√			

CSI - Midwestern Church Present–2022 LP1				
	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Trust In Leadership				
Lay leaders and the congregation are open to pastoral initiatives.	√			
The pastoral staff and congregation are open to board initiatives.		√		
Our church is free from reactive, resistant behavior toward leadership.	√			
Our church business meetings are pleasant, positive, and non-conflicted.	√			
Our church's leaders are free from a need to control the congregation.	√			

CSI - Midwestern Church Present–2022 LP1				
	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Mission / Vision Fulfillment				
Our church regularly sees conversions from its services and individual evangelism.		√		
God calls a good number of young people from our church into full-time ministry.		√		
Our pastor and his family are free from unhealthy stress related to his role in the church.			√	
Our church enjoys a consistent sense of ministry effectiveness and momentum.	√			
Our church is accomplishing what Christ put it in our community to do.		√		

CSI - Midwestern Church Present–2022 LP1				
	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Communication				
Our pastor, staff and lay leaders feel safe discussing difficult issues with each other.	√			
When leaders know real problems exist they talk about them. No "elephants are in the room."	√			
Our leaders resolve their interpersonal conflicts in a godly and timely manner.	√			
Our church's leaders courageously and consistently address church discipline issues.			√	
We are currently free from unhealthy/destructive interpersonal tension within the church.	√			

CSI - Midwestern Church Present–2022 LPI				
	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Historical Crises				
Our church was birthed without controversy or from a split.			√	
Our church history is free of injuries/wounds committed against previous pastors, boards or staff.		√		
Our church’s history is free of stories of bad behavior by previous pastors, boards or staff.		√		
Our church is free from any repetitive history (cycle) of corporate pain.		√		
Our church is currently free of trauma or corporate pain[1].		√		

[1] Corporate pain is defined as a crisis or unresolved issue that negatively impacts the leadership and/or a congregation as a whole.

Midwestern Church Scan Inventory Results, 2022–Present

Welcome to your personalized ChurchScan results. Please contact us with questions or inquiries about next steps for your church. Submitted by: hometownhopeministries@gmail.com

Corporate Pulse: Your church’s corporate pulse refers to those qualities normally found in healthy churches where Christ is present, honored, listened to, and followed. Passages like Acts 2:42-47 and 4:32-35 reveal the wonderful atmosphere God intended for your church (as a whole) to experience.

- *Strong Pulse - 18:* Churches scoring in the high range of corporate pulse tend to be unified, healthy congregations. Joy is in the atmosphere and for the most part, everyone rallies around what God is doing in your church.

- *Action Point:* Keep up the good work by purposefully investing in the emotional and spiritual health of your leadership team.

Trust in Leadership: Whether your church body trusts its leadership (or not) speaks volumes about the health of your church. Trust is the currency of leadership, the “coin” of God’s realm, and an absolute necessity for churches to function in a healthy way. Sometimes though, a congregation will not trust current leaders, or boards won’t trust pastors because of wounds received from other leaders in the past. The crux of this is that, if people do not trust their leaders, they will not follow them, so every leadership initiative gets resisted or openly opposed.

- *High Trust - 19:* The Scripture says, “Behold, how good and how pleasant it is for brothers (and sisters) to dwell together in unity!” Where trust for leaders is high, leaders enjoy positive, happy, lengthy tenures. Such leadership also produces growing, healthy congregations. Mutual trust and accountability between pastoral staff and lay leaders radiates out from there to the congregation. Leaders are followed and their initiatives received without resistance.
- *Action Point:* The temptation faced by leaders with trust is to take inappropriate advantage of it, or to seek to be served rather than serve. Learn to protect and build up your bank account of trust by understanding how leaders lose it and how hard it is to rebuild once lost.

Mission/Vision Fulfillment: How well are you fulfilling your church’s mission/vision—the reason why Christ put you where you are? This is a great indicator of either God’s blessing on your ministry or a red flag revealing His unhappiness with you. Do you as leaders know, pray

about, and pursue with commitment the mission/vision God has laid upon your hearts or on your founder's hearts? Failure to do so can be a clear symptom of the fabric of your church starting to unravel. Churches that are sick tend to use their energy and resources to get better—i.e. focus on themselves and not on reaching out. Underlying issues can subvert your best, most creative efforts at fulfilling all that God has in mind for your congregation.

- *High Fulfillment - 17:* Praise God! Your church continues to do a great job defining and fulfilling its mission and vision. Keep it up! A word of warning though: True vision fulfillment starts with a clear sense of what God wants us to do and then gets implemented by identifying the heaven-sent opportunities to fulfill the vision (Ephesians 2:10). Beware of Nebuchadnezzar's pride (Daniel 4:30), taking credit for your success and thereby incurring the displeasure of the true Head of your church (Colossians 2:19).
- *Action Point:* Keep taking risks and stretching your faith. Beware of growing comfortable. Take time to learn how to better hear from God as a leadership team. Keep feeding the motivation to reach those around you.

Communication: Healthy communication is crucial to a healthy church, like the life-blood circulating in a body or nerve signals which permit all parts to operate as they should without paralysis or insensitivity. Moreover, in a healthy church, the head (leadership) listens to the body. On the other side, without an atmosphere characterized by open, truthful communication, conflicts seldom get resolved or reconciled and bad feelings build and go underground, fueling the engines of gossip and criticism. Unhealthy churches always have unhealthy and/or painful patterns of communication. These expressions and behaviors move back and forth from overt to

covert, distorting how your church functions. In its worst expressions, “elephants” fill whatever room you are in and no one will talk about the things that desperately need to be addressed.

- *High Communication - 18:* Your church operates with that rare quality of being safe and secure enough to “speak the truth in love.” Leaders feel safe enough to discuss difficult issues with one another and congregational trust allows them to discuss such issues publicly. Your church should exercise church discipline if need be to keep the body healthy and free of infection. To have such a church is a great blessing. Guard carefully the atmosphere of trust that you have and do not take it for granted.
- *Action Point:* If your church is growing, be sure to restructure when communication lines get stretched to insure good avenues of communication stay open. Continue to build on your church's openness to communicate and confront problems.

Historical Crises: Historical crises, and especially a pattern or cycle of unresolved trauma, represent the single most significant indicator of a need for healing in your church. These wounds seldom get addressed in churches because leaders are not trained to do it and seldom realize how churches carry such damage going forward. Your church may be in crisis now, but you may also know of crises it has faced in the past. An unresolved crisis acts like a tear in the fabric of your church that, unmended, can further unravel with each new problem. If your church also scores low in the “Trust in Leadership” category, crises can result in splits, firings, petitions, or other highly unhealthy corporate behaviors.

- *Some Evidence of Historical Crises - 14:* Your church shows some evidence of having been wounded by a previous event(s). Your church may have experienced one of the

following: a painful split, abuse of or by a church leader, sinful reactivity (i.e. lashing out), shameful events (i.e. racial prejudice), or it may have suffered a moral failure by a leader. If such a wound has yet to be healed, its effects will not go away unless leaders intentionally seek to manage things right with Christ and the congregation. Unless treated, the effects of your corporate pain will linger and begin to hinder ministry effectiveness, regardless of who leads the church.

- *Action Point:* If your church is wounded, seek the Lord in regard to what is necessary to bring corporate healing to your congregation. Ask Him to give you the courage it will take to walk through such a process honestly and effectively. Avail yourselves of the consulting services Blessing Point Ministries offers to help you in this regard.

Total ChurchScan Score - 86

INVESTMENT REQUIRED

General Assessment: Churches scoring in the 76–100 enjoy spiritual and numerical health. Your church provides a wonderful illustration of the grace of God to your community! There may be individual categories of this assessment that need attention - you are not perfect - but overall you are doing things the right way. This is not time to grow complacent. Invest in the well-being of your leadership and congregation and prepare for the day and prepare for the day when you may need to deal with corporate pain.

Challenges will come to your church as they do to all churches. But with those challenges come opportunities as was the case with the church of Philadelphia in Revelation 3:7-13. In fact, churches that overcome obstacles are usually gifted with greater opportunities for the kingdom.

Be alert to the church health risks as communicated by the questions of this survey, and take the time to equip your leaders to protect your church from such dangers.

What We Suggest: When it comes to your church's health, you need to stay ahead of the curve.

Consider protecting the health of your church by sponsoring a Radiance Conference. The Radiance Conference helps equip your church's leaders to keep the body healthy.

Appendix D. Southern Church Scan (LP2), Past–Present

Church Scan Inventory, Southern Church (LP2), Past–2012

	Item	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Corporate Pulse					
	Our Congregation often has fun together, and joy is in the “atmosphere” when gathered			√	
	Our lay leaders are excited and enthusiastic about the ministry of the church		√		
	Our church leaders (pastoral, lay, and staff) enjoy unity and love among ourselves.		√		
	Our church has many former leaders who are willing and eager to serve in the future				√ - None there
	Pastors at our church feel respected and enjoy long, positive tenures	√			
Trust in Leadership					
	Lay Leaders and the congregation are open to pastoral Initiatives		√		
	The pastoral staff and congregation are open to board initiatives.		√		
	Our church is free from reactive, resistant behavior toward leadership		√		
	Our church business meetings are pleasant and non-conflicted.		√		
	Our Church’s leaders are free from a need to control the congregation.		√		
Mission / Vision / Fulfillment					
	Our church regularly sees conversions from its services and individual evangelism			√	
	God calls a good number of young people from our church into full-time ministry				√
	Our pastor and his family are free from unhealthy stress, related to his role in the church	√			

	Item	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Mission / Vision / Fulfillment					
	Our church enjoys a consistent sense of ministry effectiveness and momentum.			√	
	Our church is accomplishing what Christ put it in our community to do.			√	
Communication					
	Our pastor, staff, and lay leaders feel safe discussing difficult issues with each other			√	
	When leaders know real problems exist, they talk about them. No “elephants” are in the room		√		
	Our leaders resolve their interpersonal conflicts in a godly and timely manner.		√		
	Our church's leaders courageously and consistently address church discipline issues			√	
	We are currently free from unhealthy / destructive interpersonal tension within the church		√		
Historical Crises					
	Our church was birthed without controversy or from a split			√ - KJV Issue	
	Our church history is free of injuries / wounds committed against previous pastors, boards, or staff		√		
	Our church's history is free of stories of bad behavior by previous pastors, boards, or staff	√			
	Our church is free from any repetitive history (cycle) of corporate pain.	√			
	Our church is currently free of trauma or corporate pain [1]	√			

Southern Church (LP2) Scan Inventory Results, Past–2012

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Corporate Pulse: Your church’s corporate pulse refers to those qualities normally found in healthy churches where Christ is present, honored, listened to, and followed. Passages like Acts 2:42-47 and 4:32-35 reveal the wonderful atmosphere God intended for your church (as a whole) to experience.

- *Medium Pulse - 12:* Churches scoring in the medium range of Corporate Pulse have often reached a plateau or are starting to decline. Your church leaders need to give honest answers to questions like, “Have we lost our outward focus? Have we settled for the status quo? Is God happy with this and what does He want us to do about it?” Stability can be strength if it gets used to initiate new advances for the kingdom. However, stability can also lead to stagnation if the goal becomes comfort.
- *Action Point:* Danger signs exist and leaders must honestly discern if the pulse is getting stronger or weaker. Do there seem to be barriers you cannot get beyond? If so, underlying, systemic, issues may need to be addressed before healthy congregational life reemerges.

Trust in Leadership: Whether your church body trusts its leadership (or not) speaks volumes about the health of your church. Trust is the currency of leadership, the “coin” of God’s realm, and an absolute necessity for churches to function in a healthy way. Sometimes though, a congregation will not trust current leaders, or boards won’t trust pastors because of wounds

received from other leaders in the past. The crux of this is that, if people do not trust their leaders, they will not follow them, so every leadership initiative gets resisted or openly opposed.

- *Medium Test - 15:* Signs of mistrust exist for leaders in your church, but the culture of your church may not yet have been redefined by it. Leaders enjoy some degree of trust except, perhaps, in certain areas. There may be “hot-button topics,” minefields that leaders have learned to avoid, which are explained when one understands the history of the church. Unaddressed, these trust issues tend to increase until there is a major rift or blow-up.
- *Action Point:* The issue here is severity of the event(s) where trust may have been violated in your history. Review the history of your church to identify any such breaches of trust by current or former leaders. Even things suspected but unproven need to be addressed for trust to be restored. If leaders act to heal these wounds, trust will get “credited” to their account. Leaders will also have to make deposits into that account themselves with their behavior and in their communication with the congregation. If there are concerns about your ability to facilitate healing related to trust for leaders in your church, a consultant could help, so don’t be afraid to ask for help.

Mission/Vision Fulfillment: How well are you fulfilling your church’s mission/vision—the reason why Christ put you where you are? This is a great indicator of either God’s blessing on your ministry or a red flag revealing His unhappiness with you. Do you as leaders know, pray about, and pursue with commitment the mission/vision God has laid upon your hearts or on your founder's hearts? Failure to do so can be a clear symptom of the fabric of your church starting to unravel. Churches that are sick tend to use their energy and resources to get better—i.e. focus on

themselves and not on reaching out. Underlying issues can subvert your best, most creative efforts at fulfilling all that God has in mind for your congregation.

- *Medium Fulfillment - 12:* Jesus cares about mission/vision fulfillment and completing your works. He told the church at Sardis, “I have not found your deeds complete in the sight of my God” (Rev. 3:2). Your assessment results indicate that mission fulfillment is not as strong as it could be in your church. Though you have some strength in this area, you must discern what is slowing you down or holding you back, face these things honestly, and then you can move the church forward.
- *Action Point:* Your church’s leadership needs to ask itself some hard questions like: 1) Do we know why God put us in our community and can we articulate that clearly? 2) Does the congregation resist, overtly or covertly, following the mission/vision laid out by the leadership? This may be due to trust issues that you must address. 3) Do leaders have the energy and commitment they need to fulfill the mission/vision? The reasons for a lack in these areas must be clearly understood. These questions help you identify the source of the problem. New vitality is available to churches that take the time to hear from the Head of their church about what He wants them to do and what, if anything, needs to be corrected before God will bless your efforts to fulfill the purpose for your church.

Communication: Healthy communication is crucial to a healthy church, like the life-blood circulating in a body or nerve signals which permit all parts to operate as they should without paralysis or insensitivity. Moreover, in a healthy church, the head (leadership) listens to the body. On the other side, without an atmosphere characterized by open, truthful communication, conflicts seldom get resolved or reconciled and bad feelings build and go underground, fueling

the engines of gossip and criticism. Unhealthy churches always have unhealthy and/or painful patterns of communication. These expressions and behaviors move back and forth from overt to covert, distorting how your church functions. In its worst expressions, “elephants” fill whatever room you are in and no one will talk about the things that desperately need to be addressed.

- *Medium Communication - 13*: People do not always feel free or safe to discuss difficult topics in your church. Leaders must discern if this means people need training in conflict resolution or, if people’s unwillingness to communicate comes from old congregational wounds that have not yet been healed. In the latter case, simply teaching on conflict resolution will fail to fix your church’s communication problem, nor will restructuring or adding bylaws. Because communication is not as healthy as it could be, it becomes harder as leaders to do difficult things you may need to do, like church discipline. You may face episodes of unhelpful criticism and gossip. You may also witness occasions of reactive behavior in your church, where pent-up feelings come out more strongly than a situation warrants.
- *Action Point*: Proceed with caution, but find the courage to proceed! You may need to explore the episodes of poor communication in your church to see if there is a pattern to them and when they started. They may be rooted in old conflicts or times when the congregation felt they had no voice.

Historical Crises: Historical crises, and especially a pattern or cycle of unresolved trauma, represents the single most significant indicator of a need for healing in your church. These wounds seldom get addressed in churches because leaders are not trained to do it and seldom realize how churches carry such damage going forward. Your church may be in crisis now, but

you may also know of crises it has faced in the past. An unresolved crisis acts like a tear in the fabric of your church that, unmended, can further unravel with each new problem. If your church also scores low in the “Trust in Leadership” category, crises can result in splits, firings, petitions, or other highly unhealthy corporate behaviors.

- *Little Evidence of Historical Crises - 17:* This is a great blessing to be celebrated. Rare is the church in existence more than ten years which has not faced such crises. Your church appears free of major pain, and it’s something for which you should be tremendously thankful! But a clear history does not mean a clear future. Make sure you as leaders are staying prepared to face such events with wisdom and sensitivity.
- *Action Point:* Ask God to give you the grace to deal with conflict or crises (when they do come) in a way He can bless. Many churches languish for having failed to do so.

Total ChurchScan Score - 69

INTENTIONAL EFFORT REQUIRED: You need to address the causes of your problems and work toward strengthening your church – *before things get worse.*

General Assessment: Churches scoring in the 51–75 range exhibit a mix of healthy and unhealthy traits, where the key for leaders is to assess honestly the frequency and direction of them, i.e. are they getting worse? Monitoring is important because the frequency of pain and ministry frustration can signal your need for congregational healing. Inattention to the condition of your church body can leave you vulnerable. Wise leaders learn to ask “Where are we experiencing corporate pain right now?” and to give honest answers to the question.

Be honest about your church. Spiritual and relational problems may not appear obvious on Sunday morning, but become evident in leader relationships and how issues play out behind the scenes. You are in grave danger if competition with other churches or church leaders, fear of blame or fear of failure prevents honesty. No church is perfect and acknowledging that fact about one's own church is a healthy step.

What We Suggest: Churches that fall in this range require more discernment to determine how to proceed. We recommend that you:

1. Purchase copies of *Diagnosing the Heart of Your Church*, by Mark Barnard for your church's leadership to read. This book helps you recognize whether you simply have a problem in one area of church life or if your church suffers from deeper problems.
2. Contact us about setting up a ChurchScan Inventory specifically for your church. Doing so enables your leaders to participate in the online assessment while quickly producing a composite score for all entries. Your church's composite score, along with coaching with one of our staff to interpret your score, can help you recognize if you need to heal your church or simply need to strengthen a particular area of church life.

Southern Church (LP2) Scan Inventory, Present–2022

	Item	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
Corporate Pulse					
	Our Congregation often has fun together, and joy is in the “atmosphere” when gathered	√			
	Our lay leaders are excited and enthusiastic about the ministry of the church		√		
	Our church leaders (pastoral, lay, and staff) enjoy unity and love among ourselves.		√		
	Our church has many former leaders who are willing and eager to serve in the future			√	
	Pastors at our church feel respected and enjoy long, positive tenures		√		
Trust in Leadership					
	Lay Leaders and the congregation are open to pastoral Initiatives	√			
	The pastoral staff and congregation are open to board initiatives.		√		
	Our church is free from reactive, resistant behavior toward leadership	√			
	Our church business meetings are pleasant and non-conflicted.		√		
	Our Church’s leaders are free from a need to control the congregation.		√		
Mission / Vision / Fulfillment					
	Our church regularly sees conversions from its services and individual evangelism			√	
	God calls a good number of young people from our church into full-time ministry			√	
	Our pastor and his family are free from unhealthy stress, related to his role in the church			√	
Mission / Vision / Fulfillment					

	Item	Very Great Extent	Great Extent	Some Extent	Not At All
	Our church enjoys a consistent sense of ministry effectiveness and momentum.			√	
	Our church is accomplishing what Christ put it in our community to do.		√		
Communication					
	Our pastor, staff, and lay leaders feel safe discussing difficult issues with each other		√		
	When leaders know real problems exist, they talk about them. No “elephants” are in the room			√	
	Our leaders resolve their interpersonal conflicts in a godly and timely manner.		√		
	Our church's leaders courageously and consistently address church discipline issues			√	
	We are currently free from unhealthy / destructive interpersonal tension within the church	√			
Historical Crises					
	Our church was birthed without controversy or from a split			√ - KJV Issue	
	Our church history is free of injuries / wounds committed against previous pastors, boards, or staff	√			
	Our church's history is free of stories of bad behavior by previous pastors, boards, or staff	√			
	Our church is free from any repetitive history (cycle) of corporate pain.	√			
	Our church is currently free of trauma or corporate pain [1]	√			

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congregation will not trust current leaders, or boards won't trust pastors because of wounds received from other leaders in the past. The crux of this is that, if people do not trust their leaders, they will not follow them, so every leadership initiative gets resisted or openly opposed.

- *High Trust - 17:* The Scripture says, “Behold, how good and how pleasant it is for brothers (and sisters) to dwell together in unity!” Where trust for leaders is high, leaders enjoy positive, happy, lengthy tenures. Such leadership also produces growing, healthy congregations. Mutual trust and accountability between pastoral staff and lay leaders radiates out from there to the congregation. Leaders are followed and their initiatives received without resistance.
- *Action Point:* The temptation faced by leaders with trust is to take inappropriate advantage of it, or to seek to be served rather than serve. Learn to protect and build up your bank account of trust by understanding how leaders lose it and how hard it is to rebuild once lost.

Mission/Vision Fulfillment: How well are you fulfilling your church's mission/vision—the reason why Christ put you where you are? This is a great indicator of either God's blessing on your ministry or a red flag revealing His unhappiness with you. Do you as leaders know, pray about, and pursue with commitment the mission/vision God has laid upon your hearts or on your founders' hearts? Failure to do so can be a clear symptom of the fabric of your church starting to unravel. Churches that are sick tend to use their energy and resources to get better—i.e. focus on themselves and not on reaching out. Underlying issues can subvert your best, most creative efforts at fulfilling all that God has in mind for your congregation.

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also scores low in the “Trust in Leadership” category, crises can result in splits, firings, petitions, or other highly unhealthy corporate behaviors.

- *Little Evidence of a Historical Crises - 18:* This is a great blessing to be celebrated. Rare is the church in existence more than ten years which has not faced such crises. Your church appears free of major pain, and it’s something for which you should be tremendously thankful! But a clear history does not mean a clear future. Make sure you as leaders are staying prepared to face such events with wisdom and sensitivity.
- *Action Point:* Ask God to give you the grace to deal with conflict or crises (when they do come) in a way He can bless. Many churches languish for having failed to do so.

Total ChurchScan Score - 75

INTENTIONAL EFFORT REQUIRED: You need to address the causes of your problems and work toward strengthening your church – *before things get worse.*

General Assessment: Churches scoring in the 51–75 range exhibit a mix of healthy and unhealthy traits, where the key for leaders is to assess honestly the frequency and direction of them, i.e. are they getting worse? Monitoring is important because the frequency of pain and ministry frustration can signal your need for congregational healing. Inattention to the condition of your church body can leave you vulnerable. Wise leaders learn to ask “Where are we experiencing corporate pain right now?” and to give honest answers to the question.

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Appendix E. Strong's Expanded / Full Description of the Word ἐπιδιορθόω

1909. ἐπί **ēpi**, *ep-ee'*; a prim. prep. prop. mean. *superimposition* (of time, place, order, etc.), as a relation of *distribution* [with the gen.], i.e. *over; upon*, etc.; of *rest* (with the dat.) *at, on*, etc.; of *direction* (with the acc.) *towards, upon*, etc.:—about (the times), above, after, against, among, as long as (touching), at, beside, × have charge of, (be-, [where-]) fore, in (a place, as much as, the time of, -to), (because) of, (up-) on (behalf of), over, (by, for) the space of, through (-out), (un-) to (-ward), with. In compounds it retains essentially the same import, *at, upon*, etc. (lit. or fig.), 30.

3717. ὀρθός **ōrthōs**, *or-thos'*; prob. from the base of **3735**; *right* (as *rising*), i.e. (perpendicularly) *erect* (fig. *honest*), or (horizontally) *level* or *direct*:—straight, upright, 52.

(3735. ὄρος ὄrōs, or'-os; prob. from an obsol. ὄρω ὄrō (to rise or "rear"; perh. akin to **142**; comp. **3733**); a mountain (as lifting itself above the plain):—hill, mount (-ain), 52.

142. αἴρω **airō**, ah'ee-ro; a prim. verb; to lift; by impl. to take up or away; fig. to raise (the voice), keep in suspense (the mind); spec. to sail away (i.e. weigh anchor); by Heb. [comp. 5375] to expiate sin:—away with, bear (up), carry, lift up, loose, make to doubt, put away, remove, take (away, up), 8.

3733. ὄρνις ὄrnis, or'-nis; prob. from a prol. form of the base of **3735**; a bird (as rising in the air), i.e. (spec.) a hen (or female domestic fowl):—hen, 52.

3735. ὄρος ὄrōs, or'-os; prob. from an obsol. ὄρω ὄrō (to rise or "rear"; perh. akin to 142; comp. 3733); a mountain (as lifting itself above the plain):—hill, mount (-ain), 52.

Appendix F. The Morphology of ἐπιδιορθόω

The word, ἐπιδιορθόω, is a verb, in the aorist tense, middle voice, and subjunctive mood.

1. Aorist Tense - This fact implies unspecified action.¹³⁹ The actions encouraged by Paul to Titus are given in general, overall recommendations, which leaves Titus the freedom to follow the leadership of the Holy Spirit.

2. Voice - Middle - This “voice” emphasizes Titus’s involvement in the action of the verb and the resulting benefits arising from the action¹⁴⁰

3. Mood - Subjunctive - This is the mood of possibility and potentiality - It carries no aspect of time - (This mood use should be understood as emphasizing that this ordering of things in Crete should be seen as possible, but not certain).¹⁴¹ Aorist Subjunctive is used when the action described is indefinite, undefined, or simple.¹⁴²

¹³⁹ Fredrick J. Long, *Kairos: A Beginning Greek Grammar* (Mishawaka, IN: Fredrick J. Long, 2005), 93.

¹⁴⁰ Long, *Kairos*, 25.

¹⁴¹ Long, *Kairos*, 204–205.

¹⁴² Long, *Kairos*, 207.

Appendix G. Email Interview Mark Barnard

1. Is there an actual research base for your program (or is the program just a practical application of biblical truth gained through experience)? If there is a research base, how was the research conducted and when?

The program we use was developed out of a combination of Ken's personal journey, his D.Min. in family systems counseling, clear biblical teaching, and a sensitivity to the Holy Spirit. He did not look around the body of Christ and say, "Hey the church has wounds and systemic pain that needs to be treated biblically." It was more along the lines of a convergence of events in his life and the experience of the church in Toronto that he served at the time. Then, other churches read his book, *Healing the Heart of Your Church*, and sought his help.

2. Is there any ongoing research being conducted?

Ongoing research is limited to our online assessment called the ChurchScan Inventory. I think we are up to 2000 participants and we periodically assess the results. The survey is limited to the internal relational and spiritual functioning of a church and not the more common church growth or church health paradigms.

3. How do you see your program adding to the field of knowledge in relation to church revitalization?

We believe our approach is fundamental to revitalization because at the heart of revitalization is hearing from Jesus about the true condition of the ministry. What would He commend, what would He say are the challenges a church has faced

through the years, and of what would he say, "I have this against you?" To jump into a church and start a revitalization process without dealing with the spiritual history (especially painful history) of a group sets the revitalization pastor up for difficulty because the underlying dynamics that have led to the church's need of revitalization have never been addressed. That which the Lord may have against the church has never been repented of. Therefore, His blessing is stymied on that ministry regardless of any change in ministry model, vision, mission or values - not to mention changes in leadership.

4. What strengths does your work bring to the field of revitalization?

The strengths we bring shift the way we view the church from a gathering of individuals to a body that is subject to infection and wounds just as the human body is. This body perspective shifts the way we view problems in the church to pain in the body. The pain a church experiences corporately is often a signal of a deeper issue, particularly if it is repetitive, as it often is. I think we also contribute by looking at church pain as divine discipline rather than as a "test" or the enemy afflicting a church. This totally shifts the way leaders view the crises they experience in ministry. I also think our ministry offers hope to ministries that are on their last legs. They usually try every pragmatic, policy, or personnel change before they get to us. Sometimes for real change to occur the Lord has to bring us to such a desperate condition.

5. Do you see this work lacking in certain areas? If so, where?

What do I see lacking in our "program?" We are a ministry in waiting. By that, I mean that many churches would benefit from corporate discernment and healing. However, we are in a culture that is trained in individualism and pragmatism. It rarely occurs to church leaders to ask the Lord to "show us the real nature of our problems as a body." So as a ministry, we are swimming upstream. Another weakness is that we cannot control the outcome. We present the ministry God has entrusted to us to churches, but ultimately it is up to the church to address what they hear from the Lord. Many churches do, but others are so deeply dysfunctional that they would rather the ministry die than admit their sins and deal with their wounds.

Appendix H. Ministerial Competencies for Revitalization

Thirty-six Expert Competencies - Love for God, Love for the Bible, Humility, Evangelism (motive), Glory of God, Godly, Perseverance, Commitment to Bible Centrality, Bible Teaching, Great Commission, Honesty, Values Discipleship, Love for the Church (individual), Prayerful, Support from Spouse, Work Ethic, Commitment to Prayer, Values People, Biblical/Doctrinal/Theological Knowledge, Biblical Community, Calling to Ministry, Commitment to Preaching, Undershepherd Mentality, Evangelism (skill), People Skills, Preaching (skill), Love for People, Forgiving, Leadership, Church Health, Discipleship, Holiness, Teachable, Identity in Christ, Values Membership, Develop Leadership.

Seventy-six Core Competencies: Preaching (motive), Long-suffering, Authenticity, Self, Developing Others, Love for the City/Community Repentance , Determination, Self-Control, Calling to Individual Church, Dependence on Sovereignty of God, Long-Term Perspective, Church Health Knowledge, Relationship Building, Vision Casting, Personal Growth, Patience, Visionary, Commitment to Longevity, Resolve, Values Church Unity Biblical Ecclesiology, Conflict Resolution, Interpersonal Communication, Motivation, Strategic Planning, Congregational Knowledge, Preaching Knowledge, Timing, Willingness to Confront, Community/Context Knowledge, Love for the Church (Universal), Lifelong Learner, Shared Leadership, Teamwork and Cooperation, Approachability, Missional Success Metrics, Thick-Skinned, Delegation, Achievement Orientation, Values the Established Church, Community Engagement, Knowledge, Leadership Knowledge, Revitalization Leadership Knowledge, Diplomacy, Encouragement, Interpersonal Understanding, Missional Knowledge, Contextual Skills, Commitment to Expository Preaching, Initiative, Positivity and Optimism, Change Knowledge, Church Discipline, Flexibility, Impact and Influence, Troubleshooting,

Replication, Driven, Innovative, Organizational Communication, Organizational Skills, Service Orientation, Compassionate, Risk-Taker, Organizational Commitment, Knowledge of Church's History, Analytical Thinking, Church Growth Knowledge, Conceptual Thinking, Contentment, Self-Confidence, Small Groups Knowledge, Broad Skill Set, Cross-Cultural Sensitivity, Organizational Awareness.

Fifteen Supplemental Competencies: Concern for order, quality, and accuracy, Revival Knowledge, Networking, Sense of Humor, Church Planting, Knowledge, Information Seeking, Love For Children, Charismatic, Ministry Experience, Elder Led Polity, Commitment To Fasting, Counseling, Knowledge of Church History, Technological Skills, Extrovert., Extrovert

Appendix I: Revitalization Characteristics

Rogers

1. Leadership - Specifically called to lead that church
2. Teaching and Preaching the Bible - Text driven
3. The Priesthood of the Believer
4. Baptist and the Lord's Supper
5. Prayer
6. Pastoral trust
7. Committed to caring relationships, servant leadership
8. Servant leader multiplication
9. Outward focus
10. Mission, Vision, and Plan
11. Church Discipline
12. Be conscious of the past
13. Repentance
14. Discipleship
15. Personal evangelism - Commitment to the Great Commission.

Kendrick

1. Preparation for worship
16. Developing Leadership
17. Frequent evaluation of ministries
18. Identifying with the community.
19. Time commitment
20. Narrowing of ministry focus for a time
21. Spiritual Revival

Sprayberry

1. Change of worship style
22. Children's ministry
23. Renewal of core values and priorities.
24. Ministry teams
25. Patient, sensitive approach to change.

Sullivan

1. Change of worship style

26. Address Community felt needs - reconnect to the Community
27. Updating facilities
28. Staff and Pastoral changes
29. Leadership training
30. New Missional focus
31. Letting go of the past

Chappell

1. Prayer and discernment
32. Planning
33. Mission/Vision statement
34. Preaching - expository
35. Systematic evaluation
36. Small group establishment
37. Group leader training

Breakout churches characterized by Hadaway - 1991

1. Evangelism

38. Goal orientation
39. Facilities and settings
40. Congregational structure
41. Congregational character
42. Planning and Goal setting
43. Pastor and staff
44. Evangelism and outreach
45. Sunday School
46. Worship
47. Other church programs
48. Integration and assimilation
49. Morale and desire for growth
50. Spiritual emphasis and renewal

Samelson - 1999

1. Strong Pastoral Leadership
2. Positive Personality
3. Good Preaching Skills

4. Vision and Planning Skills
5. Being Accessible to the Congregation
6. Modeling Faithfulness
7. New Worship Services
8. Attracting Young People and Children
9. Quality Ministerial Staff
10. Creating Small Groups
11. Renewal Programs
12. Development of Lay Leadership

Stroh - 2014

1. New Pastor
13. Focus on Outreach
14. New or Expanded Facilities
15. Deliberate Ministry Planning
16. More Member Ministry
17. Added Staff
18. Quality Worship or Worship Variety

19. New Ministries

Bond - 2015

1. Missionary Mentality

20. Vibrant Leadership

21. Relational Intentionality

22. Prayerful Dependence

23. Worship

24. Community

25. Mission

Shelton - 2015

Pastor and His Leadership.

Appendix J. Transcribed Pastoral Interview, Midwestern Church

[redacted in various places—generally signified by an ellipsis—for the improved flow and elimination of extraneous content]

Interviewer

[00:03]

All right I think I'm ready.

Respondent

Alright ... Well, go ahead and ask away. I will do my best to answer.

Interviewer

Fantastic! All right. I was wanting to begin just with a basic history because my interest is in church renewal and revitalization. I have grown up in Baptist churches all of my life. I started when I was about five or six years of age and the church that I was a member of back in those days was a church in revival. They had probably on average five or six hundred people on high days. With big meetings and special events, they would have up to eight hundred. [00:42] And for about eight months to ten months from my recollection they had somebody saved and baptized basically every service for like eight to ten months. And it was just an amazing experience. Of course, I don't remember a whole lot about it. My pastor at that time who was my long-term pastor, died about ten years ago. So...since that time, you know, I've been associated obviously with other Baptist churches, but I've noticed a gradual decline not only in membership but in effectiveness and I think that's been a noticeable decline across the board, not just in Baptist churches and right now there's a whole lot of interest, as you probably know, in church renewal and revitalization.

[01:30]

You know not just in the Baptist world but in lots of other worlds as well. So what I'm trying to do, is immerse myself in this field because the three churches that I've pastored have been what most people would consider dead or dying churches. And I've worked to understand these churches. I have worked to try to understand how to recover these churches. What I've done is I've reached out to people, individuals, who have had churches in similar circumstances and seeing what they did and tried to listen to what they have done to bring those churches back. I found one church that had completely closed down and had re-opened with new leadership and now is [02:20] basically independent caring for its own pastor financially supporting missions you know the whole works. That's the only church I've found and I've searched high and low. Now from my understanding your church was one that, I believe your words were, was almost as good as dead when you took it, is that right?

Respondent

[02:41]

It was definitely on life support because of problems that existed at the time so we still have a core.. a core people coming....about a hundred and fifty.

Interviewer

[02:52]

Yes.

Respondent

The indebtedness that the church was one point seven million dollars.

Interviewer

Okay.

Respondent

And then we had nothing to show for the money. It had been absconded for the most part [03:05]. Pastor and his wife both went to federal prison over that matter. We were in a place where the payments on the debt... we were in a receivership bankruptcy. So when I took over the church the payments on the debt were ten thousand dollars a month. And with a hundred and fifty people ...that's really, that was really touch and go.

Interviewer

[03:30]

Right.

Respondent

And you know, our ability to keep the door open. And on top of that, a series of failed leaders had come through the church and they had had very brief pastorates [03:41]. So they had many years of brief pastorates. And then they'd gone for eighteen months without a pastor before I came. And of course, with no leadership, there was tensions in the congregation. The deacons told me at that time that the church was ready to split, which would have...which really would have humanly speaking ended the ministry [04:04]. On top of it during that time... this is over twenty-five years ago, I've been here twenty-two years. The problems happened a long time ago [04:15]. But during that time the press was very bad for the church. I mean the reputation in the community was completely destroyed. It was, it made all the papers. It was in the news on a regular basis when it was happening.

And, um, so yeah, we really had some mountains to cross.

Interviewer

[04:33]

Sure. Absolutely. Let me ask you this question, and right now I don't have a set list of questions. I'm just kind of going from my gut right now based on my experience with my own churches and basic experiences with other churches and these two past interviews that I've had which have been real helpful. What is your...and this and this may be a good foundational question... what is your opinion your belief about churches that are basically dead or dying? I'm finding that some pastors say, you know, just go ahead and bury them and move on and start a new one. But you know there are some that will say well no I don't think that's the best way. I think that we need to try to renew these churches, revive, revitalize these churches. So what is your philosophy, your opinion about this because there are a whole lot of churches that are just hanging on the vine right now?

Respondent

[05:31]

I definitely think that we need to revitalize the churches. I'm not in favor of closing churches unless the church has become a real cancer in its community. There are some churches... I know one in Wyoming that had really become a cancer in the small town that it was located in and I believe has closed its doors since but for the most part I think the vast majority are redeemable [05:58]. The issue is not so much the church as it is the man who comes in to do that work.

Interviewer

Yes.

Respondent

And so...a lot of men today are looking for kind of a tailor-made situation... a good stable church, a good stable salary... all of the benefits without having to build that themselves. And that to me is the bigger problem. We've lost a sense of a pioneering spirit. When I came here I was thirty-one years old. I had to have a strong pioneering spirit...[06:35]...to deal with the church, because in addition to all of its problems, without leadership the church had gone, in truth, what would have been called at the time, New Evangelicalism. It was flirting with that.... Multiplicity of Bible versions in the church. We had some music that was unacceptably contemporary. And so yeah we had a boatload of problems; no standards of any kind. It was difficult but again I go back to saying, okay does the man have a pioneering spirit? Is he the type of person gifted who can revitalize the church with his spirit being right? It has to be a man who's very positive; who's a strong leader but who is very diplomatic because you're sorting through a lot of historic problems very early on. I found when I came here that whenever someone took me out to lunch they just wanted to give me their take on the situation and then tell me how to fix it...[07:38]...Getting their take was interesting because a lot of it was similar. Then there were some people who had dissimilar ideas but the how to fix it part was also interesting. I benefited from getting to know the people on that level but I sure had a lot of eager contributors.

Interviewer

[07:57]

Sure, I imagine so. So a hundred and fifty, now that's, you know, for all practical purposes a pretty good number to start with, of course you know with the indebtedness that you had and some of the problems and background issues that you had, that certainly makes it challenging. Let me ask you a question though... you mentioned this thing about leadership, being a strong leader, diplomatic leader. Do you feel like you went into this church with those qualifications or do you feel like you developed them or maybe developed better in those areas after taking this church?

Respondent

[08:34]

I certainly...went in with some qualifications, and my very first church which I took when I was twenty-one years old. I was still a Bible college student at ... That church was on the verge of closing. That church had thirty-five members and I think a hundred and ten thousand dollars worth of debt. It was in ... Yeah, it was, it was on the ropes. They actually voted me in and I was not even married at the time. They voted me in as their pastor because they said that they knew the church was going to fold and when it did that I could just leave. It wouldn't hurt me. I didn't have a wife or kids...[09:09]...So we built that church up to probably two hundred, two fifty on a really good day.

Interviewer

That's very good...Let me approach this from a slightly different perspective for a moment. You said that you've been at your present church for, what did you say, twenty-two years?

Respondent

[09:30]

Twenty-two years on February 11.

Interviewer

Okay. Twenty-two years is a long time ago, at least from my perspective it is. I'm fifty-two right now and I can think back to, you know, thirty-two. And the culture and the climate were different I think in those days...[09:54]...the culture and the climate religiously, politically, morally, so many things have changed. What I'm curious about is this. When you're trying to go into a church revitalization or church renewal area it is I think it's so much harder now to try to revitalize and renew for a couple of different reasons because people's mindsets have changed; their ideas about faith, I mean the contemporary movement, the emergent movement, all of those things have come in like a flood of course, you know, the the the moral decline/implosion in our nation which we've seen; the difficulty that it is to actually win people to the lord now. I'm just wondering from your perspective in this day. I mean, what do you think are the key ingredients? I know you've got to have good leadership, strong leadership; and by the way in that context, you know, I think that's key because when Paul sent someone to Crete just like we talked about

in class he sent Titus. He didn't send Timothy. He sent Timothy to Ephesus. so I think there is wisdom...because he knew that Titus was a little more rough and tumble, you know, kind of guy, and knew that he could maybe handle that better than Timothy. So what do you think in this day... because I know it's slow go. I mean it's plodding along in a lot of regards in areas, but what are the key ingredients now do you think in this present culture to try to revitalize and renew...what are some of the things that you did? What are some of the things that you think would work today; maybe some things that you think wouldn't work today because things are so different culturally?

Respondent

[11:36]

Well, you know, I think that's a great question because honestly, I wouldn't want to face this church in that condition in today's culture. That would be... it would make it exponentially more difficult... is kind of the buckle of the Bible belt of ... and so we have a very strong presence of what's called the Christian church, the independent Christian church, and they're a break off the Church of Christ and some of them preach water baptism for salvation. That's really their official stand [12:10]. Others of them don't really emphasize that but when I first came here they were the churches that had begun growing. Today, ... Christian church changed its name to ... and they will have four thousand people on a Sunday in a beautiful modern campus...[12:30. We couldn't keep up with that. Those churches are very highly programmed. There is something for everybody... And all the time. I mean seven days a week and so they really have attracted your younger families. And they've really attracted...all kinds of people because there's something for everybody there. So if I had to compete with that today, I would find it very difficult. So, basically, what I would have to offer that would be different would be a Baptist, a solid Baptist framework of doctrine; dispensationalism; clear Bible preaching, and a traditional worship. Now in our area the fact that I offer traditional worship as the mainstay of the church... we don't have a contemporary service or anything. [13:20]...the fact I offer that has really attracted a lot of people. Okay, so the stars aligned ... in a certain way here that made it easier. But, if I had to face the same thing today, I would say that it would be more difficult. Now, what are the things that worked? Okay. There's a big-picture thing that I think is indispensable. When a church begins to decline or gets into big trouble like my church was, the people begin to look inward; okay, everything is inward. Nothing is outward. That had been the habit here for many years. And so when I came and placed an emphasis on evangelism and outreach that was something the church had not had in many, many years. The older people took to it like a duck to water and that's all I had basically was older people [14:14]. They took to it like a duck to water, and...I said, look we cannot focus on what happened in the past and the court cases, the jailed pastor, all the failed ministries here... we have to recognize our church is a hub of the gospel. We must reach the community. So it began with changing their view and then I had to lead in that evangelism [14:39]...At the time we branded the church, Avon's home of the old-time religion. That actually got us quite a bit of attention. Newspaper attention and things like that. And then we had a lot of visitors come...Now that branding would not work today, probably. It probably would not work today. So that might not be something that I would repeat. But I think getting the

people to look outwardly was a very important thing, you know. A second thing...that I really strongly emphasized in my ministry is that I will love my people. Ok. I am not aloof. You cannot revitalize a church by being aloof. To me now, you can't pastor if you're aloof. The old school kind of, you know, walking above the people kind of thing and distance? That doesn't work anymore because people want a pastor who is real. They want a pastor who is transparent. They want a pastor whom they can relate to [15:41]...I think those are some things today that would work, but one of the chief things I came in with, kind of a personal slogan, was loving the people and directing them to look outwardly. So we started a bus ministry which we still have today. But again, there again, would I recommend that as a means? I think it's a very good means but if the church is really struggling, that's very expensive.

Interviewer

[16:13]

Right. Plus it's easy to bring in children but if you don't have the required people and organization to manage it well, it can become unwieldy.

Respondent

[16:25]

Yeah, there was a time ... when I was younger when everyone decided that the bus ministry was...the bus ministry was the answer. I can't say that today. Okay, it helped our church to give an outward focus but, I can't, I can't necessarily say that today so [16:46]...It would be... I think there would be a lot of challenges. You know I'm fifty-two like you are. I'm old and cool, okay, and was raised old school. So what are some things that... I hire younger staff. We have a great youth pastor. He just had thirty kids saved on Friday night at a youth activity. He had a big lock-in. He had a hundred thirty-plus young people attend that. He's doing a great job. You know, so, you know, these are younger guys. They have other ideas. One thing that I think is vital today is that the pastor lead in giving his church an online presence but beyond a website [17:26]...so when I say beyond a website, if he can preach a lick, he needs to have his sermons put up...on sermon audio or something because we do have a lot of people who come to our church that moved into the area, who have listened to me for six months before they get here [17:44]...and they join the church. We've had some great families do that. So you have to have that kind of presence today. But I think it takes...a special man. And also, honestly, you have to look at the area. So I got a call last night from a guy who...grew up in our church here and he lives in Louisiana now and attends a church maybe about a hundred and fifty people and they hired a pastor...a few months ago. They just made a huge mistake. If ten percent of what he's telling me is correct they made a huge mistake [18:18]. And I would want to get rid of him and that puts the church in a hard position. But the problem with that church is it's in Podunksville ... And you're not gonna find a young guy with a lot of talent who is gonna want to camp out there very long... although I think he could build a great church there[18:39]... But you know what I'm saying. This is a suburb of ... This is the second fastest growing county in ... and it's...a very nice area to live. We have a lot of people moving in... a lot of industry. And so...all those factors, I know I cannot discount that. Another factor there, just to be frank with you, in our growth was are very

large G. R. B. C. church, but for all practical purposes it was...independent. It was led by probably one the best soul winners to ever live in the state of ... apart from ... [19:14]. He built a church of fifteen hundred to two thousand, won most of the people to Christ himself. This would go, hearken back to the nineteen seventies; built a huge work. When he died it was...turned over to a series of buffoons. There's just no other way to describe it.

Interviewer

[19:35]

Mmmm. Sad.

Respondent

The guy that's there now changed it from a Baptist church to a Bible church and he went to elder rule. And so what's happened is all those old solid trained Baptist people, they've migrated to ... So they've migrated and they're tithers....and they're workers....[19:55...]And so that was another benefit that I had. So I can't say that I have some kind of recipe for this. The stars aligned, if I can use that phraseology. The Lord knew what he was doing in this area...[20:11]....and I'm fortunate enough to be the leader of this.

Interviewer

Yes, that is blessed. I'm tellin' ya. I'm proud that you have this opportunity and are willing to share it with me. Even though my experience has not been that...I'm encouraged by what you're saying. My pastorates have been difficult and most of them have been in Podunk USA. I'm not connected to any large city, by any means. I'm in real country areas. In fact, the area that I'm in right now is very poor. There's lots of drugs... drug activity; lack of education. It's a dying town. The growth rate last year was negative zero point four percent so people are leaving.

Respondent

[20:58]

Where are you at ...?

Interviewer

... is probably about forty-five minutes south of ...

Respondent

[21:11]

Then you are in the country.

Interviewer

Yes, we're way out, and you know, you've opened up a lot of avenues...that we could traipse down here for just a little bit, but I wanna make sure I'm staying focused on this because I think you and I could probably talk all day about these matters. One of the things I want to ask is this. And this is one of the things that I'm trying to promote and champion. And this may just be a little commercial here before I ask you another question but, [21:40] I began this conversation by

saying a lot of other denominations are looking at church renewal or revitalization, and that's true: The Presbyterians, the Methodists, all of them. And they are establishing training educational programs in their facilities to train pastors to go out into these types of environments where they may have to work. They may have to get a job because churches can't support you full time so they're training them differently today. But I don't know of one independent Baptist training center of any note that has any church renewal revitalization focus or degrees. Do you know of any?

Respondent

[22:23]

No, I really don't. I really don't. I think that's an area that would be important. When I was a student at ..., I approached the Dean or one of those...some college official, and I asked if it would be possible for me to major in Bible and minor in auto mechanics at the school of applied studies... [22:42]...the Dean laughed at me and I said, no this is in case, you know, I'm in a church where you don't... I can't make much money and it would be helpful and he said, No, No they would never permit that.

Interviewer

Wow.

Respondent

I think that was an idea way ahead of its time.

Interviewer

[22:55]

I really do too.

Respondent

Men have got to have a way to support themselves and be well trained for the ministry because the smaller churches need men... [23:06]...they need men to come in. Maybe a man won't spend his whole life there... so this is an interesting thing. I preached a couple years ago up in ... for ... at a little town called ... His church is a big church. Hundreds of people go... I would say maybe three, four, five hundred. I don't know exactly... somewhere in that vicinity. It is the only thing in town. There's one stoplight in the whole county. It is a very poor county and it is way up north, in the woods in ... He's built an excellent work there, okay [23:38]. And then I met his conference ...it was the Small Church Pastors Conference. And so I met men who have been pastoring in the woods of ... for twenty, thirty, you know thirty-five years...

Interviewer

[23:53]

Sure.

[24:06]

Respondent

If you're an outdoorsman, hunter, and fisher like I am... that would be attractive. I could see that. But I think the mentality, honestly ... some of the young men that that we're training at ... I see a brightness about them. I see a loyalty to want to follow the Bible. They're not interested in our traditions or our preferences but they want to follow the Bible. I find that very positive. What I'm struggling with seeing is the pioneer spirit [24:37]. Let's say I could go to this place... church, the church I'm at now. This is the first church in my ministry, the only church in my ministry where I was able to work full time at the church and not have something on the side... I've done it all. I've roofed houses. I've emptied dumpsters. I've done it all, but I recognize the need for that in my two earlier ministries. I recognized the need for that, and I never thought I thing about it. This is just what I do.

Interviewer

[25:09]

Sure. Well, I think that... as another sideline to this topic, I think that you know ... at ... is hitting on the same idea. I don't know if you know much about him but he has actually developed a program at his school which allows for the training of preachers in auto mechanics, welding, and electrical. I believe because he knows and he can see that a lot of these young pastors are going out and they're finding themselves in these churches that just can't support them full time and what are they going to do, you know.

Respondent

[25:51]

In addition to having those skills, you can make money; but you can also, you know, fix up your church or fix the buses or the cars.

Interviewer

Exactly. it provides a great opportunity.

Respondent

[26:03]

You know but I think... a man and his wife have to have a pioneering spirit and, honestly, they have to have the willingness to take a chance.

Interviewer

Right.

Respondent

[26:14]

You know. I mean... I'm not denigrating faith when I say this but, If you have a wife, and potentially kids it's a bit of a gamble [26:25]...to go into something that's really headed the wrong way quickly. Another point that I would make and I think, I think would be a mistake, whether it would be in the culture of twenty-two years ago or the culture today, I think it would be a

mistake to try to transform the church in true dramatic ways that leave the older people behind [26:48]...Every church in our community that has done that...a Baptist Church, they have bled members. The guy who works for the funeral director here...had a funeral on Saturday... and he came up to me and said, look, my church ..., he said, it's gone totally contemporary. They're using the E.S.V. He said, I'm done. You will see me in your church. I don't know if he was there yesterday or not [27:13]...But he's pretty serious about switching. He was a deacon for all these years... a leader in the church. So you can't do that. You cannot go in like a bull in a china closet. You have to win the people toward you [27:24]...And it's a process. It is definitely a process.

Interviewer

You know, speaking along those lines I read an article the other day and actually saved it I think. I think it came across my Twitter feed but there was a church somewhere that actually disinvented the elderly population that was in their church. They had mostly old people and they were going to take a new tack on this and try to reach out to young people. They were going to do everything different and they actually told these elderly people who have been at that church for years to leave and to not come back for two years, and then when they came back in two years, they would be received by interview to see whether they even wanted these people back or not. Is that not ridiculous?

Respondent

[28:12]

It's horrible...but I tell you that must...when you describe that...That must be a thing, that is being taught because the church, the big church I described earlier, they've done essentially that... they ended up hiring a guy from McArthur's seminary. He had failed in his first church work somewhere in California, and... as people would leave, they would...come to visit my church; they'd be gone for a Sunday or two. I think if they missed two Sundays they received a letter that stated they were no longer a member...

Interviewer

[28:43]

Wow.

Respondent

...Which was totally against the constitution. I have a lady in my church every time the doors open. Now she taught in their Christian school for thirty years. Just loved the Lord, and was an active person over there and they came visiting our church and, I think, two weeks later they got their letter that basically said, look, you're not on board with us so you're no longer a member. That must be a thing.

Interviewer

[29:08]

Yes, it sounds like it. Who knows what's being taught and where?

Respondent

They have destroyed their church. Now they keep their finances very secretive because they are borrowing money from the banks to keep it open [29:21]. They've really...just simply gutted it. Years ago, their leadership met with me when they were first headed into trouble and I told them what they needed to do and they ignored it. There were three families that wanted to go Calvinistic Reformed.

Interviewer

[29:39]

Yes.

Respondent

... direction... maybe not fully Reformed but more of a progressive dispensational view and kind of a weak sauce dispensational view and they found the guy that would do it. He's just leading the church right into destruction [29:56]. I bet I have four, three or four families from that church in my church for the first time yesterday.

Interviewer

Wow.

Respondent

Yeah. It's ridiculous.

Interviewer

[30:06]

Right, well.

Respondent

People would come to me when they want to join this church, and I interview them; and they'll say something like, you know, I really...feel bad leaving my church. They don't use the King James so I have no problem saying this. I said, well don't think of it that way. Your church left you.

Interviewer

[30:22]

That's true.

Respondent

So this idea of eliminating the tithers and the faithful people who invested in that work...That's completely wrong.

Interviewer

[30:33]

Yeah.

Respondent

Now can you slowly modernize a church to make it appealing to younger families...but still maintain the old people? Yes, you can. And again, it really depends on the area that you're in. So our church has traditional music but it's not stuffy.

Interviewer

[30:52]

Sure.

Respondent

Okay. we have we have we have a vibrant online ministry. We have a vibrant presence and preaching on the internet. We have live stream. We have all those things. We're building. In fact, we are right in the middle of building a six-million-dollar new building, just down the road... twenty-five acres, and that will look very modern. The building we're in now, if you came over here ... looked at this, you'd laugh. You would just laugh. This was built beginning in the nineteen fifties [31:20]. Yeah, I mean it's laughable. We don't have room to park. We don't have room for people...when we get into the new facility, I've assured the people that a new church does not mean a new culture [31:37]. That's key, because a lot of churches struggle when they go from an old building to a newer facility, you know...the piano, the organ, the little orchestra. those things will all be in place... the music will remain conservative. And I promised the people this over and over again...we're not changing what we're doing, we're just going to do more of it.

Interviewer

[32:00]

Sure.

Respondent

The people feel very comfortable with that but honestly ... it's a miracle. I have thirty-six, I think, in my young couple's Sunday school class. I teach the young couples class. And we've added new young families but to me, honestly, you know we're working against the building right now. But we've done enough things to demonstrate we're not anti. We're not anti... does that make sense...we're not outside, like, we're not anti- [32:34] technology.

Interviewer

I understand totally because a lot of Independent Baptist churches are. I mean if you introduced...if you put your songs up on the screen, you've gone contemporary, you've gone liberal. And a lot of the Independent Fundamental Baptists with a capital I capital B would reject ya, and that's just a little thing. I mean you might mention other things as well but I totally understand where you're coming from there.

Respondent

[33:04]

Right, right.

Interviewer

And I don't have my songs on the screen, so I'll just go and say that. I know others that have.

Respondent

We would never get rid of the hymnbook. if I decide to put words up, we would still never get rid of the hymnbook. We will use the hymnbook and tell people to turn in their hymnbook. We'll do all that.

Interviewer

[33:20]

Sure. Yeah, I still do that as well. You know speaking about the middle group, I've been asked to preach a revival for a church, probably about thirty-five forty minutes away from where I'm at right now and this church is struggling on various levels, and one of the levels that it's struggling on and is this. He said we have a lot of older people. He said we have a lot of young people. He said we run a bus route... we get about thirty-five or forty, you know, on that bus route every morning. He said we've got a sizable portion of older people, he said, but that middle age group is just really almost gone... it's almost missing... and it is in a lot of churches, so since you mentioned that, and you said you had thirty-some...young people in your class. How, how do you get those young people? Because, let me give you this illustration. I have tried to recruit help to this church and I think when you're renewing and revitalizing you need help. I mean you need almost a team to go into a church like this to try to renew and revitalize it but there was a man that I contacted that knew me. He came to the church once or twice. He was a missionary. He said I'll tell you what I'm gonna do. He said, I've got about [34:34], I don't know, maybe eight to ten young preachers sitting on the front row of a church that I know about, not too far from this church, he said, I'm going to talk to em and I will see if I can't recruit some of them to come down here and help you. And after about two months he didn't contact me so I reached out to him and he said, preacher...I'm so sorry. He said I told them all about you... about your work... about you trying to renew and revitalize this place and...not one of them was interested in coming over there to help you. He said, they're still just sitting on that front row, and that goes back to that [35:07] pioneering entrepreneurial...get out and get it done attitude. I mean how do you engage these people if you don't have them? I know you gotta pray. I know you got to do some other things to mention.

Respondent

[35:22]

...now obviously we didn't have them. Now when I came to the church I was in my early thirties. So that started to attract the attention of some younger ones...I immediately emphasized youth and children's ministries. Okay, you have to have something [35:39] for the youth.... okay you have to have it because the church had nothing else going for it. We had a guy who was coming

up from a Bible college that was, you know, pretty good youth man, and...I said look the only thing this church has is you and the potential of a youth group. When I got here there were maybe fifteen kids at the most, that would come and they would come not because their families came but they would come for activities and things. And so we really glorified the youth ministry. My youth pastor I currently have, he has paid for himself and his salary by bringing in families because of the youth emphasis [36:18]. We have an Awana program, and again that's labor intensive but to have something to offer children and youth is the only way you're going to attract and keep the middle-aged couples or the younger couples with kids. That's really important. Now where do you, how do you start that? You have got to have the people who are willing to do it. And sometimes that falls to the pastor. My first church, of course, I was the youth pastor. At my first church, there were no teenagers. In my first church I went into a trailer park and started meeting teenagers and [36:53] awkwardly tried to play basketball with them. I am not very athletic. I bought a bus for three hundred bucks and I said, okay we're gonna pick you all up...I was picking people up in my car and then I picked them up, I was the bus ministry. I didn't drive the bus. I had someone who would drive but I was the person who went out and worked it. and then I got some kids to come and then started to grow and then all of a sudden people were like, Oh, that church has something for young people. I think you can't underestimate the value of having something.

Interviewer

[37:25]

Right. Yeah yeah I think that's key and I think targeted ministry, you know, in a setting like this is very important for instance fifty-three percent of the babies that are born in our county are born to unwed mothers... fifty-three percent.

Respondent

[37:44]

Okay.

Interviewer

So there is no ministry in this area that is specifically targeting and reaching those single mothers. So, you know, if a pastor can develop some kind of an outreach, some kind of a ministry to encourage, to support, to help, to guide, to counsel these mothers and that's part of the reason why there is so much poverty in this area and part of the reason why there are so much drugs in this area. So I agree...I just wish that it was easier to attract people when you can't pay them anything for coming to help you.

Respondent

[38:20]

Ok...Ok, so you brought up an interesting point. So when I was a student at ...s, every Friday night we would go street preaching in ... We would preach at the bars until we closed them down. We had loudspeakers... the police were behind us. We would preach... we would win all these converts. There was only one church in town... It was called Oakwood Baptist church. But

they were kind of...they were kind of the independent church...they were kind of the wealthy and stuck up. They didn't want these converts [38:46]. So toward the end of my senior year, we planted a church in Anderson. Okay, in the bad neighborhood of Anderson, and the pastor who's been there since those days...friend of mine from college and remains their pastor today. He had a burden for it, but he needed helpers because he had no one. So ... was only thirty-five, forty minutes away so he started an extension ministry and he would have ten, fifteen, twenty ... kids coming down to help things and run the church and make great programs and stuff [39:24]. But do you know what happened ...? In the last... in the last, I think I'm right to say, yes, four years he would go up to the preacher boy class of ... which is greatly diminished from the time I was there and he would present this work as an opportunity to have an extension, to have an impact, and not one person. I think I'm right to stay in four years [39:46]...not one person from the university has shown any interest in it. And so he made an appeal to a southern Baptist college that's in Anderson, or right around there. I think they sent a couple kids but he told me that the atmosphere is so different. Man, when I was a ... student, all I wanted to do was get off campus. All I wanted to do was go out and preach...anything anything. Any dumb little thing you give me to do. I'm chomping at the bits to do it [40:14]... You know, I teach at ... Baptist College, which is about forty minutes away on the south side of town. I've got a couple kids coming from the college to our church and they're very helpful, and they're good kids but more and more, and it's a very small school, but more and more to suggest to a kid that he should drive forty minutes over here and be active in our ministry... No. There's a church directly across the street from that college. All you have to do is walk over there and sit your button in a pew and do nothing [40:45]...And that's Okay. And so many of them feel like that's okay. It's really a mentality thing.

Interviewer

Sure yeah, that's exactly right. It really is, and I think it's generational. And as much as I hate to categorize generations... you know you got Generation X, Generation Z, Generation this, that, and the other, I think there is a generational problem with the preachers that are being developed these days, that all they want is that position, that salary, that paid vacation, and they don't really want to get out and get their hands dirty.

Respondent

[41:25]

Right, exactly.

Interviewer

Yes. Now, let me ask you one more, or maybe a couple more questions and please feel free to interject anything that you think would help because I really have given my life, the rest of my life, to this idea of renewal and revitalization of churches and I have to understand this not just for myself but for the people that are struggling, and how this can be done; so feel free to add anything in and even after we get done talking if you think of something.. call me okay?

Respondent

[42:00]

I find this very, very interesting.

Interviewer

Well here's another thought because you know I've been engaged with this...I've been pastoring since about the year 2000. I took four years off to do some training and education, but got right back into it afterwards; And by the way, I've only got one more class in my doctoral program and then this major project that I have to write and I'll be done with my doctoral program so I'm really excited. But one of the things that I've faced and one of the things that I'm wading through in terms of understanding is this. There are some internal roadblocks to building and growing an Independent Baptist church in these days, and I know that I get off in dangerous waters when I start talking about these things but none the less it's still the fact, because I've had personal experience with each one of them. One of the things that's hindering Independent Baptist churches in terms of growth these days [42:53] is the standards issue. Let me just name a couple of them. The standards issue is one. The issue of the King James Bible is another. I've had problems on those two issues that I have not generated. I mean these are just like the internal...that kind of intertwined items with who Independent Baptists are. And I found those two issues specifically, and there are others, that could be mentioned. In fact, I did some writing on that in this doctoral program. But how do you overcome those internal issues? I mean because they keep cropping up. I had this one gentleman... I rarely say anything about the King James Version from the pulpit... now I do on rare occasions and I just happened to do so on a day when this elderly gentleman was in the congregation who had been visiting [43:45] I didn't say anything outlandish, by any means, I just mentioned something about the King James Bible being the inerrant and preserved Word of God. Well, he met me on the front porch after the sermon and I was basically attacked...for that belief. He said I can't believe that you would believe that and say that from the pulpit. And I tried graciously on the front porch of the church...to manage that. But I wrote him an email letter back. I tried to make a phone call. The man would not even return my call...would not return my emails...which he had done in the past. So you know he probably had some issues there as well, but he wouldn't come back.... I told him, that any public ministry or private ministry that is associated with this church will be done from the King James Bible. He told me ...[he works] youth...use[s] the N.A.S.B [44:39]. He said I think that's foolish. I would never fall underneath that.

Respondent

Right.

Interviewer

So those are the kind of issues that ... limit ...our growth.

Respondent

[44:52]

Right, right. So what I would suggest...on that, okay, so you can go overboard on the King James thing. When I came here I told the leadership and the church if you vote for me we will use the King James in all the ministries of the church. I said, eventually, I will kind of teach you why, and I've done some teaching on that topic over the years. Now, because we kind of put that in the DNA of the early ministry here I didn't have to, what's the word, I didn't have to, you know, I don't have to emphasize that now. And so I don't emphasize it now [45:28]. You know we have a public scripture reading, a responsive reading. You can't participate if you don't have a King James. Sometimes younger couples will come and they will enquire. They'll say, this is interesting that you use that version. And I'll say...Well, I have theological reasons to do so, and if they want to know, I will tell them but we're not gonna... over-emphasize that, but we will be very solid on it. One of the better arguments that I have is it promotes uniformity and promotes Bible memory. And then I'll talk about how no one memorizes scripture anymore because there are so many versions. And this version is a standard...and sometimes I talk about the literary quality of the King James as opposed to the modern versions and things like that. That's a little easier for some people to grasp.

Interviewer

[46:16]

Right.

Respondent

But no one could come here... so I've turned away people who are ... They reveal themselves very quickly about ten minutes after they visit. And I've turned them away and told them you can't join the church. You're not welcome here. So our position is strong but it's moderate. It's presented in a moderate way. And our people all understand that. They all get that. The standards thing. Okay. Again, I think our churches have got to be reasonable. It's okay to have a standard for the platform dress. It's okay to have a standard for the choir. People are going to be on the platform in the choir. It's okay to have youth group standards based on activities. Not just one you know carte blanc, this is what you're gonna wear. In my thinking, and a lot of this goes into Romans 14. In my thinking, it's suicide to get in the pulpit and declare that women should never wear pants [47:11]. Ok, in my thinking, now there are places where that might still fly, but again, you're not gonna really reach your community. And that is a preference issue, non-provable from the Scripture...so Paul said in First Corinthians 10, give none offense to the Jew, Gentile, nor to the church of God. Well...I could offend a Jew if I invited him to a pig roast. I could offend the church of God if I have an activity where there's playing cards or where there's...rock music or something like that. the old people would be offended by it and so would a lot of our young people [47:51]...But how do I offend Gentiles? ...How do you offend a Gentile? Well, the idea of offense is putting a stumbling block before them as regards the gospel and when all of your people dressed like they just stepped off of the set of Little House on the Prairie [48:08], that

becomes an offense. And people are like, that's just a weird church. And then they won't hear the message of the gospel because of it, and that impedes gospel preaching.

Interviewer

[48:19]

Sure.

Respondent

And I know ... if I said that... I will say this publicly have no problem saying this type of thing publicly because I do, but I know that there would be brethren who would declare that I'm not old paths and that's that's a thing, that we're old paths. It's a thing among certain people and they would declare me a compromiser. You're weak and all those things but, you know, I can't... I'm not going to alienate the lady who comes to church in pants. I'm glad she's here [48:48]. Nor am I gonna make that a test a fellowship at some point down the line.

Interviewer

Exactly. Exactly that's all real good information. I wish I had more time but it's one o'clock so I will have to get back after it here. I actually took my lunch break to talk to you, but I feel like there's so much more that...I could ask you and get wisdom. Would it be possible maybe if down the road I needed to call you back and talk to you, and maybe we could do that?

Respondent

[49:21]

Oh yeah, absolutely. I enjoyed our conversation immensely...And it's made me actually think through some of these issues a little more deeply. But you know, yes, absolutely. I would...ultimately like to see at least maybe an elective class [49:35] in our seminary or in our undergraduate program at the college at ... that actually addressed this issue.

Appendix K: Transcribed Pastoral Interviews, Southern Church

[redacted in various places—generally signified by an ellipsis—for the improved flow and elimination of extraneous content]

Interviewer

[00:00]

Okay, good, all right, I think we're recording now. I really appreciate you taking the time to do this and I'm glad that we were finally able to get together on this.

Respondent

[00:13]

I know it's been quite an ordeal getting it all set up and ready to go but I'm glad to be able to get with you.

Interviewer

...So that's basically where I'm at and the things that I have done, in a nutshell over the years, and I guess I just want to hear from you. Could just start by telling me a little bit about your church and your ministry there, and maybe what you've done prior and how all of it got started where you're at right now?

Respondent

[04:29]

Yes, I'll give you just a little bit of background about myself. I grew up in a pastor's home. My dad pastored basically from the time I was born till about thirteen/fourteen... somewhere in there, and at that time he went into missions work. We did this as a family and served in prison ministry. Did a lot of (My father did) overseas traveling and so we spent a lot of time on the road in those years raising support on deputation, mission conferences, all that kind of [05:11] ministry. And then as I graduated high school, I was trying to figure out what the lord wanted us to do, and ended up in a Bible college at Massillon Baptist College in Ohio and graduated there actually with a music degree [05:32]. I Had every intention of serving faithfully in a ministry somewhere, being a help to a pastor. When we graduated, my wife and I got married, and we moved back to my father-in-law's church..., over in ... Kentucky. We enjoyed being in the youth ministry there and served in a Christian school. We learned a lot and grew a lot there. Took those teenagers on a mission trip... went down, helped a church in ... that at the time was without a pastor [06:14]. Through that process of being there, seeing that church, and kind of getting a first-hand glimpse of what they were going through, being without a pastor at that time, the lord really began to work a lot in our hearts and lives. It was about a year later at that time that I sat down with our pastor and just talked about what the lord had put in our hearts and minds...to go somewhere and pastor.

Interviewer

[06:40]

Yes.

Respondent

So we begin that process of trying to figure out where the Lord wanted us to go. Had some possibilities here and there but really nothing substantial working out, and then the lord opened the door for us to come here to ..., and preach at the church, and at that time they had.. they had a missionary who lived here in the area that was kind of helping them out and filling in a little bit and was helping them to make some contacts with people. And so we came, and the Lord just opened all the doors...provided all the needs to get us moved from Kentucky to ... and get started here. So when we came around it was very very similar to what you were talking about. As far as the pastor that had started it, he was a good faithful solid man who had actually made some resignation from the Southern Baptist movement because of the King James issue [07:52]. He was up in age even when he started it. And so as he had gotten older, the congregation had gotten older. He had gotten cancer and was not able to fill the pulpit anymore [08:14]. And so, that's kind of the situation we stepped into there. When we came, the congregation, all of them, were older retired folks and just about eight or ten of them left when we came. In fact, on our first Sunday after they had voted us in as pastor there were ten of us. Five of those were myself, my wife, and our three kids. Very similar to what you had mentioned but the good thing about it was is that they had a building that was sufficient for say a hundred fifty or so comfortably. Had a fellowship hall. Had property. The church had a pretty good reputation in town, as far as that goes. So there was a lot of potential danger as much as there were problems. So that's kind of how we approached it...with that mentality as far as yes, there are churches everywhere but in our particular area there really wasn't a whole lot going on as far as outreach visitation, that kind of thing from good Independent Baptist church here in our town. There were some churches in our area you know... twenty, thirty, forty minutes away that were good and solid churches, and people were driving there.

Interviewer

[09:51]

Right.

Respondent

You know sometimes you have to do those kinds of things, but we just got started. Really getting started...My mindset in that was to feed the flock. You know there was definitely some need there for spiritual nourishment, preaching of the Word of God, encouragement, and fellowship. And so we just started that... just, you know, try to get to know people...try to get to know the area. Just really began that process of building relationships. And coming to the type of community that we did... it's just a small close-knit community town, one high school you know, one middle school.

Interviewer

[10:45]

Do you know the population of your town?

Respondent

In the city limits which are very very small, there are probably twenty-five hundred to three thousand.

Respondent

Within the eight to ten-mile radius, there's probably eight to ten thousand people.

Interviewer

Alright.

Respondent

Spread out little communities here and there. We are definitely a rural area...more of a country area but...very close knit you know. If something's going on at this or that school, it's a whole town thing. And everybody shows up you know to watch a baseball or football game or whatever. And so I really thought that it would take us quite some time to kind of become a part of the fabric of that community because immediately everybody knew that we were the out-of-towners...that was very obvious. And so that process obviously went a lot faster than I thought it would, but that was something that we tried to make a concerted effort about as far as, yes we're not from here, we don't really know a whole lot of people, but we're going to try to involve ourselves in things [12:04]. You eat at a local restaurant, support a local business, and get your hair cut at the barbershop. Sign the kids up for sports, and just become a part of what's going on. Just let people know who you are.

Interviewer

[12:23]

How long have you been there now?

Respondent

Just seven years this month, yes sir.

Interviewer

Seven years and you went from ten to how many would you say you have now regularly attending?

Respondent

[12:34]

This past Sunday we had a hundred twenty...And that's been fairly consistent.

Interviewer

Alright, now let me ask you this question.

Respondent

Sure.

Interviewer

You said it had a Southern Baptist background but that previous pastor pulled them out of the Southern Baptist Convention. Is that what I understood?

Respondent

[12:54]

He was in a church that was Southern Baptist and the issue came up about the King James... And he did everything he could to get them to this side on the King James issue [13:10]. They decided against that and so he left.

Interviewer

Okay. He left that church?

Respondent

Yes. He left that church and started ..., fresh and new, as an independent work, [13:26] ...As not having any ties...

Interviewer

Okay, let me focus our attention just a moment. You mentioned this issue about the King James version. I've been an Independent Baptist all my life. My mom and dad started church when I was about five to six years old and I've been going to church ever since, but there are some deep-seated problems I think that I've witnessed/observed in the Independent Baptist movement over the years. I want to know how individual churches are dealing with those issues. The King James Version issue is one of them [14:25]. Part of the reason why I mention that is because you mentioned it but then the second reason I mention it is because I've had people leave our church (who were considering our church) because of my stand on the King James version. I am not aggressive. I don't beat people up over that issue. It is not something that I talk about regularly but one person thought I was a kook for taking that stand. I tried my best to present it reasonably. So what are you finding in that area? Are you having to deal with that issue or is that just a nonissue for you?

Respondent

[15:09]

I wouldn't say it has been a major issue in our ministry here but it has been a few times in our seven years here...And really how that has gone is we've had some people that have come in that have had either no church background or some type of nondenominational church background...that came in...that did not have an understanding of even the fact that there is a difference between the King James and other versions of the Bible [15:45]...And so some of that was approached from my mindset of sitting down with them and once we found out that that's what they were bringing to church with them, I did not make it a big issue as far as calling it out from the pulpit, along the same lines what you're saying. I'm not standing up and beating people up over it, especially if they have no idea.

Interviewer

[16:12]

Right.

Respondent

I mean really coming from a place of ignorance. And begin to pray about that....Ask the Lord to help them with those issues, and really came down to I was preaching from the King James and it finally dawned on them that, Hey what the pastors saying...the words he's reading from his Bible are not even in my Bible [16:35]...Or mean something completely different...And so they grew through those issues. Now we had a few people that have visited like you were saying, have shown interest, and just because of preaching through the Bible the way that we do have kind of figured out that this is not really necessarily a place for me. Because I'm not gonna hold to the King James issue. In a lot of places, it's become a major issue. You know battles have been fought and people have gotten upset. We have not necessarily faced it as a major issue [17:19] ...And I have not made that a major issue as far as, hey if you're here and you don't have a King James Bible, pass it to the center aisle so we can burn it...[17:31]. I've heard people say all that kind of stuff. We have not necessarily faced that as a major issue within our church...[17:41] Now, in our area, there are obviously plenty of other options as I'm sure there are in your area...If somebody wants a more watered-down version they don't have to go very far to find it.

Interviewer

[17:53]

That's right. Well, let me ask you this question since we're talking about some of these issues. I don't know how it is in your area but in our area, there are a lot of camp meeting mentality churches...camp meeting minded churches. Now what do I mean by that?

Respondent

I think I know what you mean.

Interviewer

[19:02]

Okay, would your church be considered a camp meeting church or would it not be? Or is it a hybrid, in between, something?

Respondent

[19:14]

I would like to think it's a good mix and I don't know if that's the right term... Maybe a hybrid would be what we are... We are in the foothills of ..., and there are both extremes. You could say there are some out there that (and I'll just say it because I said publicly) carry that idea/mentality that if you're not screaming at the absolute top of your lungs, you have no person of the Holy Spirit working in your life.

Interviewer

Right. Hyper emotionalism, basically.

Respondent

[19:55]

As far as you know on the other end... if a church mouse makes a peep... we can't have that going on either. I try to be somewhere in the middle with that issue as far as we want to follow the biblical precept, as far as letting all things be done decently in order. Now if something happens in the service and I feel it's the leading of the Lord and it's not on the schedule, then so be it. But, yes if things just need to go according to schedule and I believe that's right as well. The mentality we've tried to have here with our church is, I want it to be alive and exciting. I want the music, [20:40] not of the worldly sort, but I think it should have some excitement to it and be alive. I have no problem whatsoever if people say amen and raise their hands. We have that on a regular basis. I would say it this way. The guys that are camp-meeting in our area would not consider us to be camp-meeting.

Interviewer

[21:06]

Okay, okay. Yes, I understand. My idea about camp-meeting is three things: Number one, there is a hyper-emotionalism about the group. Number two, there seems to be an anti-education anti-intellectualism about the group. In fact, I just saw some information today about some individuals who were criticizing preachers who had gone to the cemetery (you probably heard that yourself). Instead of the seminary, they call it the cemetery. It's just a really anti-education atmosphere unless the education is by some little group that they approve of, and then there's a hyper-aggressive argumentative type of spirit in the midst of that. The reason I mention all of these is that you've got that on one side and it's saturating the southeast primarily, but then you've also got the contemporary religious experience on the other side, and mega-churches which usually grow out of that contemporary or emergent type church philosophy; and then you've got somebody like yourself who is trying to build a biblical New Testament church and you're surrounded by all of this stuff. How do you break through that stuff, or do you? Do you just live

your life, preach your message, visit your flock, and do the best you can letting God take care of the results? Do you even think about things like that, that I've just mentioned?

Respondent

[22:43]

Yes sir, and it's something that we try not to focus on but, in all reality, it's never too far from your mind [22:53]. Because there are so many churches in our area, And that's part of the problem. You can't get caught up in that one way or the other. One thing I've done, and this may be right or wrong, I don't know. I guess time will tell. But one thing I have done is I have gotten into particular preacher's fellowships or as we were saying a certain camp of type of ministries that are here in our area simply because there are some good men that I know and love and appreciate in the camp meeting. There are some good solid men I love and appreciate that are a little bit more reserved but still biblically correct [23:47]...And I love and appreciate all of them and I'm not necessarily going to choose sides one or the other...But those issues, you know, I don't know necessarily it's something I could change [23:59]...So we carry that mentality. Hey, look, my job here is to preach the word of God. Do right. Love the people. Reach our Jerusalem. Our prayer really has been here, Lord add them to the church as you would see fit [24:17]. And sometimes that's you know a long process...

Interviewer

Sure. One other issue I see that is creating difficulty is the issue of dress standards, and that's among others like entertainment. People are going to the movie theaters now. When I was a kid growing up that was like taboo. You know people are wanting to drink alcoholic beverage now. They're wanting to smoke cigarettes now... Of course, they've always wanted to smoke cigarettes and chew tobacco. But now these closet drinkers are coming out of the closet so to speak, and saying, Hey it's okay to drink a little wine... so the issue of standards but particularly that dress standard. That is one issue that I see. If a woman thinks that she has to wear dresses all the time and she's gonna be looked down on if she doesn't... I mean you've probably lost ninety percent of the people that walk through your door.....so what are you thinking on that and how have you managed that and does that create a problem in your area?

Respondent

[25:31]

It is the same as what you were saying with all of those issues, and I am sitting here in my house and you mentioned the smoking issue [25:41]. 10 minutes from my house is a town named ..., And we are north of ... the ... capitol of the world [25:51].

That's something that's always ongoing but the issue you mentioned about modesty in dress/standards... we've preached on that, we've taught on that...especially with our workers... especially with ministry-related things we try to get them to adhere to those standards and raise that bar as we can; and we preached on that and we've taught on it. It doesn't necessarily mean that it always works.

Interviewer

[26:26]

Right, do you do that on an ever-so-often basis or is that just like some you did when you first went there?

Respondent

When I preach, I preach through the books a lot. And so, as those passages of Scripture deal with different parts of the Bible, I mean obviously, when we preach through 1st and 2nd Timothy, it's right there, boom, verbatim. Here's what it is [26:54]. That's a little bit more pointed in that particular message. The principles of preaching through different chapters will apply. We'll mention it. We'll deal with it. We'll go on. What we have tried to do is set a good standard for ourselves personally and the people that we have that are visible [27:16]. You know our strong leaders. If he's going to be on the platform, he needs to be dressed appropriately...his wife. Our youth department as well, very much so... setting a good standard in front of our teenagers especially. I have not tried to make that a major issue [27:37]. It has come up. We have been questioned on it a few times... we've had that discussion. Sometimes it works out good... sometimes people grow. Sometimes they get mad... that's fine. But I think that that's something that we're going to continue to deal with [27:55] from here forward....

Interviewer

...Would you say that this would be an accurate reflection of what you've just said? If the leadership of the church is on the church property engaging in some form of service or ministry or even if the church is offsite, some membership is offsite, but it's a church-related function and activity then you would expect the women to dress modestly in a dress and you'd expect the man, of course, to dress modestly as well, but if they are not in relation to a church activity is just a family thing they're going to do, then, you know, whatever is kind of okay there you mean you're not going to be the fashion police in other words.

Respondent

[28:41] Yes Sir. Yes Sir. You're pretty much right on with that. We've had that discussion, especially with our leaders. If this is something we got going on as the church, we need to represent the Lord [28:54]. We need to represent who we are and of course there's church activities that we will have where people will know that, and still don't adhere to it [29:05]. And because of that you know there's some responsibility that can't be given to them but... Yeah, I have said that publicly... Hey, look. I'm not going to show up at your house and beat you up over what you're wearing. And the thing with me with that is that and maybe this is just my own personal mindset on it. And I've preached this, especially when we went through the books of 1st and 2nd Timothy. In that scripture, he doesn't mention you know...Exact specification [29:37] ...But he does mention shamefacedness this and sobriety, and that which becometh godliness. And if the heart is right, you won't have much trouble with the modesty issue [29:52]... Those things are in order....if there's sobriety, a right Holy Spirit-led mindset. If there's godliness if the heart is right...

Interviewer

[30:05]

Yeah. That's a good point.

Respondent

...they will adhere to what is a godly standard and if not, you'll have problems with it....that's kind of what we've done with that.

Interviewer

[30:16]

Good point. Well, thinking about preaching since we're mentioning preaching and teaching and such, are you the type of preacher that will mention specific sins... I mean even if those sins target your community, target people in your church, Or ...and I'm not talking about, you know, grinding an axe, you know, against somebody or anything like that. Or are you the type of preacher that you might mention abortion or you might mention homosexuality but it doesn't go much further than that?

Respondent

[30:51]

I would like to say there's a good balance there. There are times where we talk about some things in generalities because I don't feel that there's people in our church that are dealing with things. I probably would not scream and yell about homosexuality as much as some of the preachers because I don't know that there's anybody in my church dealing with homosexuality. I think we need to be against that, but I don't know necessarily that other than getting a hurrah, that's going to be spiritually [31:22] advantageous to my people.

Interviewer

Right.

Respondent

But as far as mentioning things specifically you know....living together without being married, [31:35] smoking, drinking, alcohol, those kind of things... I think I hit on smoking there a couple of minutes last night. Talking about the sanctity of a holy life and a pure heart [31:48]. And so we would...definitely mention some things specifically even if it is... but I guess some people would consider pointed.

Interviewer

[31:59]

Yes.

Respondent

And I think that's necessary sometimes.

Interviewer

Sure.

Respondent

Especially dealing with the flock.

Interviewer

I've noticed some in the bigger churches... Independent Baptist churches... that you hardly ever hear them say anything about specific sins or you hardly ever hear them mention anything about standards in terms of dress, entertainment, lifestyle, that kind of thing... so I'm just wondering if that's a key, so to speak. In other words, you're not riling people up over issues and you can grow your church bigger that way but the preachers that I've talked to so far... I talked to one preacher who had a church of about six hundred and now I'm talking to you and most of the churches [32:44] that I'm talking to and pastors that I know who have smaller churches, they will pointedly preach against sin. I mean they won't ask for a quarter and they won't give one. They will preach against sin and of course, you know most of the time people say well if you preach against sin you're not gonna have a very big congregation but I don't know necessarily that that's true. I'm just trying to feel my way through this because I've always been one that would be more specific in terms of preaching against sin and I've done differently. I mean I've been preaching for almost thirty-six years and I've went through stages, I guess you would say, or phases of preaching where I would be more pointed... I'd be less pointed... I would be more generic and [33:31] I'm just kind of curious... you know the people I'm talking to; I mean one guy, he told me he says oh absolutely he says I will nail it down he said if there's some sin that needs to be preached on, I will preach on it, and I will name it. Absolutely.

[33:57]...

[34:22]

Interviewer

Okay. I don't remember what I was talking about but I think I got an answer on that, but all right... let me, let me ask you this in, and of course I will give you the opportunity to talk about anything you want to talk about at some point but I wanted just to talk about this a little while. I'm finding you know in my younger days, my younger ministry, there was a lot of emphasis on soul-winning. There's a lot of emphasis on outreach. There is a lot of emphasis on trying to get people saved and now we're seeing such a scarcity of true conversions and salvation, you're almost hearing nothing from some of the smaller churches about personal evangelism in trying to win souls because even the souls that you win it seems like are stillborn and you can't get anything out of them. So what are you seeing in that area in your church and what are you doing in terms of evangelism and outreach?

Respondent

[35:22]

Sure, Yeah. It's definitely something that we don't see as much of as we would like for sure. It's still happening; in fact, we had a family that's been visiting with us this past month or so. And got four or five kids in the house. I noticed when I was giving the invitation on Sunday that the lady was speaking to one of the teenage boys and I kind of got the impression that maybe he was dealing with some things...they did not come forward but when they came back to the service that night, they said Hey preacher we need to talk to you for a second [35:59]. So I talked to them... when they had gotten home they had sat down and had that discussion with that teenage boy about his salvation, and was able to sit down with him take the Bible and open it up, and show him how to be saved as well as his younger brother [36:17]. That was a great blessing. Yeah, we've had, I wouldn't say several, but we definitely had some that have been saved in our services, in our jail ministry [36:28], in our junior church program as well this year so, the Lord's still, I think still definitely doing that. We have definitely made that an emphasis as far as trying to grow our church.

Interviewer

[36:41]

Right.

Respondent

Being regular to go out and hand out tracts and follow up on folks.

Interviewer

Do you...have a set time for visitation every week?

Respondent

[36:52]

Yes Sir. Yes Sir. We'll go out on a Saturday mornings. We have some men that are just faithful, just just real faithful in that. The Lord's used them. And our people have really kind of developed the mindset of, Hey look I might not be able to make it on Saturday but I'm going to talk to somebody you know, and I know our people some of them don't come on Saturday but I know that they spend time during the week talking to people they work with, their neighbors, family [37:22]. And we know that because people have showed up that they have invited and spoke to. So that's been something that we tried to do and again going back to what we said earlier in this area there are so many churches. You go out, you knock on somebody's door and say Hey we're from ... Baptist... just out inviting... Oh yeah well we go, you know, and its some uncle's cousins twice removed you know friends pastors there... whatever [37:49]. Also, we kind of joke on some of our visitation days that you know...we have no idea what we're doing. Everybody here is saved. We know that there are people out there that just put up a religious front and we don't see that as much as we'd like to but we have seen that and this last couple months we have seen some more that have been saved and the Lord's blessed in that area so I think if we're faithful...I think if we continue to fulfill the great commission, I believe

the lord blesses that and I believe when we tell other people about the Lord, the Lord tells people about our church.

Interviewer

[38:33]

Yes.

Respondent

It's amazing how the Lord has just brought people our way... added to the church, you know. We've had folks show up, and I say, do you know anybody around here? Somebody invite you? No, we just saw the sign...you know, drove by and thought we would stop. So the lord blesses that faithfulness I believe.

Interviewer

[38:56]

So looking at it from your seven-year perspective going from ten to you know just over a hundred what would you say has been the greatest reason or reasons for the growth that you've experienced?

Respondent

[39:13]

I'll give you a couple. I really do believe that I think I mentioned some of these at the church rescue workshop there a couple of weeks ago...but I believe...Prayer obviously and we should all understand that but prayer I believe has been a big key [39:29]. As far as our church has prayed for that. Our men's prayer room...Saturday morning visitation prayer time. We've done some special prayer times church-wide and I believe the praying of God's people for God to intervene has definitely seen God's blessings upon that.

Interviewer

[39:53]

Yes.

Respondent

I believe also that the Lord has given us good men in our church. When I say that, I'm not talking about a handful. I am talking about all throughout our church, of all different age brackets and stages of life. God's given us good faithful men...that I really truly believe love the Lord, love the family, and just are trying to do something to serve the Lord in some capacity. I believe that's went a long way for helping us to see that church growth... to see people mature because these men are fulfilling their role. Their families see that, you know, their extended family sees that. The people they work with see that it's important to them and I believe that's going a long way towards helping us.

Interviewer

[40:49]

Okay. That's good.

Respondent

Yes sir...and I do believe that the Lord's really really blessed us with good men.

Interviewer

Well. All right.... here's a scenario you've got a pastor somewhere and he's got a very very small church not very many men... maybe he just has a few ladies... a couple of older men and maybe a couple of children they bring in on Sunday morning for Sunday school but he's really got a vision. He wants to grow. He wants his church revitalized and renewed so....what would be your advice to this pastor for the best way that he could recruit workers? I know the Bible says pray ye the Lord of the harvest that He would send for laborers into his harvest but he's got little to nothing to offer. I mean he's got a little small church, really not a whole lot going on. How is this guy going to get workers in there? How is he going to inspire others to come and say let's join arms and work together to rebuild and revitalize this church?

Respondent

[41:49]

Yes Sir. What you said is true. I do believe that that's prayer. And that verse I do believe is true... pray for the laborers. Lord give us laborers.

Interviewer

[42:00]

Yes.

Respondent

I believe the Lord honors that. And again what we were talking about just a moment ago. The thing that we focused on...of course we were in an advantageous place where my wife and I...three kids... it's a younger family. It was easy for us to connect with other younger families that had kids the same age... going through the same stages of life but at the same time I would encourage that pastor to do what he could to build relationships and friendships. However, he needs to go about doing that in his community, his Jerusalem, with other men. And those families may never come to your church, but they may tell somebody else about your church that they may come.

Interviewer

[42:51]

Yeah.

Respondent

And that I think that is important as far as finding something that identifies your community for who it is.

Interviewer

[43:05]

Right.

Respondent

And I think we talked about this at the church rescue workshop. The old cars and car shows and that kind of thing and the high school sports are two of the major things that make our town go around. And hey, we show up at the car show, you know. We show up at the ballfields... just meet people and build those relationships and you know you plant the seed... God waters... God gives the increase. So I would encourage you...you know just stay faithful at it [43:42]. Work at building relationships, especially with other men...cause you need those men to take those places and roles of leadership and you know just be mindful of that and train. Boy... that's something, I'll be honest with you, I'm not the best at. I love to teach. But administrative things and organizational...that kind of stuff...I'm not a very good administrator. I love to preach and I'd preach all day if they'd let me [44:16]. Yeah, but, you know...some of those other areas as far as organization are not my strong suit. And I've literally tried to find other people that I could build a relationship with that that is their strength. And surround yourself with those kinds of people that can help you...not necessarily they have to do it for you [44:39] but that can help you to stay focused, stay organized, and do what needs doing that takes a lot of training sometimes. And you know, sometimes, you just gotta work with what you got. And when we came, we had no Sunday school classes other than the older senior adult class. And so we just [45:04] started...you know, you can't start a Sunday School class with no kids...But we took the mindset of literally approaching other families and saying, Hey look somebody's got to be the first.

Interviewer

[45:18]

Yeah.

Respondent

Everybody wants to be first in line. Everybody wants to be first at the bank. Everybody wants to be first in the line at Walmart. We need somebody to be first....the first family the first kids in a Sunday School class. And so when the lord opens that door and gives somebody, that does go a long way.

Interviewer

[45:40]

Yeah. Now, have you been full-time at your church ever since you went?

Respondent

Yes Sir. I've been fortunate enough...the Lord blessed us. When we left ... in [45:53] ... we were working at the Christian school they gave us a salary and you know paid insurance, all that kind of thing. I worked evenings, summertime, once school was out. We left... we came... we did so totally and completely by faith. Bro. ..., my father-in-law sat down... He wrote out a letter to several pastor friends of his that he knew. And just said Hey you know pray for Bro... This is what the Lord is doing in his life. He's going here... here's what the situation is [46:31]. The Lord saw fit to put upon some of those pastor's hearts to support us, some for six months.....some for a year.

Interviewer

[46:42]

Yeah.

Respondent

And so we just packed up and came...A lot of people would say that that was not the smartest move I ever made... We never went hungry.

Interviewer

[46:56]

Yes.

Respondent

And the lord provided and I tell you...It helped me to grow in my faith. Apart from all of our family... probably more than about anything I've done.... just taking that step of faith, and saying Lord, I have no idea how I am going to pay the electric bill next week but here we are. This is what you want us to do, and the Lord provided in those first couple years through some different folks and through some of those churches. And the church did what they could [47:35].

When we saw some people growing, the church saw fit to help us and they have they have done so... Wonderfully and sacrificially to help us be here.

Interviewer

[47:49]

Yes. That's good.

Respondent

Again, I had a couple of good men that were older in the faith...knew what it was all about, and when it came to those times they got up and said some things like, Hey, if we take care of the man of God, God will take care of us [48:05]. They were gracious enough to continue to increase us to a place that we are truly blessed.

Interviewer

Let me get let me give you this scenario and I don't know how long you have...but you and I can probably talk all day and all night too. Here's a scenario for you. Let's say you've got a pastor who comes into a restart...this church completely shut down and then it reopened under a different name and had a bad name in the community, the church did so for various reasons. And this pastor comes in, and he comes in from the business world. He has never pastored before. He's called to preach now and he wants to pastor and he comes into this setting and he actually raises support. He's got this mind...a business mind... and he raises support so that he can be full-time at this church because he knows the value of that. All right so he raises support, and churches support this gentleman let's say for about three years.... All right, so he is supported fully for about three to four years...not a lot, you know, compared to what the guy could make in the outside world, so to speak, but by the time that three to four years runs out [49:36], he discovers that his church is not able or capable of supporting him still after three to four years.

Respondent

[49:46]

Yes Sir.

Interviewer

So you know he's got a big decision to make there. Does he leave? Does he get a call to another church? Does he stay and just duke it out you know and fight his way through it? I mean what would you tell a fella; I mean, do you think it's wise number one, to be full-time if you're going to do church revitalization work or what do you think about the value of being Bivocational... the dangers the drawbacks of Bivocational...and should the Bivocational be seeking to go full time so that he can give himself to the work of prayer and the ministry of the Word? So I guess I'm just kind of looking in this area of money right now and finances because that is a huge hindrance if you cannot be full-time it is a huge blockade. So what are your thoughts on that?

Respondent

[50:41]

That's, that's good. It's a lot of different variables. We just finished revival, I believe, last Wednesday and Thursday and that's part of the reason we couldn't do it (this interview) last week; but that pastor is in that situation. He was full time as a pastor at the church he was at... took this other church, believed it to be the lord's will (which I believe it is) and he told me he said my five-year plan was to come here, work five years, grow the church, and then be full-time. And, he said we're on year six and a half and it hasn't worked out that way. And so I could see just in his countenance the way that he was talking about it, you could see the burden and desire of his heart to be full time and you know talked about that. And my heart really went out to him and even some of the men in his church [51:43] came to me and said you know preacher tell us about how you did this, and how you are full-time and basically asked me the same question you just did. You know, how did you do that? Were you full-time the whole time you were there? So we had that discussion and just tried to help them to see his heart and I know

they know that [52:06] and it's it's one of those difficult things that in a place of leadership, you can't necessarily fully express that like Hey, you know, you people ought to be paying me so I can do the work God has called me to. You can't get up and say that but at the same time seeing that burden in his heart, Knowing his desire to be full-time, and going through what you're just talking about... not being able to give the full one hundred percent effort in some of those areas that you could, because you are putting time in at a job; you know my advice would be you know if you're able to do that... God opens that door, obviously, you need to take it. The scenario that you brought up about, you know, the man is there, he's been there, his supports about to end and the church is not able to fully support him...that's a difficult situation.

Interviewer

[53:01]

Yeah.

Respondent

My advice would be, it really comes down to if you're in the place that God wants you to be; you're doing what God wants you to do. He's going to take care of that one way or the other. Either He's going to open the door for you to get a job and be able to continue there, or, you know, a step of faith by the church... that may be what needs to be happening [53:22]. So that's something that really in my mind at least comes down to, if this is where God wants me to be, he'll sustain us... he'll provide all our needs [53:34]. And you know, maybe this was the training ground for me to go on to something else. Somebody else can take them to the next level...and that would come down to knowing God's will for your life. But that is a difficult position. It is hard, I mean, it's hard to do the work of the ministry in a manner that is, I would say, to the most potential, the most effective [54:01], and still have to put in forty, fifty hours at a job. That's very difficult. I don't know if there's a set solution to that [54:14]. We'd like to think as pastors that you know people would want to take us on full-time and do what they could as a church to do so.

Interviewer

Right.

Respondent

[54:25]

You brought up kind of another scenario there as far as perhaps somebody that is willing to help other ministries, you know, be revitalized and rescued and that would really come down to how you approach that ministry about going to work to be able to do those things or am I going to approach this from kind of a full-time missionary aspect where this will be my ministry and churches can help support this on a long term basis to be able to do that and then not have that church have the financial burden of taking care of us while we're helping them [55:06]. And that's something you know that probably isn't explored as much as it probably should be in our mission's mindset. And I believe [55:23]. If We're going to see our country back to what God wants it to be I think that we as American churches, and as Independent Baptists, are going to have to see the growth of church planting from our ministries [55:37] like we've not seen in a

long time. And I made mention of that when we were praying in one of our prayer groups last night, one of our men's prayer groups for our country specifically. And made mentioned that in our prayer time as far as sometimes we get caught up so much in building the kingdom that we forget to spread the kingdom [56:02]. We forget to spread the kingdom and that's something that we, I think, as Independent Baptists really struggle with. My father-in-law, the way he preached for a long time, did a very in-depth study and brought out some good things about the difference in scripture between a king and a shepherd.

Interviewer

[56:25]

Right.

Respondent

And we've kind of got away from that I'm afraid as pastors and I'll talk about our Independent Fundamental Baptists, from being the shepherd and trying to be CEO.

Interviewer

[56:39]

Right.

Respondent

And that's hindered us a lot starting churches in our Samaria and to the uttermost parts of the earth.

Interviewer

[56:50]

Mmhm. Alright, very good. What do you think the metrics are whereby we can measure what a healthy New Testament church is? I mean I know you know the first thing out of most of their mouths is well you can't look at the numbers. Okay, Well. Can you look at the numbers? What is a healthy New Testament church in your mind? How would you identify it if somebody came to you and said Hey is my church healthy? What would be going through your mind about what a healthy church is?

Respondent

[57:22]

In my mind that would go directly to what's coming from the pulpit. If the preaching is Biblical...it is Spirit-led [57:32]. If it is filled with the power of God, you're on the right track and I think that has to be a foundational point that you start with.

Interviewer

[57:42]

Right.

Respondent

Now the results of that may vary depending upon the ebbs and flows of ministry and I've heard the arguments for and against numbers my whole life you know. But I try not to get focused on numbers but at the same time numbers are people [58:01], and people are our ministry. Obviously, we have to honor God. We have to do what the Bible says first and foremost regardless of what else happens, but you do have the promises of God that if we do things biblically there are gonna be some spiritual fruits there. There should be some spiritual marks of God's people that show that we're doing things in a right and biblical way. And so I think you start with preaching. I think you start with where the people are there. Are they growing?

Interviewer

[58:35]

Yes.

Respondent

Are they being fed spiritually? Are they advancing in their personal relationship with God? And the marks of the New Testament church were, they preached right. They prayed right. They lived right. And they did everything they could to reach their Jerusalem and to the uttermost parts of the earth. And that to me, in my mind, is what God's called us to do. Preach the Word, and feed the flock of God. You know. Trust God by faith. Prayer and the results are up to God. Now it sure is good sometimes to see some of those things in the physical manifestation.

Interviewer

[59:16]

Yes.

Respondent

We all, as pastors, get done preaching and wonder, well why didn't nobody come forward? So it's good to see those things in and I've said this to other preachers as well but, and it may sound kind of funny. But obviously, when somebody gets saved it's an absolute miracle of God. There's rejoicing in heaven and boy O boy, that'll help you out. But my favorite part or what I guess I get the most satisfaction out of from my ministry as a pastor is when I see people growing in their spiritual life. I see them make decisions that are biblical I see them raising the bar of their service to God or their separation from the world or show some marked improvement in their life. Maybe it's an attitude. Maybe it's, you know, something that's changed in their relationship as husband and wife or between them and their children [01:00:18]. That, to me, is the most satisfying part of what we do as far as being a pastor, preaching the word of God. When you see somebody grasp it and then put it into real life, it's like, oh yes, yes they got it, and that that really helps me along to see.. to see people grow. Yes Sir.

Interviewer

[01:00:41]

Yes Sir. So this is the first church that you pastored?

Respondent

Yes Sir. Still just a newborn in this pastoral ministry.

Interviewer

[01:00:52]

Okay. That's great. Let me ask you one more question.

Respondent

Yes sir.

Interviewer

And this has to do with the authority and the government of the local church. You know, down through the years I have observed that a lot of problems develop in and around improper government of the church. Now, I don't know if I can adequately describe it, but, I will try. What I mean by that... I mean, I know that most Independent Baptist churches believe in congregational government. They believe in pastoral leadership... a pastor-led, congregation approved. Well, I think what my question involves is not so much that but I'm talking about on a week-by-week, a month-by-month, a year-by-year fleshing out of that leadership... not that leadership, but that governmental style. How does that look within a church, because a lot of problems develop when something is not handled right and when something is not managed well. So, do you all have monthly business meetings like a lot of traditional churches do?

[01:02:15] How do you deal with interpersonal conflicts and issues of that nature? Does that help a little bit does it give a little guidance as to what I'm looking at?

Respondent

[01:02:26]

Yes Sir. I do think I know what you are getting at there. We do our financial part of it as far as we do quarterly business meetings. We hand out a financial report to all the members. We have a regular business meeting at that time. We'll go over that and then we'll discuss as a congregation anything that needs to be done or has come up. If there's some type of emergency, our bylaws/constitution gives the ability to call an emergency meeting for some reason. If not, it's a quarterly thing. Or if something comes up you know if our heating and air system you know goes haywire.[01:03:11] We're gonna have to fix it... spend three or four thousand dollars... we'll call them together and vote on it. So that's kind of how we do that. I've tried to always keep the idea that it's an open-door policy. You know, there's nothing that goes on that's secretive as far as the financial part of it. You know there's been some questions. I'll be honest with you. Earlier this year we kind of ran into a little bit of an issue where some people had questions about some of the things that the money was being spent on [01:03:45]. It came down to there was a misunderstanding of what had been approved, you know, by the church previously for the money to be spent. They didn't understand all that and it kind of got made into an issue, because, like, what you were saying, we didn't go about the proper channels of communication and leadership and authority. And you know how it is. Everybody would rather talk to each other than talk to the

pastor. I don't know if that's an issue for you...[01:04:18] but it is for me. Boy, Oh Boy, it really gets under my skin.

Interviewer

And that needs to be... I think that needs to be taught. I think that church membership need to understand proper church government and functioning, and how to interact one with another. because I don't think sometimes they have a clue.

Respondent

[01:04:40]

Yes Sir. You are correct. You are correct, and for whatever reason, you know, and I've even had some of our men come and say, Well preacher, you know, people are just kind of nervous about talking to you. I was like, I would like to think I'm a pretty nice guy [01:04:58]. I try to be laid back...not get upset over things. And, boy, it's a whole lot easier to deal with something when somebody comes to you...If upfront honest, then it is to try to, you know, put all the puzzle pieces together and try to do it that way. So what we ended up doing was we had a business meeting coming up. And so before that business meeting happened, I said all right, all the men of the church, we're going to get together, and have a Saturday night prayer meeting and discuss a few things. And so we got all the men together that could, we sat down, I said all right, you know, it's come to my attention there's a little bit of a misunderstanding. We have a problem going on. Here's your chance to say something because I'm not going to go into the business meeting and get blindsided by something that everybody's been talking about privately [01:05:52]. And so I gave them an opportunity to discuss a few things and you know got some things ironed out and really in that meeting went over...the biblical mandate. We have a problem. You know we follow the biblical mandate. Jesus said in Matthew eighteen you go that brother, you know, and you deal with it [01:06:20]. You just have to continue teaching those things...training, and reviewing reminding, and reminding them that it all works out the way it's supposed to.

Interviewer

[01:06:35]

Right. Is your ministry fairly typical in terms of like Sunday, Sunday night, Wednesday night, you got a visitation on Saturday mornings and that's about it, or do you have small groups that are going on throughout the week, you know, ministering to people? I understand you said something about nursing home and jail but I'm not really talking about that.

Respondent

[01:06:56]

Sure. We are just pretty much a typical, you know, Sunday mornings, Sunday School, Sunday morning service, Sunday night, Wednesday night. You know, we have Sunday school classes for all of our young people. We have a junior church program. We don't really have any type of in-home Bible study or small group thing going on. We try to fellowship on a pretty regular basis....especially when we get new people to come around we try to do a couple church wide

type things. We try to do some Sunday school class fellowships and activities that give people a chance to get to know one another but we do have the jail ministry. We do have two nursing homes they go to [01:07:46]. So that's kind of the outreach. But as far as small groups, we don't have any of that going on. And I don't know, I guess, I don't know... maybe it's because I'm not really all that familiar with that type of thing [01:08:05]. Some of it is kind of a trepidation on my part as far as what's going on there.

Interviewer

Yes.

Respondent

Who is in charge of it? What are they talking about? I don't have any control over those kind of meetings.

Interviewer

[01:08:18]

Mmhm.

Respondent

And it's not necessarily that I have to have control over it as much as... I just want to be well informed about what's going on there. The only thing. The only thing that would even be remotely close to that is when we were there at the church rescue workshop thing. One of the sessions that Preacher Baker was talking about [01:08:47]. He made a statement there, and he said, people have a psychological need for variety. And boy, I was like, man oh man. There's some wisdom in that, and knowing Preacher Baker the way that I do, and boy he's been a great help and encouragement here in our area to me especially, but, [01:09:06] I know his mindset there is not changing what we do but every once in a while it's good to kind of just refresh maybe how we do that. And so one thing I've done is our Wednesday night prayer time. I've changed that a little bit and instead of just having an open time where it was, you know, pray for my cat, she's got a hairball, you know, all that kind of stuff. I said here's what we're gonna do we're gonna break up into three groups for the men, and we are gonna have the ladies pair off and [01:09:46] class number one, you're going to pray for our church. You'll pray specifically for God's blessings in our church... souls to be saved, you know, laborers. You're gonna pray for the church. Group two, you are going to pray for all of our missionaries. You're gonna go through them specifically by name. And really I want to pray for their wives and their children and their particular fields. And then group three, I want to pray for our country, and we got one man, in particular, he keeps up with all the stuff that's going on [01:10:21]...State level up, you know. Local level and a lot of things going on nationally. He's brought up some stuff, you know, even I was not aware of and hey, we're going to pray for our country from now till this time next year [01:10:37]. And so we've done that. It seems like our people enjoy that. Our ladies have paired off and said, you know, basically what I said to them is, hey, you are here in the auditorium. I want you to find a lady to pray with. Next week I want to find a different one, you know, none of this buddy buddy standing around talking about what the kids did at school, you know. Get to

know some of these...share prayer requests with each other. Spend time in prayer for our families specifically and so that that would be the only thing that would even be remotely close to [01:11:11]. Not any type of small group...In-home...Baptizing in a swimming pool...kind of a deal.

Interviewer

Yes. Do you engage technology much? Are you on Facebook, Instagram, got a website and all that stuff?

Respondent

[01:11:30]

We have a church website. It's been under construction. We've had a couple of guys in the church help us out with that. It's not all that advanced. It's got time and information, and things on that. We utilize our Facebook page. We live stream our services on there. That way you can always provide for folks that you know traveling, sick, whatever. Some of our missionaries have the chance to tune in.

Interviewer

[01:11:58]

Do you find that brings in visitors? Does it seem to be a good promotional type thing for the church?

Respondent

[01:12:10]

It's a good...I'll say this. It is a good way for us as a church to communicate. We've had some folks then that know who we are, that have tuned into the services. We've had a few people that have, you know, come across the website or our Facebook page... have found it, have visited. So that's been beneficial to us in a couple of instances [01:12:40], but I wouldn't say it's an overwhelming influence in what we do.

Interviewer

All righty. Well, I think I will have to let you go I've got another appointment at six pm but, if... do you have anything else that you've just been busting to say or tell me? Or have I covered most of the bases of things you thought?

Respondent

[01:13:03]

Yeah, yeah. I mean that was basically what I was going to, you know, try to get at with you that's pretty much what I had said there at the workshop you know.

Interviewer

Yes.

Respondent

Just preach the word, and pray. Be involved in your community. You know get out there. Don't be afraid to make yourself visible and all that kind of stuff and just love the Lord, and love those people that God's called you to. And do what has to be done according to the Bible, and just enjoy it.

Interviewer

[01:13:35]

Absolutely. Absolutely.

Respondent

Yes Sir.

Interviewer

If I had a need to perhaps reach out to you again would that be all right?

Respondent

Yeah, yeah, yeah, anytime, brother.

Interviewer

Okay.

Respondent

Yeah, if something else hits you later on, and you say, Oh, I didn't ask you about that... you call and we'll be glad to help you out.

Interviewer

[01:13:52]

So you know I may be here until I die or until Jesus comes; You know either one of those things could happen today. So you know I may be here long term and I may not. I don't have any intention of leaving but you know if God calls and I have the opportunity and I do have some dreams that I feel like I'd like to fulfill that God's placed in my heart. But I want to be wise, you know, and not make mistakes at this stage in my life, so just say a prayer for me.

Respondent

[01:15:01]

We sure will. We sure will and if you get to a place especially where you're trying to do something along those lines...on a scale of traveling and helping other churches you make sure you call me.

Interviewer

[01:15:16]

Yes.

Respondent

And I'll do what I can to help you for sure.

Interviewer

Absolutely, absolutely. I appreciate that very much thank you.

Respondent

Yes Sir. Yes Sir. Because I know I know when we came here you know that's.... I'll be honest with you. When we showed up for that workshop and boy they called me to stand up there.... I looked out at that crowd... I thought to myself, that's a big crowd of people....

Interviewer

[01:15:39]

Yes.

Respondent

.....Surely not this many churches that are in our area are struggling. And, boy, it just kind of hit home, as far as like, man, you know, I guess maybe coming in here and not really knowing a lot of other places... you feel kind of isolated. I guess as far as well, you know, our church is the exception to the rule. Everybody else is doing alright. Has got a crowd. You get up there in something like that and you find out...Hey, wait a second. There are people all over....

Interviewer

[01:16:10]

Yeah.

Respondent

Especially our area of the world...that boy they're going through hard things.

Interviewer

Yes.

Respondent

They need somebody to come and help them... so yes that definitely hit home sure

Interviewer

[01:16:23]

Churches are struggling everywhere. They really are. I mean over seven thousand closes every year. Now that's that's a statistic that's kind of come and gone and you know went up and went

down. I think I said seven thousand. I didn't mean seven thousand. Let me see if I remember correctly. Four thousand, if I'm not mistaken, churches close every year, now and that's taking into consideration churches that are opening. You know you've got new start churches and you take all of it together and if I'm not mistaken it's four thousand churches that are closing every year and those that are not closing I think it's like sixty.

[01:17:07]

Percent... it used to be eighty percent... but they've done some new statistics and I think it's more in the higher sixties now, churches have plateaued or are in decline. I mean the majority of churches you know I have what they call plateaued or declined and when you think about... I just collected this statistic ...if you have a minute, let me read this statistic to you. This is a two thousand eighteen world view result I think that Pew put it out... the research company... It says the two thousand eighteen data revealed that the proportion of adults who have a biblical worldview dropped from ten percent in 2016 thousand sixteen nine percent in 2011 thousand seventeen and seven percent in two thousand eighteen.

[01:17:53]

And then it goes on and says... among the demographic correlations noted by Barna, Oh, it was Barna and not Pew, were the following adults under the age of thirty-five are just half as likely as older adults to have a biblical worldview. Among millennials, four percent have one, compared to eight percent among Gen X'ers, nine percent among baby boomers, and nine percent among elders. In total, just ten percent of adults in America who identify themselves as Christians have a biblical worldview among people whose beliefs about salvation qualify them as being born-again Christians less than one out of every four or twenty-three percent have a biblical worldview. And the reason I posted that to Twitter is because.

[01:18:45]

We're seeing a whole lot of emphasis right now among Independent Baptists about evangelism about revival about you know winning the country, you know, to God, and this kind of thing but part of the reason why we're in the problem that we are in right now is that we so over-emphasized evangelism and revival that we didn't teach our people how to stand. We didn't teach our people how to discern truth from error. We didn't teach our people the core doctrines and tenets of the faith, so my idea is, Yes, let's emphasize revival, and evangelism but let's make sure that we are teaching our people because if you remember in the great commission Matthew check number twenty-eight to times it mentions teaching.

[01:19:29]

So if we've got this superficial camp meeting mentality that does not emphasize and maybe even de-emphasizes teaching, then we're headed for another problem even worse down the road because our culture has imploded. I mean secular culture has just imploded. And Christian culture is, you know, imploding as well. But, I think it's so important that we teach because we are in a very very difficult place in this country and whoever we have that God's put within the

sound of our voice, they need to be taught the word of God. They need to be taught what to believe, why to believe, and what to do with what they believe. I think that's so key.

Respondent

[01:20:16]

Sure.

Interviewer

Absolutely.

Respondent

I was very, very surprised when we came here. I mean, here we are....

Interviewer

[01:20:29]

Yes.

Respondent

Man, there are churches everywhere.

Interviewer

Yes.

Respondent

And I would get up and then preach a chapter of the Bible. We've preached through Nehemiah...you know just several books. People would come up and say, Preacher, Where did you get that? I've never heard anything like that in my life.

Interviewer

[01:20:47]

The ignorance is appalling and I'm not saying that in an ugly way... the ignorance is appalling.

Respondent

Yes, and I thought to myself, you've been in church for thirty years. What do you mean you've never heard.....It's right there black and white right?

Interviewer

[01:21:01]

Yes.

Respondent

What have you heard? It really just set home, Hey look these people have been sitting on a pew. They've heard a lot of things, but haven't heard a whole lot of the Bible. And it's been amazing.

Interviewer

[01:21:19]

Yes well, I'm proud of you, and what you're doing up there and I pray the Lord continues to bless you and just tell your church to go forward. My wife just walked in too.....she's waving at ya.

Respondent

[01:21:33]

Yes, very nice.

Interviewer

So anyway. Oh, she was waving at me.... I'm sorry.

Respondent

A big thank you to the Mrs. for being a good faithful pastor's wife.

Interviewer

[01:21:45]

I would definitely say that... I would definitely say that....and that's key too by the way. Family strength, and cohesiveness when you're trying to revitalize. If your family falters or struggles you... you're [01:21:57] in trouble....Have your family stayed strong or have you had to take proactive measures to help them or has it always been easy sailing for you?

Respondent

Lord's been good to us. You know we were, we were a little bit nervous I guess you could say when we left Kentucky because our kids had been born there. They had Grandma and Grandpa there. They had aunts and uncles, and cousins there. And we took them from all of that to them being by themselves.

Interviewer

[01:22:30]

Yes.

Respondent

Home-schooled obviously.

Interviewer

Yes.

Respondent

They didn't have anybody at the church. So the good part about all that was that we got to spend some good time together as a family those first three, four, five years really and we still do. We went from I mean honestly... we went from doing something at the church seven days a week to Hey, what are we gonna do today [01:23:00]? We visited all five people yesterday. So let's do

something together as a family. That was part of I think why the Lord did what he did at that time in our life. And I remember my wife and I having that conversation you know as far as our kids are growing up I don't remember a whole lot of it. In some of those younger years, we were so busy raising everybody else's kids in the teen group. The Lord gave us that opportunity to build those strong family relationships and I tell you, our kids have done really well. They love being here [01:23:36]. We go back to visit family now, you know, two or three days later they come by and say, Dad, whenever you want to go back to ..., that's fine with me.

Interviewer

Okay. That's great, that's perfect. All right my friend, listen, I appreciate it and hopefully you and I can talk again sometime maybe develop, you know, a greater relationship in days to come.

Respondent

[01:24:17]

Yes, Sir, that sounds like a good thing. Yes Sir.

Interviewer

Have a great evening okay?

Respondent

You're welcome, my friend. You too. God bless you.

[01:24:22]

Appendix L: Adapted Church Health Inventory, Midwestern Church

ID	LP 1 Then - 1998	LP 1 Now - 2022	FSM 1 Then - 2008	FSM 1 Now - 2022	FSM 2 Then - 2013	FSM 2 Now - 2022
FELLOWSHIP						
We have several cliques.	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree
It is difficult to join existing groups.	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Disagree
Priority should be meeting members' needs.	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree
People are willing to start new groups.	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Church was recently involved in member conflict.	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
People in church are angry with others.	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Undecided	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
There is unresolved conflict in church.	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
People in church enjoy being together.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree

FELLOWSHIP						
I have fellowship regularly with members.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
New members are quickly invited to groups.	Undecided	Undecided	Disagree	Agree	Strongly disagree	Agree
Church is unified.	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree		
I enjoy the fellowship of other members.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
My voice is heard.	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree
Pastor, church staff, and people have healthy relationships.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
Open unrepentant sin is dealt with quickly.	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree
I am a part of a group that reaches others.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I am excited to be a part of this church.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
It has become increasingly difficult to come to church.	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Disagree

FELLOWSHIP						
Church is seen as very unified.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Our church has a good reputation.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
I feel like I belong.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Visitors sometimes feel unwelcome.	Undecided	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Church people are more interested in themselves than in reaching out.	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree
Fellowship encourages people to live faithfully.	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I was quickly accepted when I began at this church.	Undecided	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
EVANGELISM						
People share faith regularly.	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Church supports missionaries.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
People seek out ways to reach others.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree

EVANGELISM						
Visitors feel welcome.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Small groups seek to reach people.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Church emphasizes church planting.	Strongly disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
I have fears that keep me from sharing my faith.	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Agree
Church hosts regular opportunities to do foreign missions.	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Church has a known plan for outreach.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Church meets members' needs before others.	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Strongly Disagree
A church should not start a new church without surplus funds.	Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Strongly Disagree
Only people with the gift of evangelism should evangelize.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly disagree	Strongly Disagree	Undecided	Strongly Disagree
I attempt to establish relationships with the unchurched.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Agree

EVANGELISM						
Church has regular opportunities for evangelism training.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
I have a few relationships with unbelievers.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
People accept Christ on a regular basis.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
A lifetime missionary must be called.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
One purpose of small groups is evangelism.	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
A portion of the budget is allocated for mission work.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
I make efforts to introduce myself to new people.	Agree	Agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I share my faith regularly with lost people.	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
My pastor models personal evangelism.	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
More personal evangelism comes from more training.	Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Agree

EVANGELISM						
There are enough churches in our community.	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Church is growing more by transfer of membership.	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
DISCIPLESHIP						
I am involved in regular Bible study.	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
I am growing in maturity as a Christian.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
Most attendees have regular Bible study.	Disagree	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Undecided	Agree
Christians are discipled after conversion.	Disagree	Agree	Undecided	Agree	Undecided	Agree
Children have opportunities to grow in maturity.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
Knowledge of the Bible is rated as high in our church.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Small groups are strong in Bible study.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Members were lost within a few months.	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree

DISCIPLESHIP						
Church seems to lose more people than it gains.	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Commitment level of the majority is low.	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
People in the church understand the church's doctrine.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
New members receive training and information when they join.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
Our church does a very good job discipling.	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
We have many people involved in one-on-one discipling.	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree
I have grown as a Christian since being at this church.	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
People are given training on how to develop a prayer life and quiet time.	Disagree	Agree	Undecided	Agree	Disagree	Disagree
People are given opportunities to learn how to share/defend their faith.	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree

DISCIPLESHIP						
Members' lifestyles are different from the world's.	Agree	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
I know what I believe and why I believe it.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Mature Christians have a desire to help the less mature.	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree
Someone personally disciplined me.	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided
I feel prepared to disciple a new believer.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided
Believers are trained to give financially.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
People are trained how to read and interpret the Bible.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
Discipleship classes are usually boring or irrelevant.	Undecided	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Undecided
PRAYER						
Intercessory prayer ministry includes many participants.	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Leadership regularly emphasizes prayer.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree

PRAYER						
Thirty to sixty minutes a day for prayer is nearly impossible.	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
Major efforts are first bathed in prayer.	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Prayers for non-Christians are by name.	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Prayer is central in our services.	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Church has special prayer emphases.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Prayer needs are made available.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Prayer is integral in classes or small groups.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Church regularly prays for world missions.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Church regularly prays for its ministries.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Prayer during services is vital.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree

PRAYER						
There is regular prayer for leadership.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Prayer meetings are boring.	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree
Prayer meetings = gossip times.	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Undecided
When we pray nothing happens.	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Prayer room/place where people pray.	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Undecided
Prayer should be a daily part of a Christian's life.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
I pray regularly during the day.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Answered prayers are communicated to the church.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
I believe that prayer works.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
I feel adequately trained in prayer.	Undecided	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided

PRAYER						
I pray regularly for missionaries.	Agree	Strongly agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided
I pray regularly for non-believers.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided
Church is so busy that we pray too little.	Undecided	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
MINISTRY						
A good youth ministry.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Agree
A good music ministry.	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Agree
A good preschool or children's ministry.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Successfully ministering to different ages of adults.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
When there is a need, many respond.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Pastor (and staff) should do most of the ministry.	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree
I am regularly involved in doing ministry.	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided

MINISTRY						
Most members know their spiritual gifts.	Disagree	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided
Most members use their spiritual gifts.	Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Undecided	Disagree	Agree
Many people in our church volunteer when needed.	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
Getting involved in ministry in our church is difficult for me.	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Getting involved in ministry in our church is difficult for newcomers.	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Ministry in church is done by a small group.	Agree	Disagree	Undecided	Disagree	Agree	Disagree
I have creative freedom in ministry.	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree
I receive fulfillment by doing ministry in our church.	Undecided	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
The leadership equips people to do ministry.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree

MINISTRY						
The church is strong in benevolence ministry.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Ministry is an avenue of outreach in our church.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Ethnic background is not a factor in ministry.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
When counseling is needed people have options.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
I am willing to serve in the church.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Pastor challenges us to get involved.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Clearly defined strategy for ministering to sick/bereaved.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree
Tired in ministry due to responsibility.	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
My church will minister to me if in need.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I worship God at services.	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree

MINISTRY						
Pastor's sermons are informative.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
Music used leads me to worship.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
The Pastor's sermons are mostly topical.	WORSHIP	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree
The Pastor's sermons are mostly expositional (verse by verse / book by book).	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Pastor's sermons are mostly textual.	Undecided	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree
Disagreement exists about type of music/worship style.	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Undecided	Undecided
Sermons are relevant.	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
The church has a good way of greeting guests.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
A blend of music/worship styles is agreeable.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided

WORSHIP						
The church has traditional worship.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
Service time is just right.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Sermon length is just right.	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Facility in which to worship is good.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
People have trouble finding parking spaces.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree
Order of worship is liked.	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
Services are prayerful.	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
There is good participation in singing.	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Non-Christians are comfortable in our services.	Disagree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
I like all the elements of our worship services.	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree

DOCTRINE						
The Bible is perfect as it was originally written.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
God intervenes in the lives of Christians.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Christ alone is the only way to Heaven.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Fellowship with God is only through the shed blood of Jesus Christ.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
God is a trinity.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
A good person of another faith other than Christianity may go to heaven.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Hell is a literal place.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
God is in total control of our world.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Jesus is the Son of God.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree

UNIQUE						
KJV is used in ministry.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Strongly Agree
Lady church workers are required to wear dresses/skirts at church/events.	Undecided	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Disagree
There is solo Pastor leadership.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Church discipline is handled well.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Preaching includes topics on Biblical standards and separation.	Undecided	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
Regular business meetings are held.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
DESCRIPTORS						
Roles	Senior Pastor	Senior Pastor	Associate Pastor	Associate Pastor	Associate Pastor	Associate Pastor
Setting	Suburban	Suburban	Suburban	Suburban	Suburban	Suburban
Dates	1998	2022	2008	2022	2012	2022

Geography	Midwest	Midwest	Midwest	Midwest	Midwest	Midwest
Congregation Size	150	650	350	650	350	650

Appendix M: Church Health Inventory, Southern Church

ID	LP 2 Then* - 2012	LP 2 Now - 2022	RSM 1 Then - 2015	RSM 1 Now - 2022	RSM 2 Then - 2015	RSM 2 Now - 2022
FELLOWSHIP						
We have several cliques.	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Disagree	Undecided
It is difficult to join existing groups.	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
The priority should be meeting members' needs.	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Undecided	Disagree	Disagree
People are willing to start new groups.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
Church was recently involved in member conflict.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree
People in church are angry with others.	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
There is unresolved conflict in church.	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Undecided	Disagree	Disagree
People in church enjoy being together.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
I have fellowship regularly with members.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
New members are quickly invited to groups.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Church is unified.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree

FELLOWSHIP						
I enjoy the fellowship of other members.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
My voice is heard.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree
Pastor, church staff, and people have healthy relationships.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Open unrepentant sin is dealt with quickly.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
I am a part of a group that reaches others.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
I am excited to be a part of this church.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
It has become increasingly difficult to come to church.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Church is seen as very unified.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Our church has a good reputation.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I feel like I belong.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Visitors sometimes feel unwelcome.	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree
People are more interested in themselves than in reaching out.	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
Fellowship encourages people to live faithfully.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree

FELLOWSHIP						
I was quickly accepted when I began at this church.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
EVANGELISM						
People share faith regularly.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Church supports missionaries.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Church seeks out ways to reach people.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
Visitors feel welcome.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Small groups seek to reach people.	Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided
Church emphasizes church planting.	Undecided	Undecided	Disagree	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided
I have fears that keep me from sharing my faith.	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Undecided
Church hosts regular opportunities to do foreign missions.	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Undecided
Church is known plan for outreach.	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Agree
Church meets members' needs before others' needs.	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided
A church should not start a new church without surplus funds.	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Agree
Only people with the gift of evangelism should evangelize.	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree

EVANGELISM						
I attempt to establish relationships with the unchurched.	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Church provides regular opportunities for evangelism training.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
I have a few relationships with unbelievers.	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree
People accept Christ on a regular basis.	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Disagree	Agree	Undecided
Lifetime missionaries must be called.	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree
One purpose of small groups is evangelism.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
A portion of the budget is allocated for mission work.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
I make efforts to introduce myself to new people.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree
I share my faith regularly with lost people.	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Disagree
My pastor models personal evangelism.	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
More personal evangelism comes from more training.	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Disagree	Disagree
There are enough churches in our community.	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree

DISCIPLESHIP						
New members receive training and information when they join.	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Undecided
Our church does a very good job discipling.	Agree	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
We have many people involved in one-on-one discipling.	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Disagree	Disagree
I have grown as a Christian since being at this church.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agrees	Agree	Agree
People are given training on how to develop a prayer life and quiet time.	Agree	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
People are given opportunities to learn how to share or defend their faith.	Agree	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
Members' lifestyles are different from the world's.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
I know what I believe and why I believe it.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Mature Christians have a desire to help the less mature.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided
Someone personally disciplined me.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided

DISCIPLESHIP						
I feel prepared to disciple a new believer.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree
Believers are trained to give financially.	Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Undecided
People are trained how to read and interpret the Bible.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree
Discipleship classes are usually boring or irrelevant.	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Undecided	Undecided
PRAYER						
Intercessory prayer ministry includes many participants.	Agree	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Leadership regularly emphasizes prayer.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Thirty to sixty minutes a day for prayer is nearly impossible.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
Major efforts are first bathed in prayer.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Prayers for non-Christians are by name.	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Disagree	Disagree
Prayer is central in our services.	Agree	Agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Undecided	Agree
Church has special prayer emphases.	Agree	Agree	Strongly agree	Strongly agree	Agree	Agree
Prayer needs are made available.	Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Disagree

PRAYER						
Prayer is integral in classes and small groups.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
World missions are regularly prayed for.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
The ministries of the church are regularly prayed for.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Prayer during services is vital.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Regular prayer for leadership is made.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Prayer meetings are boring.	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
Prayer meetings = gossip times.	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
When we pray nothing happens.	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
There is a prayer room or place where people pray.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
Prayer should be a daily part of a Christian's life.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
I pray regularly during the day.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Strongly Agree
Answered prayers are communicated to the church.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
I believe that prayer works.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
I feel adequately trained in prayer.	Disagree	Undecided	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree

MINISTRY						
Getting involved in ministry in our church is difficult for me.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
Getting involved in ministry in our church is difficult for newcomers.	Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
Ministry in church is done by a small group.	Agree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Agree
There is creative freedom in ministry.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
I receive fulfillment by doing ministry in our church.	Strongly Agrees	Strongly Agrees	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
The leadership equips people to do ministry.	Agree	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
Church is strong in benevolence ministry.	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Undecided
Ministry is an avenue of outreach in our church.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
Ethnic background not a factor in ministry.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
When counseling is needed, people have options.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
I am willing to serve in the church.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided	Agree
Pastor challenges us to get involved.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree

WORSHIP						
A blend of music or worship styles is agreeable.	Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Worship is traditional.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Service time is just right.	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Sermon length is just right.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
The facility in which to worship is good.	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
People have trouble finding parking spaces.	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
Order of worship is liked.	Agree	Agree	Strongly agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
Services are prayerful.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
There is good participation in singing.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
Non-Christians are comfortable in our services.	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided	Agree	Agree
I like all the elements of our worship services.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
There are distractions in our services.	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree	Disagree
Comparatively, our services are among the best.	Disagree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
People make decisions in our services.	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree

WORSHIP						
There is a right emphasis on money in our services.	Undecided	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Agree
There is plenty of room for growth in our facility.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Agree	Undecided
Guests regularly attend our services.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided
Keeping everyone together in one morning service is best.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Undecided
My faith in God is strengthened by our services.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree
I am excited to invite others to our services.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Non-Christian faiths can worship God in the same way Christians do.	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
DOCTRINE						
The Bible is perfect as it was originally written.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
God intervenes in the lives of Christians.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Christ alone is the only way to Heaven.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Fellowship with God is only through the shed blood of Jesus Christ.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree

DOCTRINE						
God is a trinity.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
A good person of another faith other than Christianity may go to heaven.	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Hell is a literal place.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
God is in total control of our world.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Jesus is the Son of God.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
UNIQUE						
KJV is used in ministry.	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree
Lady church workers are required to wear dresses/skirts at church/events.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Agree	Agree
There is solo Pastor leadership.	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree
Church discipline is handled well.	Agree	Agree	Agree	Agree	Undecided	Undecided
Pastor preaches on Biblical standards and separation.	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
Church holds regular business meetings.	Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Agree	Agree
DESCRIPTORS						
Roles	Senior Pastor	Senior Pastor	Associate Pastor	Associate Pastor	Associate Pastor	Associate Pastor
Setting	Rural	Rural	Rural	Rural	Rural	Rural
Dates	2012	2022	2015	2022	2015	2022
Geography	South	South	South	South	South	South
Congregation Size	10	110	50	110	50	110

Vita

Pastor Brent Madaris was saved on May 12, 1982; shortly after, he surrendered to preach on July 18, 1982. Matthew 4:23 states, “And Jesus went about all Galilee, teaching in their synagogues, and preaching the gospel of the kingdom, and healing all manner of sickness and all manner of disease among the people.” It has been Pastor Madaris’ goal to live out the truth of this verse in his life. Preparation for this work and a brief description of the work follow.

Education

Ministry: Pastor Madaris holds a Master of Ministry and a Bachelor of Theology degree from Covington Theological Seminary, completing these degrees between 1990 and 1991. From July 2006 to May 2008, he studied at The Crown College/Seminary (External studies – Master of Ministry). He entered on-campus classes in September 2007 and graduated with a Master of Divinity in 2010. Since 2015, he has been pursuing a Doctor of Ministry degree at Pensacola Theological Seminary. The project presented in this paper is the conclusion of his Doctor of Ministry Studies.

Medicine: The healing ministry of Jesus put within Pastor Madaris’ heart a desire to engage in healthcare sciences. He completed an Associate of Arts in Physical Therapy, completed between 1985 and 1987. After that, he completed an Associate of Science in Nursing from Dalton College between 1987 and 1990. His Bachelor of Science in Nursing from West Georgia College came next, completed in 1993. Finally, Pastor Madaris earned a Master of Nursing with a specialization as a Family Nurse Practitioner from Emory University in Atlanta, GA, in 1994.

Teaching

From 1983 to 1985, he served as an assistant Sunday School teacher in a junior boys class. Then in 1985, he transitioned to the role of teacher, serving there until 1990. Concurrently, between 1985 and 1992, he directed a Children's Church ministry. In 1988, he expanded his teaching to include Bible classes for primary, middle, and high school students at a local Christian Day School. In 1993, he became an assistant teacher in the college/career Sunday School class. From 1994 to July 1996, he served as an assistant teacher in an Adult Auditorium Sunday School class. From July 1996 to December 1997, he was the teacher in an adult auditorium Sunday School class. Beginning January 1997 and continuing to March 1998, he taught a young adult Sunday School class.

Preaching

In January 2000, he started a church in his home, which eventually moved to the building of a nearby church that was closing. He remained at this church from May 2000 until June 2006. In May 2009, he founded Madaris Evangelistic Ministries, focusing on revival, evangelism, and missions, providing a platform for teaching various subjects such as Missionary Health and Wellness, History of the KJV, Creationism Apologetics, and Baptist History. In 2014, he pastored a revitalization work for one year. From 2015 to the present, he has been pastoring a replanted church. Over the past forty-two years, he has had the opportunity to preach in many churches. In May 2021 Pastor Madaris established Hometown Hope Ministries, Incorporated—a comprehensive Independent Baptist church revitalization ministry to assist churches in navigating the unique challenges of ministry today.

Healing

As a nurse practitioner for the last twenty-nine years, Pastor Madaris has had the privilege of working in many varied areas of healthcare, gaining a broad wealth of experience. In 1993 and 1994 he participated in two medical mission trips to Honduras, known as "Jungle 93" and "Aguanqueterique 94. In 1998, he participated in a mission trip to Haiti. In December 2019, he established Ministry Medicine International, LLC, a telemedicine company, for the benefit, primarily, of ministry and ministry-related personnel.

Writing

Believing that Jesus was also a writer, since He authored the best-selling Book of all time, Pastor Madaris has been inspired to write. In 2001, he published his first book, *The Lord Harkened Unto The Voice Of A Man*. In mid-2003, he began writing a column in a local paper titled *Ask the Pastor*, which eventually appeared in five local newspapers for about one and a half years. In January 2005, he started publishing *The Conservative Standard*, a monthly periodical addressing religious, political, medical, and current events. This project lasted for about four years. Since 2017, he has been writing the *Answers for the Heart* column in the newspaper local to his church.

That a strong literary foundation be laid for the work of revitalization in Independent Baptist churches is important. As the future unfolds, it is Pastor Madaris's desire to write and help lay the foundation for both present and future pastors, providing practical written works to assist in the greatest work the world has ever known: the work of the Lord Jesus—reaching and teaching souls within local churches.

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